

Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 3069–3192

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Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Technical Report 0029

Cover photo

MAHLI view of a fine-grained clastic rock outcrop broken by Curiosity's wheels (target named Gourdon). This is MAHLI focus merge product 3110MH0001930001101741R00, created onboard the instrument from a focus stack acquired on Sol 3110 (06 May 2021).

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7.1 Definitions and conventions

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Acknowledgements

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Note that pages are not numbered in this document because all of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, and *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* were inserted separately after creation using a word processing tool that differs from the one used for the text.

Abstract

Covering the time between Curiosity’s 3069th and 3192nd Martian days (sols) of operations in northern Gale crater, Mars, this document is a compilation of the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Principal Investigator’s notes and information about MAHLI images and activities conducted during that period. The report includes brief sol-by-sol notes—written as the mission unfolded—regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used and significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation. The document, further, contains information regarding range and scale (camera working distance and scale of in-focus elements of an image); the parent images, range, and scale information associated with each MAHLI focus merge product created onboard the instrument; and a description of the purpose and intent behind acquisition of each MAHLI image and creation of each onboard focus merge product. The MSL science team and rover engineers routinely used the information contained in this report during the course of the mission for tactical planning, strategic planning, and scientific analysis.

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction and purpose

This document is a compilation of the Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Principal Investigator's notes and information about MAHLI images and activities that occurred during the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) mission between Sols 3069 and 3192.

MAHLI is a 2-megapixel color camera with a focusable macro lens mounted on the turret at the end of a robotic arm aboard NASA's MSL rover, Curiosity (Edgett *et al.* 2012). The rover landed and began operation in northern Gale crater, Mars, on 6 August 2012 (Vasavada *et al.* 2014).

Each *Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook* covers a specific period corresponding to a release of MAHLI data to the NASA Planetary Data System (PDS) Imaging Node (<http://pds-imaging.jpl.nasa.gov/>). As some MAHLI data can arrive from Mars months or years after a given release period, the publication of these reports typically lags behind the PDS release schedule by a period that varies from one occasion to the next, depending largely on when data acquired during that period arrive on Earth and when we have time to complete the *Principal Investigator's Notebook* report.

This report, *Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 3069–3192*, corresponds to MAHLI data Release 28 in the NASA PDS archives. These are data acquired 25 March 2021 through 29 July 2021.

1.2 Versions and change log

The enclosed materials were compiled as the MSL mission unfolded. That being the case, we might sometimes have made errors. The reader should be aware that this report might be corrected via release of a new version in the future.

A new version would also be created if new data from this report's period (Martian sols) are received from the instrument after an earlier version has been made available. This can occur because MAHLI can store data onboard the instrument for weeks, months, and even years after acquisition. As a result, images are archived with the NASA PDS on the basis of when they are received on Earth, not when they are acquired on Mars.

Covering the Sol 3069 through 3192 period, this document is Version 1.

If this were a later version, this section would document the changes made relative to the previous.

2 Instrument activities for this period

This section captures day-by-day or sol-by-sol notes written by the MAHLI PI and PI's assistants, as the mission unfolded, regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used or significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 3069 – 3192						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Nontron drill site	25 Mar 21	3069	8	54	4	MAHLI imaged the Nontron Sample Discard Pile and the target Chassenon. The focus stack images were also merged.
	26 Mar 21	3070	60	60	0	A rover self-portrait was acquired to document the Nontron drill site near Mont Mercou.
	27 Mar 21	3071	7	19	0	During the day, MAHLI imaged the REMS UV Sensor and the target Chassenon. At night, MAHLI acquired a dark current assessment image to help with the Sol 3017 triboluminescence study and MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.
	28 Mar 21	3072	1	2	1	MAHLI imaged the Nontron drill cuttings and the Sol 3071 focus stack images were merged.
Exploration of Mont Mercou	30 Mar 21	3074	3	22	2	MAHLI imaged the target Bara Bahau and the focus stack images were merged.
Exploration of Mont Mercou	01 Apr 21	3076	3	22	2	MAHLI imaged the target Tursac and the focus stack images were merged.
	03 Apr 21	3078	10	54	0	MAHLI acquired the first part of a 2-sol activity for full rover wheel inspection (to image $\geq 360^\circ$ surface of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel). MAHLI also imaged the targets Garve and Scoor.
	04 Apr 21	3079	17	18	4	MAHLI imaged the target Garve and acquired the second part of a 2-sol activity for full rover wheel inspection (to image $\geq 360^\circ$ surface of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel). The focus stack images from Sol 3078 were merged as well.
	06 Apr 21	3081	3	23	2	MAHLI imaged the target Orliac and the focus stack images were merged.
	08 Apr 21	3083	3	23	2	MAHLI imaged the target Puymanjou and the focus stack images were merged.
	11 Apr 21	3085	12	75	0	MAHLI imaged the sky, with the dust cover open and closed for flat fielding, and the DRT-brushed target Peyrignac.
		3086	0	0	4	The focus stack images from Sol 3085 were merged.
13–14 Apr 21	3088	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the target Gout Rossignol and the focus stack images were merged. However, a stepper motor "skipping" issue occurred, which caused all reported motor counts (which are used to determine range and scale) to be incorrect. In addition, because of this anomaly, the images are not in sharp focus, although they are use-able.	
Bardou drill site on Mont Mercou	18 Apr 21	3092	7	50	4	MAHLI imaged the target Cussac and the intended drill target Bardou after the Sol 3090 DRT and a drill bit preload test; then the focus stack images were merged.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 3069 – 3192						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Bardou drill site on Mont Mercou	20 Apr 21	3094	3	6	0	Drill preparation activities at the planned Bardou sample extraction site. MAHLI imaged the intended site for the Bardou sample discard pile and the alternate and intended "Portion Characterization" sites.
	The Bardou sample was extracted using Curiosity's drill on Sol 3094. The MAHLI was not operated during the period that the drill bit assembly held the sample until sample analyses were complete. The sample held by the drill bit assembly was discarded on Sol 3102.					
	28 Apr 21	3102	6	13	0	MAHLI imaged the Bardou sample discard pile, the Bardou drill hole and the surfaces surrounding SAM inlet #2, with the inlet cover open, a follow-up to Bardou sample drop-offs.
	29 Apr 21	3103	0	0	0	<u>MAHLI mechanism fault</u> . A MAHLI mechanism fault left the dust cover in a partially open state.
Bardou drill site on Mont Mercou	01 May 21	3105	0	0	0	<u>MAHLI mechanism fault</u> . An attempt to complete dust cover opening and closure on sol 3105 resulted in an additional fault.
	04 May 21	3108	0	0	0	The Sol 3105 fault was studied, understood, and the dust cover was driven closed and into its launch restraint position.
Leaving Mont Mercou	06 May 21	3110	4	36	3	MAHLI imaged the target Gourdon and the focus stack images were merged.
	08–09 May 21	3112	7	61	5	MAHLI imaged the targets Pezuls and Le_Bugue and the focus stack images were merged.
	11–12 May 21	3115	7	51	4	MAHLI imaged the targets Biras and Quinsac and MAHLI acquired an image of the sky to inspect for dust on the lens following the Sol 3103 MAHLI mechanism fault. The focus stack images were also merged.
	13 May 21	3117	4	36	3	MAHLI imaged the target Busserolles and the focus stack images were merged.
	16 May 21	3119	13	70	5	MAHLI imaged the targets Monsec and Salagnac and the focus stack images were merged. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness. However, a stepper motor "skipping" issue occurred during the night-time imaging, which caused all reported motor counts (which are used to determine range and scale) to be incorrect relative to actual lens focus position for the CheMin inlet. Because of this anomaly, the CheMin inlet images are not in sharp focus.
Drive toward the Pontours drill site	18 May 21	3122	0	0	2	<u>MAHLI mechanism fault</u> . With the MAHLI camera head at ~25 cm above the surface, a mechanism fault occurred on Sol 3122 while the MAHLI dust cover was opening. None of the planned imaging occurred on Sol 3122. Since no new data were collected, the Salagnac focus stack images from Sol 3119 were merged a second time.
	21 May 21	3124	1	1	0	<u>MAHLI Fault Recovery Process</u> . MAHLI was presented by the robotic arm for Mastcam inspection, then the MAHLI was moved such that the robotic arm was in a shoulder-out staging pose ~1.25 m above the surface, with MAHLI pointed down, to help protect the front lens element (sapphire window) from dust settling from suspension and from the impact of potential saltating sand grains from below. With no MAHLI mechanism movement, MAHLI acquired an image at this 1.25 m standoff position to provide more data about lens focus position relative to the position of the mostly open dust cover. The reported motor count for the Sol 3124 image does not indicate actual focus position.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 3069 – 3192						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Drive toward the Pontours drill site	23 May 21	3126	0	0	0	<u>MAHLI Fault Recovery Process</u> . MAHLI attempted to close dust cover to recover from the Sol 3122 fault, but the instrument was marked “sick”. A Mastcam-100 image (3126MR1001020001402223C00) showed the cover to be physically closed by instrument could not confirm whether it was in launch restraint (launch lock).
	26 May 21	3129	0	0	0	<u>MAHLI Fault Recovery Process</u> . MAHLI attempted to ensure that the dust cover was closed and in launch restraint position but the sequence did not execute owing to an error.
	28 May 21	3131	0	0	0	<u>MAHLI Fault Recovery Process</u> . After running a sequence to close the cover, the MAHLI dust cover was confirmed to be closed and in launch restraint position.
	The MAHLI team decided to stand down from MAHLI operations while they and JPL engineers worked to understand appropriate paths forward. The faults and “skipping” events that occurred since Sol 3088 appeared to be related to thermal conditions (i.e., lubricant in the camera head mechanism likely too cold for morning and night operations since arrival at Mont Mercou); operation during the warmest part of the afternoon since Sol 3088 was always successful.					
Drive toward the Pontours drill site	05 Jun 21	3139	5	39	0	The MAHLI team decided to resume science and engineering operation but with a temporary restriction to operate in the warmest part of the afternoon between local times of 14:00 to 17:00. For Sol 3139, MAHLI imaged targets Beauronne and Cladech. These were successful and concluded without incident.
	05 Jun 21	3140	0	0	3	Focus stack images from Sol 3139 were merged.
	08 Jun 21	3142	6	47	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Minzac and Terrasson Lavilledieu.
	09 Jun 21	3143	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 3142 were merged.
	10 Jun 21	3144	8	63	0	MAHLI imaged the REMS UV Sensor and the targets Plaisance and Sarlande.
	11 Jun 21	3145	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3144 were merged.
	12 Jun 21	3146	6	50	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Monpazier and Nabirat.
	13 Jun 21	3147	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 3146 were merged.
	27 Jun 21	3160	6	50	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Simeyrols and Rouffignac.
28 Jun 21	3161	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 3160 were merged.	
Pontours drill site	04 Jul 21	3167	8	53	4	MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Pontours before and after DRT and a drill bit preload test; then the focus stack images were merged.
	05 Jul 21	3168	3	6	0	Drill preparation activities at the planned Pontours sample extraction site. MAHLI imaged the alternate and intended "Portion Characterization" sites and the intended site for the Pontours sample discard pile.
	The Pontours sample was extracted using Curiosity’s drill on Sol 3170 . The MAHLI was not operated during the period that the drill bit assembly held the sample until sample analyses were complete. The sample held by the drill bit assembly was discarded on Sol 3178 .					
	15 Jul 21	3178	9	19	0	MAHLI imaged the Pontours sample discard pile, the Pontours drill hole and the surfaces surrounding SAM inlet #2, with the inlet cover open, a follow-up to Pontours sample drop-offs. Then, MAHLI imaged the target Chanterac.
	17 Jul 21	3180	7	54	5	MAHLI imaged the Pontours Sample Discard Pile and the target Chanterac. The focus stack images were also merged.
	18 Jul 21	3181	1	2	0	MAHLI imaged the Pontours Drill Cuttings.
Drive toward the Maria Gordon drill site	20 Jul 21	3183	4	32	3	A new camera head heating strategy went into effect that allows MAHLI imaging resume being acquired at any time of day. In addition, MAHLI imaged the target Montagenet and the focus stack images were merged.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 3069 – 3192						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Drive toward the Maria Gordon drill site	22 Jul 21	3185	3	25	2	MAHLI imaged the target Javerlhac and the focus stack images were merged.
	24 Jul 21	3187	8	64	0	MAHLI imaged the target Chauffour after DRT and the target Le Manet.
	25 Jul 21	3188	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 3187 were merged.
	27 Jul 21	3190	3	25	2	MAHLI imaged the target Fressignas and the focus stack images were merged.
	29 Jul 21	3192	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the targets Champeaux and Ezyerac and the focus stack images were merged.

3 Helpful tips

3.1 MAHLI instrument and investigation

Please refer to Edgett *et al.* (2012) for a description of the MAHLI instrument and investigation, Edgett *et al.* (2015) for information about the characterization and calibration of the instrument, and Yingst *et al.* (2016) for some of the lessons learned after ~1.5 Mars years of surface operations. Additional information on how the instrument and data have been used is in the paper by Minitti *et al.* (2013) and the extended abstract by Garvin *et al.* (2017).

3.2 MAHLI image IDs

MAHLI images and onboard focus merge products are identified by their image IDs. The following figure describes the information content of these IDs.

Note that raw images released within minutes of receipt on Earth to the public via the JPL-Caltech web site (<http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/>) do not necessarily have the correct, final, archival image IDs.

MAHLI Image IDs

- This is the only official, correct, archival image ID scheme.
- Raw Images released rapidly at <http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/> do not always give you the correct, archival image ID.

0132MH0001580010101221C00

sol → 0132

camera
MH = MAHLI → MH

CDPID
a.k.a. MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID → 000158001

product type
as received from Mars → C00

sequence ID → 000158001

order in sequence
usually, first = 0, second = 1, etc. → 0101

CDPID counter
How many times the following CDPID has been used since landing → 01

version
version received on Earth
0 = parent image on Mars → 221

GOP counter
for video Group of Pictures (JPEG video frames) → C00

Note that, for onboard focus merge products, the sol is the sol that the merge took place. This is not always on the same sol that the parent images were acquired.

The MAHLI team pays most attention to the items in yellow. In a focus stack, the images are acquired in order of increasing CDPID.

Product type tells you about the image as received from Mars; not necessarily the image you are looking at, if it has been further processed, uncompressed, or recompressed on Earth.

The NASA PDS archives include documentation that describes the MAHLI image ID and file naming scheme and the nature of the archived Experiment Data Record (EDR) and Reduced Data Record (RDR) products (Malin *et al.*, 2013).

The EDR products, the raw data product, have the following file name scheme:

- 1 **[Image ID]_XXXX** – these are always 8-bit images except for the 16-bit products (type A) returned from MAHLI for calibration purposes.

The RDR products are of the following nature:

- 2 **[Image ID]_DRXX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated color images,
- 3 **[Image ID]_DRLX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated and geometric calibrated color images,
- 4 **[Image ID]_DRCX** – 8-bit relative radiometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied, and
- 5 **[Image ID]_DRCL** – 8-bit relative radiometric and geometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied.

The following table describes the variety of image types (raw, lossless, JPEG, focus merge, thumbnail, *etc.*). Malin *et al.* (2013) described these in greater detail.

product type	product format
A	raster 16-bit image
B	raster 8-bit image
C	lossless compressed image
D	JPEG grayscale image
E	JPEG 4:2:2 color image
F	JPEG 4:4:4 color image
G	raster thumbnail of parent image
H	JPEG gray thumbnail of parent image
I	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of parent image
J	raster 8-bit video frame
K	lossless compressed video frame
L	JPEG grayscale video frame
M	JPEG 4:2:2 color video frame
N	JPEG 4:4:4 color video frame
O	raster 8-bit thumbnail of video frame
P	JPEG gray thumbnail of video frame
Q	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of video frame
R	focus merge best focus image product
S	focus merge range map product
T	focus merge best focus thumbnail
U	focus merge range map thumbnail

Types R and T are JPEG 4:4:4; S and U are JPEG grayscale products.

3.3 MAHLI LED positions

The MAHLI camera head has two groups of two white light LEDs (Edgett *et al.* 2012), called Group 1 and Group 2. For reference, the figure below shows their location on the camera head and how these locations translate to positions relative to pixel 0,0 (column 0, row 0) on the MAHLI CCD. In addition, MAHLI has two 365 nm ultraviolet (UV) LEDs, also shown in the figure. Each group of two LEDs (Group 1, Group 2, and UV) can be operated together or independently with each of the other two groups. When the LEDs are used, which group was operated is reported in the RATIONALE_DESC description of the image intent and purpose (**Section 6**).

MAHLI image TVC_MH0809080020000032B00, left, shows the violet and white reflections of the UV and Group 1 and Group 2 white light LEDs, indicating their location in relation to the CCD's pixel at column 0, row 0. The photograph on the right shows the camera head with its dust cover open and LEDs labeled.

4 Camera range and scale information

4.1 Purpose and description

MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* (or “Distance and Scale Information Sheets”) describe **(a)** the distance between the MAHLI camera and an imaged target, and **(b)** the scale of in-focus features in the image, based on knowledge of that distance. Usually, these are determined using the camera’s stepper motor count focus position (Edgett *et al.* 2015).

These information sheets were created only for cases in which there was a need. Cases for which they are not usually created include those when the only MAHLI image(s) acquired on a given sol are **(a)** views of the landscape, focused at infinity; **(b)** intended to make a rover self-portrait mosaic; **(c)** sky flat field calibration data; or **(d)** routinely-acquired images of the rover wheels for inspection purposes.

For the Sol 3069–3192 period, *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were created for the following **Sols: 3069, 3071, 3072, 3074, 3076, 3078, 3079, 3081, 3083, 3085, 3088, 3092, 3094, 3102, 3110, 3112, 3115, 3117, 3119, 3124, 3139, 3142, 3144, 3146, 3160, 3167, 3168, 3178, 3180, 3181, 3183, 3185, 3187, 3190, 3192.**

The origin of the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was in the need for a rapid, tactical response from the MAHLI team to the Curiosity Rover Planners—the engineers tasked with operating the rover’s mobility and robotic arm systems—for range-finding and image scale information derived from MAHLI’s autofocus and focus merge capabilities. As described by Minitti *et al.* (2013), during the rover’s first sample extraction campaign, conducted at the Rocknest eolian sand deposit in October–November 2012, the engineers elected to use MAHLI autofocus sub-frames to confirm their estimates of the range to the sand surface for subsequent scoop placement (Anderson *et al.* 2015). These *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were borne of that effort to provide the information almost as soon as the data arrived on Earth.

Presented in this section are the latest versions of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, for the above stated sols, as of the date of this *MAHLI Technical Report* publication. Most of these sheets were actively used during the MSL mission for tactical and strategic planning, as well as for the scientific analyses. Note that some of the sheets exhibit slightly different formatting from each other, as the formatting and content evolved over time.

The image IDs presented in these Information Sheets are the identifiers of the best, least-compressed version of the image received from Mars for a given camera position for the stated purpose (autofocus, imaging, range-finding, etc.). In cases for which only a thumbnail version of the image was received, the image ID is colored orange.

4.2 Formulae

4.2.1 Working distance

The working distance (d_w , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was computed from the empirical relationship between working distance and motor count for the flight unit MAHLI when the dust cover is open (m_{open}) described by Edgett *et al.* (2015):

$$d_w = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For the dust cover closed case (m_{closed}), Edgett *et al.* (2015) found that m_{closed} is related to m_{open} as follows:

$$m_{closed} = 17075 - m_{open}. \quad (2)$$

4.2.2 Standoff distance (RP distance; MAHLI toolframe +X distance)

The standoff distance (d_s , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* is 1.9 cm less than the MAHLI working distance (Edgett *et al.* 2015). Note that “standoff distance” is equivalent to “RP distance” and “MAHLI toolframe +X distance”; see **Section 7.1**). It is determined by subtracting 1.9 cm from the working distance (d_w) computed from motor count:

$$d_s = d_w - 1.9 \text{ cm} \quad (3)$$

4.2.3 Distance or range uncertainty estimate

Estimation approach applied to the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

For the Sol 0–945 period (except Sol 687), the uncertainty in distance (whether expressed as d_w or d_s) was estimated using an early version of our team’s understanding (Edgett *et al.* 2013) of the flight unit MAHLI depth of field (DOF; d_{old_DOF} , in centimeters) as a function of working distance (d_w).

The method for estimating the far range of the DOF, d_{old_far} , was:

$$d_{old_far} = ad_w^5 - bd_w^4 + cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 + ed_w - f \quad (4)$$

in which $a = 2.067963396 \times 10^{-10}$, $b = 5.81503025785 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 1.55563715379086 \times 10^{-5}$, $d = 1.78558768966003 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 7.87243271888297 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 3.57047935299353 \times 10^{-2}$.

The method for estimating the near range of the DOF, d_{old_near} , was:

$$d_{old_near} = -(ad_w^5 + bd_w^4 - cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 - ed_w + f) \quad (5)$$

in which $a = -9.6497783 \times 10^{-12}$, $b = 1.06050131902 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 5.8615047292452 \times 10^{-6}$, $d = 2.42284468424977 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 4.28714139095939 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 7.534391000189 \times 10^{-4}$.

The MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* added the absolute values of the near and far DOF, then divided by two, to provide an overall uncertainty, $\pm d_{old_DOF}$, in centimeters:

$$\pm d_{old_DOF} = ((-d_{old_near}) + d_{old_far})/2 \quad (6)$$

The $\pm d_{old_DOF}$ estimate was sufficient for using MAHLI as a range finder for subsequent scoop placement during the Rocknest sample extraction campaign (Minitti *et al.* 2013; Anderson *et al.* 2015).

Improved estimation method, used for Sol 687 and after Sol 945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

Later analysis refined our DOF estimate (Edgett *et al.* 2015), but these results arrived too late to be incorporated into most of the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*. That said, for small working distances (*e.g.*, < 20 cm), the results are about the same. As a function of dust cover open focus motor count (m_{open}), the near (d_{near}) and far (d_{far}) depth of field can be expressed, in centimeters, as:

$$d_{near} \text{ or } d_{far} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

in which, for d_{near} , $a = 1.03565$, $b = -11.9083$, $c = 2.82403 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.29003 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.34332 \times 10^{-12}$; and, for d_{far} , $a = 1.03438$, $b = -11.4118$, $c = 2.69297 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.17752 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.02494 \times 10^{-12}$.

4.2.4 Pixel scale

The estimated pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel) is based on working distance (d_w) and applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. We estimate the scale from the working distance (d_w) as described by Edgett *et al.* (2012):

$$p = 6.9001 + 3.5201d_w. \quad (8)$$

4.2.5 Pixel scale uncertainty estimate

No estimation applied to the Sol 0–998 range and scale information sheets

No estimate of pixel scale uncertainty was applied to the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* until Sol 999.

Estimation approach

Pixel scale uncertainty (p_{far} , p_{near} , $\pm p_{uncertainty}$, in μm per pixel) can be estimated based on the depth of field (d_{far} , d_{near} , in centimeters; **Equation 7**) and pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel, **Equation 8**) as determined from working distance (d_w , in centimeters; **Equation 1**). The uncertainty applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. The uncertainty can be estimated as follows (please round $\pm p_{uncertainty}$ to the nearest 0.1 μm per pixel):

$$p_{far} = (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{far})) - p, \quad (9)$$

$$p_{near} = p - (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{near})), \text{ and} \quad (10)$$

$$\pm p_{uncertainty} = (p_{far} + p_{near})/2. \quad (11)$$

4.2.6 Image dimensions estimate

The image dimension estimates described in the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* are computed by multiplying the estimated pixel scale (p) by the number of horizontal (columns) and vertical (rows) covered by the image. This simplistic approach, of course, assumes that the target is a plane parallel to the CCD.

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3069 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)			
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)		
Nontron sample discard pile															
mhl00122	medium-resolution	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3069MH0001220011101177C00	1177	13937	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
mhl00122	medium-resolution	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3069MH0001220011101179C00	1179	13924	7.4	5.5	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9		
target named Chassenon															
mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	APXS raster spot 3														
	3069MH0007060011101181C00	1181	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00763	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 3														
	3069MH0007630011101184C00	1184	13985	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3069MH0001530001101236R00				range map product:						3069MH0001530001101237S00	
mhl00794	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm													
	APXS raster spot 3														
	3069MH0007940011101195C00	1195	15091	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3069MH0001530001101234R00				range map product:						3069MH0001530001101235S00	
mhl00763	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3069MH0007630011101206C00	1206	13976	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3069MH0001530001101232R00				range map product:						3069MH0001530001101233S00	
mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3069MH0007060011101217C00	1217	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00721	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3069MH0007210011101220C00	1220	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3069MH0001530001101230R00				range map product:						3069MH0001530001101231S00	

Sol 3071 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

REMS UV sensor													
mhl00095	standard viewing position	intended standoff: ~15 cm											
	3071MH0008250001101299C00	1299	13258	16.8	14.9	-0.7	0.8	65.9	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9

target named Chassenon															
mhl00763	medium-r resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 4 3071MH0007630011101301C00	1301	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3072MH0002580001101319R00				range map product:						3072MH0002580001101320S00	

dark current image - at night - in support of the sol 3017 triboluminescence investigation - dust cover closed - 60 second exposure													
Note: Where the Motor Count is given in blue font, the dust cover was closed during imaging; please use caution in interpreting the range and scale information, as the results are less certain.													
mhl00826	Full frame acquired with no mechanism motion												
	3071MH0008260001101311C00	1311	0	0-0	-1-0	0-0	0-0	0-1	0-1	1608	1198	1-6	1-2

CheMin sample inlet - at night with its cover open - deep imaging to check cleanliness state of mesh, funnel, funnel throat													
intended working distance to mesh is 12.4 cm; to funnel throat is 16.3 cm - for scale, note that mesh diameter is 3.5 cm													
mhl00312	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 1 of 3 to inspect funnel throat												
	manual focus 3071MH0003120001101312C00	1312	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
mhl00326	image focused at mesh												
	manual focus 3071MH0003120011101313C00	1313	13458	12.5	10.6	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.5	1024	1024	5.2	5.2
mhl00326	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 2 of 3 to inspect funnel throat												
	manual focus 3071MH0003260001101314C00	1314	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
mhl00326	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 3 of 3 to inspect funnel throat												
	manual focus 3071MH0003260001101315C00	1315	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6

CheMin sample inlet - at night with its cover open - overview of entire inlet													
intended working distance to inlet is ~19 cm - for scale, note that mesh diameter is 3.5 cm													
mhl00228	manual focus	intended distance: ~19 cm											
	3071MH0002280001101316C00	1316	13182	19.1	17.2	-0.9	1.0	74.0	3.4	1608	1198	11.9	8.9

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3072 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information*

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

Nontrondrill hole cuttings

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhl00122	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3072MH0001220011101318C00	1318	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3074 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Bara_Bahau													
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3074MH0001900011101322C00	1322	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1
mhl00168	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3074MH0001680011101324C00	1324	14023	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3074MH0002650001101345R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3074MH0002650001101346S00							
mhl00168	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3074MH0001680011101334C00	1334	14031	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3074MH0002650001101343R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3074MH0002650001101344S00							

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3076 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Tursac													
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3076MH0001900011101348C00	1348	13005	27.3	25.4	-1.9	2.1	102.9	7.0	1608	1198	16.5	12.3
mhl00306	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3076MH0003060011101350C00	1350	13952	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3076MH0002650001101371R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3076MH0002650001101372S00							
mhl00306	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3076MH0003060011101360C00	1360	13964	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3076MH0002650001101369R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3076MH0002650001101370S00							

Sol 3078 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 1 of 5 (performed on sols 3078 and 3079)

mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm											
	3078MH0007690011101373E01	1373	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm											
	3078MH0007700011101374E01	1374	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm											
	3078MH0007710011101375E01	1375	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm											
	3078MH0007720011101376E01	1376	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

target named Garve - bedform trough

mhl00706	context view													
	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3078MH0007060011101378C00	1378	13031	25.7	23.8	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	1608	1198	15.7	11.7	
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-1													
	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3078MH0007630011101381C00	1381	14181	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3	
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3079MH0007070001101451R00				<i>range map product:</i>				3079MH0007070001101452S00	
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-2													
	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3078MH0007630011101392C00	1392	14197	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2	
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3079MH0007070001101449R00				<i>range map product:</i>				3079MH0007070001101450S00	

target named Scoor - bedform crest

mhl00706	context view													
	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3078MH0007060011101403C00	1403	13024	26.1	24.2	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8	
mhl00709	medium-resolution stereo-1													
	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3078MH0007090011101406C00	1406	14126	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4	
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3079MH0007070001101447R00				<i>range map product:</i>				3079MH0007070001101448S00	
mhl00709	medium-resolution stereo-2													
	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3078MH0007090011101417C00	1417	14160	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3	
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3079MH0007070001101445R00				<i>range map product:</i>				3079MH0007070001101446S00	

Sol 3079 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Garve - bedform trough

mhl00122	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3079MH0001220011101428C00	1428	14205	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 2 of 5 (performed on sols 3078 and 3079)

mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel	intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm											
	manual focus 3079MH0007690011101429E01	1429	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel	intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm											
	manual focus 3079MH0007700011101430E01	1430	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel	intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm											
	manual focus 3079MH0007710011101431E01	1431	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel	intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm											
	manual focus 3079MH0007720011101432E01	1432	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 3 of 5 (performed on sols 3078 and 3079)

mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel	intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm											
	manual focus 3079MH0007690011101433E01	1433	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel	intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm											
	manual focus 3079MH0007700011101434E01	1434	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel	intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm											
	manual focus 3079MH0007710011101435E01	1435	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel	intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm											
	manual focus 3079MH0007720011101436E01	1436	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 4 of 5 (performed on sols 3078 and 3079)

mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel	intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm											
	manual focus 3079MH0007690011101437E01	1437	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel	intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm											
	manual focus 3079MH0007700011101438E01	1438	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel	intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm											
	manual focus 3079MH0007710011101439E01	1439	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel	intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm											
	manual focus 3079MH0007720011101440E01	1440	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 5 of 5 (performed on sols 3078 and 3079)

mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel	intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm											
	manual focus 3079MH0007690011101441E01	1441	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel	intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm											
	manual focus 3079MH0007700011101442E01	1442	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel	intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm											
	manual focus 3079MH0007710011101443E01	1443	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel	intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm											
	manual focus 3079MH0007720011101444E01	1444	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

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Sol 3081 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Orliac													
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3081MH0007060011101454C00	1454	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0
mhl00299	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3081MH0002990011101457C00	1457	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3081MH0002650001101478R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3081MH0002650001101479S00						
mhl00299	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3081MH0002990011101467C00	1467	14014	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3081MH0002650001101476R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3081MH0002650001101477S00						

last update: 13_May_2021

Sol 3083 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Puymangou													
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3083MH0007060011101481C00	1481	13002	27.5	25.6	-1.9	2.2	103.6	7.1	1608	1198	16.7	12.4
mhl00152	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3083MH0001520011101484C00	1484	13957	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3083MH0002650001101505R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3083MH0002650001101506S00							
mhl00152	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3083MH0001520011101494C00	1494	13944	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3083MH0002650001101503R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3083MH0002650001101504S00							

Sol 3085 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover closed - first set

mhl00712	close focus - ~2.04 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
	3085MH0007120001101507C00	1507	0	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	2 cm standoff equivalent - ~3.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
	3085MH0007120011101508C00	1508	2412	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	5 cm standoff equivalent - ~6.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
	3085MH0007120021101509C00	1509	3078	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	25 cm standoff equivalent - ~26.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
3085MH0007120031101510C00	1510	4062	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a		
infinity focus - manual focus														
3085MH0007120041101511C00	1511	4488	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a		

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover open - first set

mhl00453	close focus - ~2.04 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
	3085MH0004530001101512C00	1512	15996	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	2 cm standoff equivalent - ~3.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
	3085MH0004530011101513C00	1513	14664	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	5 cm standoff equivalent - ~6.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
	3085MH0004530021101514C00	1514	13998	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	25 cm standoff equivalent - ~26.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
3085MH0004530031101515C00	1515	13014	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a		
pre-launch flat field equivalent - ~63.3 cm working distance focus position - manual focus														
3085MH0004530041101516C00	1516	12750	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a		
infinity focus - manual focus														
3085MH0004530051101517C00	1517	12552	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a		

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover open - second set (camera rotated approximately 180° relative to first set)

mhl00453	close focus - ~2.04 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
	3085MH0004530001101518C00	1518	15996	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	2 cm standoff equivalent - ~3.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
	3085MH0004530011101519C00	1519	14664	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	5 cm standoff equivalent - ~6.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
	3085MH0004530021101520C00	1520	13998	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	25 cm standoff equivalent - ~26.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
3085MH0004530031101521C00	1521	13014	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a		
pre-launch flat field equivalent - ~63.3 cm working distance focus position - manual focus														
3085MH0004530041101522C00	1522	12750	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a		
infinity focus - manual focus														
3085MH0004530051101523C00	1523	12552	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a		

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover closed - second set (camera rotated approximately 180° relative to first set)

mhl00712	close focus - ~2.04 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
	3085MH0007120001101524C00	1524	0	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	2 cm standoff equivalent - ~3.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
	3085MH0007120011101525C00	1525	2412	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	5 cm standoff equivalent - ~6.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
	3085MH0007120021101526C00	1526	3078	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
	25 cm standoff equivalent - ~26.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
3085MH0007120031101527C00	1527	4062	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a		
infinity focus - manual focus														
3085MH0007120041101528C00	1528	4488	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a		

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target named Peyrignac - after DRT - quantitative relief model (QRM) data													
mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3085MH0007060011101530C00	1530	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00721	med res - stereo-1 & relief model position 1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2												
	3085MH0007210011101533C00	1533	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3086MH0001530001101588R00	range map product:				3086MH0001530001101589S00					
mhli00721	med res - stereo-2 & relief model position 2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2												
	3085MH0007210011101544C00	1544	14001	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3086MH0001530001101586R00	range map product:				3086MH0001530001101587S00					
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 3	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2												
	3085MH0007050011101555C00	1555	14001	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 4	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2												
	3085MH0007050011101557C00	1557	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 5	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2												
	3085MH0007050011101559C00	1559	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhli00795	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2												
	3085MH0007950011101561C00	1561	14692	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3086MH0001530001101584R00	range map product:				3086MH0001530001101585S00					
mhli00721	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 1												
	3085MH0007210011101572C00	1572	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3086MH0001530001101582R00	range map product:				3086MH0001530001101583S00					

last update: 14_April_2021

Sol 3088 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Gout_Rossignol - images are not in sharp focus and reported motor counts do not indicate actual focus position, image range, or image scale

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3088MH0001900011101591C00	1591	13356	14.4	12.5	0.6	0.6	57.7	2.0	1608	1198	9.2	6.9
	<i>our best estimate:</i>			~26.9	~25.0	~2.9	~8.6	~101.6	~20.3			~16.3	~12.2
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3088MH0001730011101593C00	1593	14421	4.7	2.8	0.2	0.2	23.5	0.3	1608	1198	3.8	2.8
	<i>our best estimate:</i>			~6.8	~4.9	~0.2	~0.2	~31.0	~0.6			~5.0	~3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>		3088MH0001930001101626R00				<i>range map product:</i>		3088MH0001930001101627S00			
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3088MH0001730011101603C00	1603	14418	4.7	2.8	0.2	0.2	23.5	0.3	1608	1198	3.8	2.8
	<i>our best estimate:</i>			~6.9	~5.0	~0.2	~0.2	~31.0	~0.6			~5.0	~3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>		3088MH0001930001101624R00				<i>range map product:</i>		3088MH0001930001101625S00			
mhl00176	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm											
	3088MH0001760011101613C00	1613	15115	2.8	0.9	0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
	<i>our best estimate:</i>			~3.8	~1.9	~0.1	~0.1	~20.3	~0.3			~3.3	~2.4
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>		3088MH0001930001101622R00				<i>range map product:</i>		3088MH0001930001101623S00			

Our best estimates are based on subtraction of 420 motor counts from reported values, based on final reported motor count when dust cover was closed and homed.

last update: 19_April_2021

Sol 3092 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Cussac													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3092MH0001900011101629C00	1629	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00168	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3092MH0001680011101631C00	1631	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3092MH0001530001101684R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3092MH0001530001101685S00					

intended drill target named Bardou - after sol 3090 DRT													
mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3092MH0007060011101641C00	1641	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00763	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3092MH0007630011101644C00	1644	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3092MH0001530001101682R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3092MH0001530001101683S00					
mhli00763	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3092MH0007630011101655C00	1655	13995	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3092MH0001530001101680R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3092MH0001530001101681S00					
mhli00813	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm										
	3092MH0008130011101666C00	1666	14671	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3092MH0001530001101678R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3092MH0001530001101679S00					

intended drill target named Bardou - after sol 3090 DRT - after drill bit pre-load test													
mhli00465	context view		intended standoff - 35 cm										
	3092MH0004650011101677C00	1677	12894	36.6	34.7	-3.3	4.0	135.7	12.7	1608	1198	21.8	16.3

last update: 20_April_2021

Sol 3094 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

intended sample discard site for planned Bardou drill sample

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3094MH0001900011101687C00	1687	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1

alternate portion characterization site for planned Bardou drill sample

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00197	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3094MH0001970011101689C00	1689	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0

intended portion characterization site for planned Bardou drill sample

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00197	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3094MH0001970011101691C00	1691	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0

last update: 28_April_2021

Sol 3102 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

*Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

Bardou sample discard pile

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00197	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3102MH0001970011101693C00	1693	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1

Bardou drill hole

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00197	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3102MH0001970011101695C00	1695	13023	26.2	24.3	-1.7	1.9	99.0	6.5	1608	1198	15.9	11.9
mhli00774	intermediate-resolution view		intended standoff - 10 cm										
	3102MH0007740011101697C00	1697	13538	11.3	9.4	-0.4	0.4	46.7	1.3	1608	1198	7.5	5.6

SAM sample inlet 2 - cover open - after sample drop-off - inspect surface surrounding inlet perimeter

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00779	full-frame using manual focus		intended standoff - 20 cm										
	3102MH0007790011101698C00	1698	13080	23.1	21.2	-1.4	1.5	88.3	5.0	1608	1198	14.2	10.6
	full-frame based on 128 x 128 autofocus sub-frame (starting pixel 1008, 768)												
	3102MH0007790031101700C00	1700	13100	22.2	20.3	-1.3	1.4	85.1	4.7	1608	1198	13.7	10.2

Bardou sample discard pile

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00122	medium-resolution APXS raster spot 1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3102MH0001220011101702C00	1702	13958	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
mhli00122	medium-resolution APXS raster spot 2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3102MH0001220011101704C00	1704	13963	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8

last update: 10_May_2021

Sol 3110 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Gourdon													
mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3110MH0007060011101706C00	1706	13009	27.0	25.1	-1.8	2.1	102.0	6.9	1608	1198	16.4	12.2
mhli00723	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3110MH0007230011101709C00	1709	13905	7.5	5.6	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.4	4.0
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3110MH0001930001101745R00			range map product:			3110MH0001930001101746S00	
mhli00723	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3110MH0007230011101720C00	1720	13909	7.5	5.6	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	4.0
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3110MH0001930001101743R00			range map product:			3110MH0001930001101744S00	
mhli00797	high resolution view		intended standoff - 3 cm										
	3110MH0007970011101731C00	1731	14251	5.4	3.5	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.1
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3110MH0001930001101741R00			range map product:			3110MH0001930001101742S00	

last update: 10_May_2021

Sol 3112 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Pezuls**

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3112MH0007060011101748C00	1748	13010	27.0	25.1	-1.8	2.1	101.8	6.9	1608	1198	16.4	12.2	
mhli00740	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3112MH0007400011101751C00	1751	13953	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.8	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3112MH0002270001101816R00				range map product:					3112MH0002270001101817S00
mhli00740	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3112MH0007400011101762C00	1762	13958	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3112MH0002270001101814R00				range map product:					3112MH0002270001101815S00
mhli00800	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3112MH0008000011101773C00	1773	14618	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3112MH0002270001101812R00				range map product:					3112MH0002270001101813S00

target named **Le_Bugue**

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3112MH0007060011101784C00	1784	13013	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1	
mhli00740	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3112MH0007400011101787C00	1787	14118	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3112MH0002270001101810R00				range map product:					3112MH0002270001101811S00
mhli00740	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3112MH0007400011101798C00	1798	14118	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3112MH0002270001101808R00				range map product:					3112MH0002270001101809S00

last update: 12_May_2021

Sol 3115 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Biras

mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3115MH0007060011101819C00	1819	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
mhl00721	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3115MH0007210011101822C00	1822	13978	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3115MH0001530001101875R00				range map product:					3115MH0001530001101876S00	
mhl00721	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3115MH0007210011101833C00	1833	13982	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3115MH0001530001101873R00				range map product:					3115MH0001530001101874S00	

target named Quinsac

mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3115MH0007060011101844C00	1844	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
mhl00708	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3115MH0007080011101847C00	1847	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3115MH0001530001101871R00				range map product:					3115MH0001530001101872S00	
mhl00708	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3115MH0007080011101858C00	1858	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3115MH0001530001101869R00				range map product:					3115MH0001530001101870S00	

MAHLI diagnostic imaging following Sol 3103 mechanism fault - sky image to inspect lens cleanliness

mhl00573	close focus - ~2.04 cm working distance focus position - manual focus												
	3115MH0005730011101868C00	1868	15996	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a

last update: 14_May_2021

Sol 3117 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Busserolles													
mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3117MH0007060011101878C00	1878	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0
mhli00723	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3117MH0007230011101881C00	1881	14030	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3117MH0001930001101917R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3117MH0001930001101918S00				
mhli00723	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3117MH0007230011101892C00	1892	14034	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3117MH0001930001101915R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3117MH0001930001101916S00				
mhli00785	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm										
	3117MH0007850011101903C00	1903	15183	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3117MH0001930001101913R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3117MH0001930001101914S00				

Sol 3119 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)		

target named Monsec - before DRT													
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3119MH0001900011101920C00	1920	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1
mhl00122	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3119MH0001220011101922C00	1922	13982	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8

target named Monsec - after DRT															
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3119MH0007060011101924C00	1924	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
mhl00723	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3119MH0007230011101927C00	1927	13980	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3119MH0002270001101992R00				range map product:				3119MH0002270001101993S00		
mhl00723	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3119MH0007230011101938C00	1938	13984	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3119MH0002270001101990R00				range map product:				3119MH0002270001101991S00		
mhl00802	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3119MH0008020011101949C00	1949	14635	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3119MH0002270001101988R00				range map product:				3119MH0002270001101989S00		

target named Salagnac															
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3119MH0007060011101960C00	1960	13026	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	1608	1198	15.8	11.8		
mhl00723	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3119MH0007230011101963C00	1963	14143	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.4		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3119MH0002270001101986R00				range map product:				3119MH0002270001101987S00		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3122MH0002650001102001R00				range map product:				3122MH0002650001102002S00			
mhl00723	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3119MH0007230011101974C00	1974	14148	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3119MH0002270001101984R00				range map product:				3119MH0002270001101985S00		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3122MH0002650001101999R00				range map product:				3122MH0002650001102000S00			

CheMin sample inlet - at night with its cover open - deep imaging to check cleanliness state of mesh, funnel, funnel throat - images are not in sharp focus and reported motor counts do not indicate actual focus position, image range, or image scale

intended working distance to mesh is 12.4 cm; to funnel throat is 16.3 cm - for scale, note that mesh diameter is 3.5 cm

mhl00312	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 1 of 3 to inspect funnel throat		intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm										
	manual focus		intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm										
	3119MH0003120001101994C00	1994	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
mhl00326	image focused at mesh		intended distance to mesh: 12.4 cm										
	manual focus		intended distance to mesh: 12.4 cm										
	3119MH0003120011101995C00	1995	13458	12.5	10.6	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.5	1024	1024	5.2	5.2
mhl00326	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 2 of 3 to inspect funnel throat		intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm										
	manual focus		intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm										
	3119MH0003260001101996C00	1996	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
mhl00326	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 2 of 3 to inspect funnel throat		intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm										
	manual focus		intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm										
3119MH0003260001101997C00	1997	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6	

CheMin sample inlet - at night with its cover open - overview of entire inlet - images are not in sharp focus and reported motor counts do not indicate actual focus position, image range or image scale

intended working distance to inlet is ~19 cm - for scale, note that mesh diameter is 3.5 cm

mhl00228	manual focus		intended distance: ~19 cm										
	3119MH0002280001101998C00	1998	13182	19.2	17.2	-0.9	1.0	74.0	3.4	1608	1198	11.9	8.9

last update: 21_May_2021

Sol 3124 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information*

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

fault recovery diagnostic imaging - no mechanism movement - MAHLI camera head at shoulder-out cover staging pose pointed downward at ~1.25 m above surface of Mars

mhl100808	diagnostic image, not in focus		intended standoff - 1.25 m										
	full frame acquired with no mechanism motion - no part of scene is in focus - reported motor count may not indicate actual focus position												
	3124MH0008080021102003E01	2003	15750	±0	0-0	0-0	0-0	±3-5	0-±	1608	1198	±2	±6

last update: 07_June_2021

Sol 3139 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Beauronne

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3139MH0007060011102005C00	2005	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1
mhli00763	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3139MH0007630011102008C00	2008	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3140MH0001930001102047R00			range map product:			3140MH0001930001102048S00		

target named Cladech

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3139MH0007060011102019C00	2019	13028	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.7
mhli00709	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2	3139MH0007090011102022C00	2022	14196	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	1608	1198	4.3
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3140MH0001930001102045R00			range map product:			3140MH0001930001102046S00		
mhli00709	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 1	3139MH0007090011102033C00	2033	14188	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	1608	1198	4.4
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3140MH0001930001102043R00			range map product:			3140MH0001930001102044S00		

Sol 3142 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Minzac

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3142MH0007060011102050C00	2050	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3142MH0006990011102053C00	2053	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3143MH0001530001102102R00				range map product:							3143MH0001530001102103S00
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3142MH0006990011102064C00	2064	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3143MH0001530001102100R00				range map product:							3143MH0001530001102101S00

target named Terrasson_Lavilledieu

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3142MH0001900011102075C00	2075	13008	27.1	25.2	-1.8	2.1	102.2	6.9	1608	1198	16.4	12.2	
mhli00297	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3142MH0002970011102077C00	2077	14043	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3143MH0001530001102098R00				range map product:							3143MH0001530001102099S00
mhli00297	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3142MH0002970011102087C00	2087	14048	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3143MH0001530001102096R00				range map product:							3143MH0001530001102097S00

last update: 11_June_2021

Sol 3144 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

REMS UV sensor													
mhli00095	standard viewing position		intended standoff: ~15 cm										
	3144MH0000950011102105C00	2105	13257	16.8	14.9	-0.7	0.8	66.0	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9

target named Plaisance - after DRT													
mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3144MH0007060011102107C00	2107	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3144MH0006990011102110C00	2110	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3145MH0002270001102175R00		range map product:		3145MH0002270001102176S00			
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3144MH0006990011102121C00	2121	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3145MH0002270001102173R00		range map product:		3145MH0002270001102174S00			
mhli00824	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm										
	3144MH0008240011102132C00	2132	14690	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3145MH0002270001102171R00		range map product:		3145MH0002270001102172S00			

target named Sarlande													
mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3144MH0007060011102143C00	2143	13023	26.2	24.3	-1.7	1.9	99.0	6.5	1608	1198	15.9	11.9
mhli00708	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3144MH0007080011102146C00	2146	14221	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3145MH0002270001102169R00		range map product:		3145MH0002270001102170S00			
mhli00708	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3144MH0007080011102157C00	2157	14124	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3145MH0002270001102167R00		range map product:		3145MH0002270001102168S00			

Sol 3146 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Monpazier

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3146MH0007060011102178C00	2178	13051	24.6	22.7	-1.5	1.7	93.5	5.7	1608	1198	15.0	11.2	
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3146MH0006990011102181C00	2181	14357	5.0	3.1	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3147MH0001530001102233R00				range map product:							3147MH0001530001102234S00
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3146MH0006990011102192C00	2192	14366	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3147MH0001530001102231R00				range map product:							3147MH0001530001102232S00

target named Nabirat

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3146MH0007060011102203C00	2203	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1	
mhli00740	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3146MH0007400011102206C00	2206	14014	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3147MH0001530001102229R00				range map product:							3147MH0001530001102230S00
mhli00740	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3146MH0007400011102217C00	2217	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3147MH0001530001102227R00				range map product:							3147MH0001530001102228S00

Sol 3160 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Simeyrols

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3160MH0007060011102236C00	2236	12996	27.9	26.0	-1.9	2.2	105.0	7.3	1608	1198	16.9	12.6		
mhli00723	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3160MH0007230011102239C00	2239	13881	7.7	5.8	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	1608	1198	5.5	4.1		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3161MH0001530001102291R00				range map product:					3161MH0001530001102292S00	
mhli00723	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3160MH0007230011102250C00	2250	13882	7.7	5.8	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	1608	1198	5.5	4.1		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3161MH0001530001102289R00				range map product:					3161MH0001530001102290S00	

target named Rouffignac

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3160MH0007060011102261C00	2261	13004	27.3	25.4	-1.9	2.1	103.1	7.1	1608	1198	16.6	12.4		
mhli00709	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3160MH0007090011102264C00	2264	13932	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3161MH0001530001102287R00				range map product:					3161MH0001530001102288S00	
mhli00709	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3160MH0007090011102275C00	2275	13922	7.4	5.5	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3161MH0001530001102285R00				range map product:					3161MH0001530001102286S00	

Sol 3167 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

intended drill target named Pontours - before DRT													
mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3167MH0001900011102294C00	2294	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1
mhli00122	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3167MH0001220011102296C00	2296	13944	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9

intended drill target named Pontours - after DRT														
mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3167MH0007060011102298C00	2298	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1	
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	APXS raster spot 2	3167MH0006990011102301C00	2301	13957	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3167MH0001530001102352R00		range map product:		3167MH0001530001102353S00							
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	APXS raster spot 2	3167MH0006990011102312C00	2312	13967	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3167MH0001530001102350R00		range map product:		3167MH0001530001102351S00							
mhli00785	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm												
	APXS raster spot 2	3167MH0007850011102323C00	2323	14971	3.1	1.2	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.1
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3167MH0001530001102348R00		range map product:		3167MH0001530001102349S00							
mhli00699	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	APXS raster spot 1	3167MH0006990011102334C00	2334	13969	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3167MH0001530001102346R00		range map product:		3167MH0001530001102347S00							

intended drill target named Pontours - after drill bit pre-load test													
mhli00465	context view	intended standoff - 35 cm											
	3167MH0004650011102345C00	2345	12893	36.7	34.8	-3.3	4.0	136.1	12.8	1608	1198	21.9	16.3

last update: 07_July_2021

Sol 3168 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

alternate portion characterization site for planned Pontoursdrill sample

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00197	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3168MH0001970011102355C00	2355	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0

intended portion characterization site for planned Pontoursdrill sample

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00197	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3168MH0001970011102357C00	2357	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1

intended sample discard site for planned Pontoursdrill sample

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3168MH0001900011102359C00	2359	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1

Sol 3178 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
Pontoussample discard pile													
mhl00197	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3178MH0001970011102361C00	2361	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00122	medium-resolution	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 1	3178MH0001220011102363C00	2363	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0
mhl00122	medium-resolution	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2	3178MH0001220011102365C00	2365	14045	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8
SAM sample inlet 2 - cover open - after sample drop-off - inspect surface surrounding inlet perimeter													
mhl00779	full-frame using manual focus	intended standoff - 20 cm											
	3178MH0007790011102366C00	2366	13080	23.1	21.2	-1.4	1.5	88.3	5.0	1608	1198	14.2	10.6
	full-frame based on 128 x 128 autofocus sub-frame (starting pixel 1008, 768)	3178MH0007790031102368C00	2368	13099	22.3	20.4	-1.3	1.4	85.3	4.7	1608	1198	13.7
Pontoussdrill hole													
mhl00197	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3178MH0001970011102370C00	2370	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00774	intermediate-resolution view	intended standoff - 10 cm											
	3178MH0007740011102372C00	2372	13498	11.9	10.0	-0.4	0.4	48.7	1.4	1608	1198	7.8	5.8
target named Chanterac													
mhl00172	context stereo-1	intended standoff - 20 cm											
	3178MH0001720011102374C00	2374	13108	21.9	20.0	-1.2	1.3	83.9	4.5	1608	1198	13.5	10.0
mhl00172	context stereo-2	intended standoff - 20 cm											
	3178MH0001720011102376C00	2376	13107	21.9	20.0	-1.2	1.3	84.0	4.5	1608	1198	13.5	10.1
mhl00122	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3178MH0001220011102378C00	2378	14030	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6

last update: 18_July_2021

Sol 3180 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

Pontoussample discard pile

mhlh00122	medium-resolution	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 1												
	3180MH0001220011102384C00	2380	13940	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9
mhlh00122	medium-resolution	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2												
	3180MH0001220011102382C00	2382	13981	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8

target named Chanterac

mhlh00297	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 5														
	3180MH0002970011102384C00	2384	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3180MH0002270001102441R00				range map product:						3180MH0002270001102442S00	
mhlh00297	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3180MH0002970011102394C00	2394	13979	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3180MH0002270001102439R00				range map product:						3180MH0002270001102440S00	
mhlh00297	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3180MH0002970011102404C00	2404	13955	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.8		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3180MH0002270001102437R00				range map product:						3180MH0002270001102438S00	
mhlh00297	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 3														
	3180MH0002970011102414C00	2414	13968	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3180MH0002270001102435R00				range map product:						3180MH0002270001102436S00	
mhlh00297	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 4														
	3180MH0002970011102424C00	2424	13945	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3180MH0002270001102433R00				range map product:						3180MH0002270001102434S00	

last update: 20_July_2021

Sol 3181 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information*

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

Pontoursdrill hole cuttings

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhl00122	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3181MH0001220011102444C00	2444	14061	6.5	4.6	-0.1	0.1	29.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6

last update: 26_July_2021

Sol 3183 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Montagenet													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3183MH0001900011102446C00	2446	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1
mhli00299	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3183MH0002990011102448C00	2448	13977	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3183MH0001930001102481R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3183MH0001930001102482S00				
mhli00299	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3183MH0002990011102458C00	2458	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3183MH0001930001102479R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3183MH0001930001102480S00				
mhli00649	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm										
	3183MH0006490011102468C00	2468	15086	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3183MH0001930001102477R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3183MH0001930001102478S00				

last update: 23_July_2021

Sol 3185 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Javerlhac													
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3185MH0007060011102484C00	2484	13026	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	1608	1198	15.8	11.8
mhl00803	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3185MH0008030011102487C00	2487	14260	5.4	3.5	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.1
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3185MH0002650001102510R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3185MH0002650001102511S00				
mhl00803	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3185MH0008030011102498C00	2498	14310	5.2	3.3	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	1608	1198	4.0	3.0
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3185MH0002650001102508R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3185MH0002650001102509S00				

Sol 3187 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named *Chauffour* - after DRT

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3187MH0001900011102513C00	2513	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0	
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3187MH0001820011102515C00	2515	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3188MH0001630001102586R00				range map product:					3188MH0001630001102587S00
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3187MH0001820011102525C00	2525	13978	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3188MH0001630001102584R00				range map product:					3188MH0001630001102585S00
mhli00302	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3187MH0003020011102535C00	2535	14622	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3188MH0001630001102582R00				range map product:					3188MH0001630001102583S00

target named *Le_Manet*

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3187MH0001900011102545C00	2545	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhli00224	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3187MH0002240011102547C00	2547	13923	7.4	5.5	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3188MH0001630001102580R00				range map product:					3188MH0001630001102581S00
mhli00224	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3187MH0002240011102557C00	2557	13977	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3188MH0001630001102578R00				range map product:					3188MH0001630001102579S00
mhli00176	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3187MH0001760011102567C00	2567	14642	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3188MH0001630001102576R00				range map product:					3188MH0001630001102577S00

last update: 28_July_2021

Sol 3190 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Fressignas													
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3190MH0007060011102589C00	2589	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00721	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3190MH0007210011102592C00	2592	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3190MH0002650001102615R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3190MH0002650001102616S00							
mhl00721	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3190MH0007210011102603C00	2603	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3190MH0002650001102613R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3190MH0002650001102614S00							

last update: 30_July_2021

Sol 3192 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Champeaux

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3192MH0001900011102618C00	2618	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3192MH0001820011102620C00	2620	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3192MH0001930001102653R00			range map product:			3192MH0001930001102654S00		
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3192MH0001820011102630C00	2630	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3192MH0001930001102651R00			range map product:			3192MH0001930001102652S00		

target named Eyzerc

mhli00359	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3192MH0003590011102640C00	2640	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3192MH0001930001102649R00			range map product:			3192MH0001930001102650S00		

5 Focus merge product information

5.1 Purpose and description

The MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* provide information about the best focus and range map products created by focus merges performed onboard the MAHLI instrument.

The information includes:

1. thumbnail images representing the appearance of each best focus and range map product;
2. a brief title or description of the image target and purpose;
3. the Sol and date (UTC) that the merged parent images were acquired;
4. the Sol on which the focus merge took place,
5. image IDs for the focus merge products and a corresponding full-frame image;
6. the MAHLI command sequence that acquired the parent images and the command sequence that created the focus merge products;
7. the commanded stack depth; that is, the number of parent images acquired in a given focus stack;
8. the type of focus stack (relative or absolute; see definitions in **Section 7**);
9. a list of the thumbnail image IDs for the parent images acquired in the focus stack (because, in some cases, these are the only versions of the focus stack images that are received on Earth);
10. the focus position (stepper motor count) for each parent image in the focus stack;
11. the range and range uncertainty determined from the focus position (motor count) of each parent image; and
12. the grayscale DN value corresponding to each parent image motor count and range in the focus merge range map product.

Further, for each parent image, the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* state whether any of the full-size images (Individual Focus Stack Images) were received on Earth, listing:

13. the image ID of the full-size parent or child image, if received on Earth;
14. the date on which the full-size image was received (applicable only to *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* for the period between Sol 0 and 946 after that, with the exception of Sol 930, this practice was abandoned as unnecessary);
15. the compression quality of the best version of the image, if received on Earth (this practice was later abandoned as unnecessary); and

16. a statement regarding the fate of parent images not received on Earth; that is, the Sol on which the parent was deleted from the data storage inside the instrument’s digital electronics assembly (DEA).

Each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is identified by the Sol on which the parent images were acquired. The onboard merge, in some cases, might have been performed on a later sol.

The parent images identified in rows that are colored orange, if they have a corresponding DN value in a yellow colored column, are those that participated in the creation of the focus merge product. In other words, those that are in white rows (for which there is a corresponding DN in the yellow column) had no in-focus elements and thus were not incorporated into the merged product, even if they had been commanded to be merged. Which images were commanded to be merged can be determined by the yellow-colored column that indicates the corresponding DN values in the range map image product; for cases in which the commanded focus stack depth is > 8 , the corresponding DN values (yellow colored column) will indicate the 8 commanded to be merged (the instrument cannot merge > 8 but it can acquire > 8 images in a focus stack).

In cases in which the focus stack parent images were returned to Earth, the data user has the option to perform a new focus merge using software approaches available on Earth, now or in the future, which might outperform the MAHLI onboard algorithm. The user also has the opportunity, in these cases, to improve each parent image before performing the merge (e.g., remove blemishes, perform flat field correction, etc.).

When a > 8 image focus stack has been acquired, the orange colored rows can *also* indicate recommendations for images that would contain in-focus elements and could be added to a future focus merge product, whether performed onboard MAHLI on Earth after receipt of the full-size images. Those images that are recommended, but were not merged onboard, have no “Corresponding DN in Range Map” in the yellow, rightmost columns of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*.

For the Sol 3069–3192 period, focus stacks that were merged onboard the instrument were acquired on **Sols 3069, 3071, 3074, 3076, 3078, 3081, 3083, 3085, 3088, 3092, 3110, 3112, 3115, 3117, 3119, 3139, 3142, 3144, 3146, 3160, 3167, 3180, 3183, 3185, 3187, 3190, 3192**. Unless otherwise stated, the onboard focus merges performed during this period were all of the “basic” type (see Edgett *et al.* 2012; Edgett *et al.* 2015).

5.2 Formulae

5.2.1 Range

When acquiring a focus stack, the MAHLI camera head is held in a fixed position. This means that the working distance (d_w) — and corresponding standoff distance (d_s) — is constant (see **Section 5.2.5**). However, each image acquired in a focus stack is done so at a different focus position; that is, a different stepper motor count position (m_{open} or m_{closed} ; usually m_{open}). That motor count is related to the range (r_{fm}) between the front lens element of the camera and the in-focus elements of the image by the same empirical formula (**Equation 1**) as applied to determine working distance from motor count. In centimeters,

$$r_{fm} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (12)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For each parent image in a given focus stack, this range is given in the green colored column on the right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

5.2.2 Range uncertainty estimate

The uncertainty ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) in the computed range (r_{fm}) is estimated using depth of field as related to the corresponding range (via motor count; **Equation 12**) for each merged parent image. The range uncertainty estimate is noted in the light green column on the lower right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Estimated Range Uncertainty”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created before Sol 942, our estimate of range uncertainty was based on the older (Edgett *et al.* 2013) depth of field equations described in **Section 4.2.3**, **Equations 4, 5, and 6**, in which we substituted r_{fm} for d_w .

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Depth of Field”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created starting with Sol 942, we used the refined knowledge of MAHLI depth of field, described by Edgett *et al.* (2015) and in **Equation 7** of **Section 4.2.3** to determine d_{far} and d_{near} for each focus stack parent image motor count. The resulting range uncertainty estimate ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) reported in the light green column on the lower right side of the corresponding *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is estimated by the average of the absolute values of d_{far} and d_{near} :

$$\pm r_{uncertainty} = ((-d_{near}) + d_{far})/2. \quad (13)$$

Alternatively, particularly after Sol 1000, the depth of field is reported in the form of both the near and far (d_{far} and d_{near}) depths of field, per **Equation 7**.

5.2.3 Corresponding DN in range map product

Focus merge range map products created onboard MAHLI are returned as grayscale JPEG compressed images. The pixel values (DN) range from 0 to 255. These are assigned by the onboard software on the basis of commanded focus stack depth. The table below, from Edgett *et al.* (2015), shows the relationship between each image commanded to be focus merged and its corresponding grayscale DN value in a MAHLI range map product. In other words, if the instrument is commanded to merge eight images, DN values are assigned according to the second column in the table; if commanded to merge only four images, the corresponding DN values are those in the sixth column. Thus, each DN in a range map product can be related to a motor count position and a corresponding range via linear interpolation between these values.

Relation between commanded image participant in an onboard MAHLI focus merge and range map grayscale data value (DN)							
image commanded to be merged	DN for 8-image merge	DN for 7-image merge	DN for 6-image merge	DN for 5-image merge	DN for 4-image merge	DN for 3-image merge	DN for 2-image merge
1st	255	255	255	255	255	255	255
2nd	223	218	212	204	191	170	127
3rd	191	182	170	153	127	84	—
4th	159	145	127	102	63	—	—
5th	127	109	84	51	—	—	—
6th	95	72	42	—	—	—	—
7th	63	36	—	—	—	—	—
8th	31	—	—	—	—	—	—

5.2.4 Determination of which parent images participated in a given focus merge product (orange rows)

Focus merge parent images in the orange colored rows on each of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* are an indicator of the images that were actually merged. A merge of up to 8 images might be commanded, but perhaps only 3, 4, or 5 of them actually exhibit in-focus elements the get incorporated into the best focus image product.

As discussed by Edgett *et al.* (2015), the parent images that were actually merged, relative to the number commanded to be merged (indicated by the number of yellow-colored rows regarding the corresponding DN in the range map products on the right side of each *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*), are determined by the range of grayscale DN, between 0 and 255, in the focus merge range map product. For example, if the DN range of this product is 91 to 138, then only three of 8 images commanded to be merged participated in that merge, per the DN values corresponding to an 8-image focus merge, per the table above.

5.2.5 Camera working distance and standoff distance

For a given focus stack, the distance between the MAHLI camera head and an imaged target can be determined from a corresponding image acquired via autofocus (assuming the autofocus effort found focus). In other words, while the range between the camera and the in-focus elements of a parent image are captured by the individual parent images in the focus stack (**Section 5.2.1**), the camera acquired the stack from a fixed working distance. On the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the corresponding autofocused image, and its stepper motor count focus position, are stated on the left side of the sheet, beneath the thumbnail images, in rows and columns colored light blue.

For some *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the working distance (d_w) and standoff distance (d_s) are provided in these blue rows and columns. These were computed from the motor count position using the same formulae for d_w and d_s described in **Section 4.2 (Equations 1 and 3, respectively)**. Where these values are not given, the data user can apply **Equations 1 and 3** to the motor count, or use the corresponding full-frame image ID to identify the working distance and standoff distance using the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* for that Sol. We began to regularly provide a result for d_w and d_s starting with Sol 694; before that, the cases in which these values are not given are a reflection of the evolution of the production and content of the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* over time.

updated: 29_March_2021

Sol 3069 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3069MH0007630011101184C00			
best focus image:	3069MH0001530001101236R00		1236	motor count:		13985	range (cm):	6.9	
range map product:	3069MH0001530001101237S00		1237	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	25-Mar-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3069	focus merged on sol:		3069	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3069MH0007630031101186C00	1186	13889	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
3069MH0007630031101187C00	1187	13913	7.45	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	223	2
3069MH0007630031101188C00	1188	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3069MH0007630031101189C00	1189	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3069MH0007630031101190C00	1190	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3069MH0007630031101191C00	1191	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	85	6
3069MH0007630031101192C00	1192	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
3069MH0007630031101193C00	1193	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_March_2021

Sol 3069 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - ~1 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3069MH0007940011101195C00			
best focus image:	3069MH0001530001101234R00		1234	motor count:		15091	range (cm):	2.9	
range map product:	3069MH0001530001101235S00		1235	acquired sequence:		mhli00794	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	25-Mar-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3069	focus merged on sol:		3069	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3069MH0007940031101197C00	1197	14899	3.27	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	255	1
3069MH0007940031101198C00	1198	14947	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	223	2
3069MH0007940031101199C00	1199	14995	3.05	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	191	3
3069MH0007940031101200C00	1200	15043	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	159	4
3069MH0007940031101201C00	1201	15091	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	127	5
3069MH0007940031101202C00	1202	15139	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	85	6
3069MH0007940031101203C00	1203	15187	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	63	7
3069MH0007940031101204C00	1204	15235	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3069 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Chassenon - APXS spot 2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3069MH0007630011101206C00			
best focus image:	3069MH0001530001101232R00		1232	motor count:		13976	range (cm):	7.0	
range map product:	3069MH0001530001101233S00		1233	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	25-Mar-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3069	focus merged on sol:		3069	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3069MH0007630031101208C00	1208	13880	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1
3069MH0007630031101209C00	1209	13904	7.52	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2
3069MH0007630031101210C00	1210	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
3069MH0007630031101211C00	1211	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
3069MH0007630031101212C00	1212	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	127	5
3069MH0007630031101213C00	1213	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	85	6
3069MH0007630031101214C00	1214	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
3069MH0007630031101215C00	1215	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3069 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Chassenon - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3069MH0007210011101220C00			
best focus image:	3069MH0001530001101230R00		1230	motor count:		14009	range (cm):	6.8	
range map product:	3069MH0001530001101231S00		1231	acquired sequence:		mhli00721	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	25-Mar-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3069	focus merged on sol:		3069	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3069MH0007210031101222C00	1222	13841	8.02	-0.2	0.2	35.1	0.7	255	1
3069MH0007210031101223C00	1223	13883	7.68	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
3069MH0007210031101224C00	1224	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	191	3
3069MH0007210031101225C00	1225	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3069MH0007210031101226C00	1226	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3069MH0007210031101227C00	1227	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	85	6
3069MH0007210031101228C00	1228	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
3069MH0007210031101229C00	1229	14135	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3071 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Chassenon - APXS spot 4 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3071MH0007630011101301C00				
best focus image:	3072MH0002580001101319R00	1319	motor count:		13988	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3072MH0002580001101320S00	1320	acquired sequence:		mhli00763		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	27-Mar-21		merge sequence:		mhli00258		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3071		focus merged on sol:		3072
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3071MH0007630031101303C00	1303	13892	7.61	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3071MH0007630031101304C00	1304	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2
3071MH0007630031101305C00	1305	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3071MH0007630031101306C00	1306	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3071MH0007630031101307C00	1307	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3071MH0007630031101308C00	1308	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	85	6
3071MH0007630031101309C00	1309	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
3071MH0007630031101310C00	1310	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 26_April_2021

Sol 3074 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3074MH0001680011101324C00				
best focus image:	3074MH0002650001101345R00	1345	motor count:		14023	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3074MH0002650001101346S00	1346	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	30-Mar-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3074	focus merged on sol:		3074	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3074MH0001680021101325C00	1325	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
3074MH0001680021101326C00	1326	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
3074MH0001680021101327C00	1327	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
3074MH0001680021101328C00	1328	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3074MH0001680021101329C00	1329	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
3074MH0001680021101330C00	1330	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	85	6
3074MH0001680021101331C00	1331	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3074MH0001680021101332C00	1332	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 26_April_2021

Sol 3074 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3074MH0001680011101334C00				
best focus image:	3074MH0002650001101343R00	1343	motor count:		14031	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3074MH0002650001101344S00	1344	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	30-Mar-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3074	focus merged on sol:		3074	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3074MH0001680021101335C00	1335	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	255	1
3074MH0001680021101336C00	1336	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
3074MH0001680021101337C00	1337	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
3074MH0001680021101338C00	1338	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
3074MH0001680021101339C00	1339	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3074MH0001680021101340C00	1340	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	85	6
3074MH0001680021101341C00	1341	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3074MH0001680021101342C00	1342	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3076 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tursac - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff											
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3076MH0003060011101350C00							
best focus image:		3076MH0002650001101371R00		1371		motor count:		13952		range (cm):		7.2	
range map product:		3076MH0002650001101372S00		1372		acquired sequence:		mhli00306		stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:		1-Apr-21				merge sequence:		mhli00265		merge type:		Basic	
motor count interval:		54		acquired on sol:		3076		focus merged on sol:		3076			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8				
				near	far								
3076MH0003060021101351C00	1351	13736	8.97	-0.3	0.2	38.5	0.9	255	1				
3076MH0003060021101352C00	1352	13790	8.46	-0.2	0.2	36.7	0.8	223	2				
3076MH0003060021101353C00	1353	13844	7.99	-0.2	0.2	35.0	0.7	191	3				
3076MH0003060021101354C00	1354	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	159	4				
3076MH0003060021101355C00	1355	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	127	5				
3076MH0003060021101356C00	1356	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	85	6				
3076MH0003060021101357C00	1357	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7				
3076MH0003060021101358C00	1358	14114	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8				

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Sol 3076 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tursac - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff											
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3076MH0003060011101360C00							
best focus image:		3076MH0002650001101369R00		1369		motor count:		13964		range (cm):		7.1	
range map product:		3076MH0002650001101370S00		1370		acquired sequence:		mhli00306		stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:		1-Apr-21				merge sequence:		mhli00265		merge type:		Basic	
motor count interval:		54		acquired on sol:		3076		focus merged on sol:		3076			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8				
				near	far								
3076MH0003060021101361C00	1361	13748	8.85	-0.2	0.2	38.0	0.8	255	1				
3076MH0003060021101362C00	1362	13802	8.35	-0.2	0.2	36.3	0.8	223	2				
3076MH0003060021101363C00	1363	13856	7.89	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	191	3				
3076MH0003060021101364C00	1364	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	159	4				
3076MH0003060021101365C00	1365	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	127	5				
3076MH0003060021101366C00	1366	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	85	6				
3076MH0003060021101367C00	1367	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7				
3076MH0003060021101368C00	1368	14126	6.08	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	31	8				

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Sol 3078 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3078MH0007630011101381C00				
best focus image:	3079MH0007070001101451R00	1451	motor count:		14181	range (cm):		5.8	
range map product:	3079MH0007070001101452S00	1452	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	3-Apr-21	merge sequence:		mhli00707	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3078	focus merged on sol:		3079	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3078MH0007630031101383C00	1383	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	255	1
3078MH0007630031101384C00	1384	14109	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	223	2
3078MH0007630031101385C00	1385	14133	6.05	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	191	3
3078MH0007630031101386C00	1386	14157	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	159	4
3078MH0007630031101387C00	1387	14181	5.79	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	127	5
3078MH0007630031101388C00	1388	14205	5.67	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	85	6
3078MH0007630031101389C00	1389	14229	5.55	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	63	7
3078MH0007630031101390C00	1390	14253	5.43	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3078 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3078MH0007630011101392C00				
best focus image:	3079MH0007070001101449R00	1449	motor count:		14197	range (cm):		5.7	
range map product:	3079MH0007070001101450S00	1450	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	3-Apr-21	merge sequence:		mhli00707	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3078	focus merged on sol:		3079	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3078MH0007630031101394C00	1394	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	255	1
3078MH0007630031101395C00	1395	14125	6.09	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	223	2
3078MH0007630031101396C00	1396	14149	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	191	3
3078MH0007630031101397C00	1397	14173	5.83	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	159	4
3078MH0007630031101398C00	1398	14197	5.71	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	127	5
3078MH0007630031101399C00	1399	14221	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	85	6
3078MH0007630031101400C00	1400	14245	5.47	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	63	7
3078MH0007630031101401C00	1401	14269	5.36	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3078 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff											
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3078MH0007090011101406C00							
best focus image:		3079MH0007070001101447R00		1447		motor count:		14126		range (cm):		6.1	
range map product:		3079MH0007070001101448S00		1448		acquired sequence:		mhli00709		stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:		3-Apr-21				merge sequence:		mhli00707		merge type:		Basic	
motor count interval:		48		acquired on sol:		3078		focus merged on sol:		3079			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8				
				near	far								
3078MH0007090031101408C00	1408	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1				
3078MH0007090031101409C00	1409	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2				
3078MH0007090031101410C00	1410	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	191	3				
3078MH0007090031101411C00	1411	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	159	4				
3078MH0007090031101412C00	1412	14126	6.08	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	127	5				
3078MH0007090031101413C00	1413	14174	5.83	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	85	6				
3078MH0007090031101414C00	1414	14222	5.58	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	63	7				
3078MH0007090031101415C00	1415	14270	5.35	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	31	8				

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Sol 3078 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff											
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3078MH0007090011101417C00							
best focus image:		3079MH0007070001101445R00		1445		motor count:		14160		range (cm):		5.9	
range map product:		3079MH0007070001101446S00		1446		acquired sequence:		mhli00709		stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:		3-Apr-21				merge sequence:		mhli00707		merge type:		Basic	
motor count interval:		48		acquired on sol:		3078		focus merged on sol:		3079			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8				
				near	far								
3078MH0007090031101419C00	1419	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1				
3078MH0007090031101420C00	1420	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	223	2				
3078MH0007090031101421C00	1421	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	191	3				
3078MH0007090031101422C00	1422	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	159	4				
3078MH0007090031101423C00	1423	14160	5.90	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	127	5				
3078MH0007090031101424C00	1424	14208	5.65	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	85	6				
3078MH0007090031101425C00	1425	14256	5.42	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	63	7				
3078MH0007090031101426C00	1426	14304	5.20	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	31	8				

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Sol 3081 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Orliac - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3081MH0002990011101457C00			
best focus image:	3081MH0002650001101478R00		1478	motor count:		14007	range (cm):	6.8	
range map product:	3081MH0002650001101479S00		1479	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Apr-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3081	focus merged on sol:		3081	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3081MH0002990021101458C00	1458	13863	7.84	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	255	1
3081MH0002990021101459C00	1459	13899	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2
3081MH0002990021101460C00	1460	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
3081MH0002990021101461C00	1461	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3081MH0002990021101462C00	1462	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3081MH0002990021101463C00	1463	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	85	6
3081MH0002990021101464C00	1464	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3081MH0002990021101465C00	1465	14115	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3081 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Orliac - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3081MH0002990011101467C00			
best focus image:	3081MH0002650001101476R00		1476	motor count:		14014	range (cm):	6.8	
range map product:	3081MH0002650001101477S00		1477	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Apr-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3081	focus merged on sol:		3081	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3081MH0002990021101468C00	1468	13870	7.78	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	255	1
3081MH0002990021101469C00	1469	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
3081MH0002990021101470C00	1470	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3081MH0002990021101471C00	1471	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3081MH0002990021101472C00	1472	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3081MH0002990021101473C00	1473	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	85	6
3081MH0002990021101474C00	1474	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3081MH0002990021101475C00	1475	14122	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3083 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Puymangou - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3083MH0001520011101484C00			
best focus image:	3083MH0002650001101505R00	1505	motor count:		13957	range (cm):	7.1		
range map product:	3083MH0002650001101506S00	1506	acquired sequence:		mhli00152	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	8-Apr-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3083	focus merged on sol:		3083	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3083MH0001520021101485C00	1485	13765	8.69	-0.2	0.2	37.5	0.8	255	1
3083MH0001520021101486C00	1486	13813	8.25	-0.2	0.2	36.0	0.8	223	2
3083MH0001520021101487C00	1487	13861	7.85	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	191	3
3083MH0001520021101488C00	1488	13909	7.48	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	159	4
3083MH0001520021101489C00	1489	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	127	5
3083MH0001520021101490C00	1490	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	85	6
3083MH0001520021101491C00	1491	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3083MH0001520021101492C00	1492	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

updated: 26_April_2021

Sol 3083 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Puymangou - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3083MH0001520011101494C00			
best focus image:	3083MH0002650001101503R00	1503	motor count:		13944	range (cm):	7.2		
range map product:	3083MH0002650001101504S00	1504	acquired sequence:		mhli00152	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	8-Apr-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3083	focus merged on sol:		3083	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3083MH0001520021101495C00	1495	13752	8.81	-0.2	0.2	37.9	0.8	255	1
3083MH0001520021101496C00	1496	13800	8.37	-0.2	0.2	36.4	0.8	223	2
3083MH0001520021101497C00	1497	13848	7.96	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	191	3
3083MH0001520021101498C00	1498	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	159	4
3083MH0001520021101499C00	1499	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	127	5
3083MH0001520021101500C00	1500	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	85	6
3083MH0001520021101501C00	1501	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3083MH0001520021101502C00	1502	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 26_April_2021

Sol 3085 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Peyrignac - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3085MH0007210011101533C00				
best focus image:	3086MH0001530001101588R00	1588	motor count:		14002	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3086MH0001530001101589S00	1589	acquired sequence:		mhli00721	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	11-Apr-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3085	focus merged on sol:		3086	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3085MH0007210031101535C00	1535	13834	8.08	-0.2	0.2	35.3	0.7	255	1
3085MH0007210031101536C00	1536	13876	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	223	2
3085MH0007210031101537C00	1537	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	191	3
3085MH0007210031101538C00	1538	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3085MH0007210031101539C00	1539	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3085MH0007210031101540C00	1540	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	85	6
3085MH0007210031101541C00	1541	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3085MH0007210031101542C00	1542	14128	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 26_April_2021

Sol 3085 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Peyrignac - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3085MH0007210011101544C00				
best focus image:	3086MH0001530001101586R00	1586	motor count:		14001	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3086MH0001530001101587S00	1587	acquired sequence:		mhli00721	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	11-Apr-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3085	focus merged on sol:		3086	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3085MH0007210031101546C00	1546	13833	8.08	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	255	1
3085MH0007210031101547C00	1547	13875	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	223	2
3085MH0007210031101548C00	1548	13917	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	191	3
3085MH0007210031101549C00	1549	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
3085MH0007210031101550C00	1550	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3085MH0007210031101551C00	1551	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	85	6
3085MH0007210031101552C00	1552	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3085MH0007210031101553C00	1553	14127	6.08	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 26_April_2021

Sol 3085 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Peyrignac - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~2 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3085MH0007950011101561C00			
best focus image:	3086MH0001530001101584R00	1584	motor count:		14692	range (cm):		3.8	
range map product:	3086MH0001530001101585S00	1585	acquired sequence:		mhli00795	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	11-Apr-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		84	acquired on sol:		3085	focus merged on sol:		3086	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3085MH0007950031101563C00	1563	14356	4.98	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	255	1
3085MH0007950031101564C00	1564	14440	4.64	-0.1	0.1	23.2	0.3	223	2
3085MH0007950031101565C00	1565	14524	4.34	-0.1	0.1	22.2	0.3	191	3
3085MH0007950031101566C00	1566	14608	4.06	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	159	4
3085MH0007950031101567C00	1567	14692	3.81	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	127	5
3085MH0007950031101568C00	1568	14776	3.57	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	85	6
3085MH0007950031101569C00	1569	14860	3.36	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	63	7
3085MH0007950031101570C00	1570	14944	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	31	8

updated: 26_April_2021

Sol 3085 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Peyrignac - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3085MH0007210011101572C00			
best focus image:	3086MH0001530001101582R00	1582	motor count:		13994	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3086MH0001530001101583S00	1583	acquired sequence:		mhli00721	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	11-Apr-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3085	focus merged on sol:		3086	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3085MH0007210031101574C00	1574	13826	8.14	-0.2	0.2	35.6	0.7	255	1
3085MH0007210031101575C00	1575	13868	7.80	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	223	2
3085MH0007210031101576C00	1576	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	191	3
3085MH0007210031101577C00	1577	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
3085MH0007210031101578C00	1578	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3085MH0007210031101579C00	1579	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	85	6
3085MH0007210031101580C00	1580	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3085MH0007210031101581C00	1581	14120	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_April_2021

Sol 3088 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Gout_Rossignol - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff - reported motor counts do not indicate actual focus position, image range, or image scale; our best estimates are in red font							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3088MH0001730011101593C00				
best focus image:	3088MH0001930001101626R00	1626	motor count:		14421	range (cm):		~6.8	
range map product:	3088MH0001930001101627S00	1627	acquired sequence:		mhli00173		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	13-Apr-21	merge sequence:			mhli00193		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3088		focus merged on sol:		3088
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3088MH0001730021101594C00	1594	14301	5.21	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	255	1
		est:	~7.70	~-0.2	~0.2	~34.0	~0.7		
3088MH0001730021101595C00	1595	14331	5.08	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	223	2
		est:	~7.47	~-0.2	~0.2	~33.2	~0.7		
3088MH0001730021101596C00	1596	14361	4.96	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	191	3
		est:	~7.25	~-0.2	~0.2	~32.4	~0.6		
3088MH0001730021101597C00	1597	14391	4.83	-0.1	0.1	23.9	0.4	159	4
		est:	~7.04	~-0.2	~0.2	~31.7	~0.6		
3088MH0001730021101598C00	1598	14421	4.72	-0.1	0.1	23.5	0.3	127	5
		est:	~6.84	~-0.2	~0.2	~31.0	~0.6		
3088MH0001730021101599C00	1599	14451	4.60	-0.1	0.1	23.1	0.3	85	6
		est:	~6.64	~-0.2	~0.2	~30.3	~0.6		
3088MH0001730021101600C00	1600	14481	4.49	-0.1	0.1	22.7	0.3	63	7
		est:	~6.46	~-0.2	~0.1	~29.6	~0.5		
3088MH0001730021101601C00	1601	14511	4.38	-0.1	0.1	22.3	0.3	31	8
		est:	~6.28	~-0.1	~0.1	~29.0	~0.5		

Our best estimates are based on subtraction of 420 motor counts from reported values, based on final reported motor count when dust cover was closed and homed.

updated: 29_April_2021

Sol 3088 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		<p>target Gout_Rossignol - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff - reported motor counts do not indicate actual focus position, image range, or image scale; our best estimates are in red font</p>							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3088MH0001730011101603C00				
best focus image:	3088MH0001930001101624R00	1624	motor count:		14418	range (cm):	~6.9		
range map product:	3088MH0001930001101625S00	1625	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	13-Apr-21	merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic				
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3088	focus merged on sol:		3088	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3088MH0001730021101604C00	1604	14298	5.23	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	255	1
		est:	~7.72	~-0.2	~0.2	~34.1	~0.7		
3088MH0001730021101605C00	1605	14328	5.10	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	223	2
		est:	~7.49	~-0.2	~0.2	~33.3	~0.7		
3088MH0001730021101606C00	1606	14358	4.97	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	191	3
		est:	~7.27	~-0.2	~0.2	~32.5	~0.6		
3088MH0001730021101607C00	1607	14388	4.85	-0.1	0.1	24.0	0.4	159	4
		est:	~7.06	~-0.2	~0.2	~31.7	~0.6		
3088MH0001730021101608C00	1608	14418	4.73	-0.1	0.1	23.5	0.3	127	5
		est:	~6.86	~-0.2	~0.2	~31.0	~0.6		
3088MH0001730021101609C00	1609	14448	4.61	-0.1	0.1	23.1	0.3	85	6
		est:	~6.66	~-0.2	~0.2	~30.4	~0.6		
3088MH0001730021101610C00	1610	14478	4.50	-0.1	0.1	22.7	0.3	63	7
		est:	~6.48	~-0.2	~0.1	~29.7	~0.5		
3088MH0001730021101611C00	1611	14508	4.39	-0.1	0.1	22.4	0.3	31	8
		est:	~6.30	~-0.1	~0.1	~29.1	~0.5		

Our best estimates are based on subtraction of 420 motor counts from reported values, based on final reported motor count when dust cover was closed and homed.

updated: 29_April_2021

Sol 3088 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Gout_Rossignol - ~2 cm standoff - reported motor counts do not indicate actual focus position, image range, or image scale; our best estimates are in red font							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3088MH0001760011101613C00				
best focus image:	3088MH0001930001101622R00	1622	motor count:		15115	range (cm):	~3.8		
range map product:	3088MH0001930001101623S00	1623	acquired sequence:		mhli00176	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	13-Apr-21	merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic				
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3088	focus merged on sol:		3088	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3088MH0001760021101614C00	1614	14923	3.21	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	255	1
		est:	~4.41	~-0.1	~0.1	~22.4	~0.3		
3088MH0001760021101615C00	1615	14971	3.10	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	223	2
		est:	~4.25	~-0.1	~0.1	~21.8	~0.3		
3088MH0001760021101616C00	1616	15019	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	191	3
		est:	~4.09	~-0.1	~0.1	~21.3	~0.3		
3088MH0001760021101617C00	1617	15067	2.90	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	159	4
		est:	~3.94	~-0.1	~0.1	~20.8	~0.3		
3088MH0001760021101618C00	1618	15115	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
		est:	~3.80	~-0.1	~0.1	~20.3	~0.3		
3088MH0001760021101619C00	1619	15163	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	85	6
		est:	~3.66	~-0.1	~0.1	~19.8	~0.3		
3088MH0001760021101620C00	1620	15211	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	63	7
		est:	~3.53	~-0.1	~0.1	~19.3	~0.3		
3088MH0001760021101621C00	1621	15259	2.54	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	31	8
		est:	~3.41	~-0.1	~0.1	~18.9	~0.2		

Our best estimates are based on subtraction of 420 motor counts from reported values, based on final reported motor count when dust cover was closed and homed.

updated: 29_April_2021

Sol 3092 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Cussac - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3092MH0001680011101631C00			
best focus image:	3092MH0001530001101684R00	1684	motor count:		14003	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3092MH0001530001101685S00	1685	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	18-Apr-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3092	focus merged on sol:		3092	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3092MH0001680021101632C00	1632	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
3092MH0001680021101633C00	1633	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3092MH0001680021101634C00	1634	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3092MH0001680021101635C00	1635	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3092MH0001680021101636C00	1636	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3092MH0001680021101637C00	1637	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	85	6
3092MH0001680021101638C00	1638	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3092MH0001680021101639C00	1639	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_April_2021

Sol 3092 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Bardou - after sol 3090 DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3092MH0007630011101644C00			
best focus image:	3092MH0001530001101682R00	1682	motor count:		13993	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3092MH0001530001101683S00	1683	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	18-Apr-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3092	focus merged on sol:		3092	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3092MH0007630031101646C00	1646	13897	7.57	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3092MH0007630031101647C00	1647	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3092MH0007630031101648C00	1648	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3092MH0007630031101649C00	1649	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3092MH0007630031101650C00	1650	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3092MH0007630031101651C00	1651	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	85	6
3092MH0007630031101652C00	1652	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3092MH0007630031101653C00	1653	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_April_2021

Sol 3092 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Bardou - after sol 3090 DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff											
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3092MH0007630011101655C00							
best focus image:		3092MH0001530001101680R00		1680		motor count:		13995		range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:		3092MH0001530001101681S00		1681		acquired sequence:		mhli00763		stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:		18-Apr-21				merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type:		Basic	
motor count interval:		24		acquired on sol:		3092		focus merged on sol:		3092			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8				
				near	far								
3092MH0007630031101657C00	1657	13899	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	255	1				
3092MH0007630031101658C00	1658	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2				
3092MH0007630031101659C00	1659	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3				
3092MH0007630031101660C00	1660	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4				
3092MH0007630031101661C00	1661	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5				
3092MH0007630031101662C00	1662	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	85	6				
3092MH0007630031101663C00	1663	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7				
3092MH0007630031101664C00	1664	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8				

updated: 29_April_2021

Sol 3092 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Bardou - after sol 3090 DRT - ~2 cm standoff											
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3092MH0008130011101666C00							
best focus image:		3092MH0001530001101678R00		1678		motor count:		14671		range (cm):		3.9	
range map product:		3092MH0001530001101679S00		1679		acquired sequence:		mhli00813		stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:		18-Apr-21				merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type:		Basic	
motor count interval:		30		acquired on sol:		3092		focus merged on sol:		3092			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8				
				near	far								
3092MH0008130031101668C00	1668	14551	4.25	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	255	1				
3092MH0008130031101669C00	1669	14581	4.15	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	223	2				
3092MH0008130031101670C00	1670	14611	4.05	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	191	3				
3092MH0008130031101671C00	1671	14641	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	159	4				
3092MH0008130031101672C00	1672	14671	3.87	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	127	5				
3092MH0008130031101673C00	1673	14701	3.78	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	85	6				
3092MH0008130031101674C00	1674	14731	3.70	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	63	7				
3092MH0008130031101675C00	1675	14761	3.61	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	31	8				

updated: 10_May_2021

Sol 3110 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Gourdon - stereo-1 - ~55 mm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3110MH0007230011101709C00		
best focus image:	3110MH0001930001101745R00	1745		motor count:		13905	range (cm):	7.5	
range map product:	3110MH0001930001101746S00	1746		acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	6-May-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3110	focus merged on sol:		3110	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3110MH0007230031101711C00	1711	13761	8.72	-0.2	0.2	37.6	0.8	255	1
3110MH0007230031101712C00	1712	13797	8.40	-0.2	0.2	36.5	0.8	223	2
3110MH0007230031101713C00	1713	13833	8.08	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	191	3
3110MH0007230031101714C00	1714	13869	7.79	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	159	4
3110MH0007230031101715C00	1715	13905	7.51	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	127	5
3110MH0007230031101716C00	1716	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	85	6
3110MH0007230031101717C00	1717	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	63	7
3110MH0007230031101718C00	1718	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	31	8

updated: 10_May_2021

Sol 3110 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Gourdon - stereo-2 - ~55 mm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3110MH0007230011101720C00		
best focus image:	3110MH0001930001101743R00	1743		motor count:		13909	range (cm):	7.5	
range map product:	3110MH0001930001101744S00	1744		acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	6-May-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3110	focus merged on sol:		3110	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3110MH0007230031101722C00	1722	13765	8.69	-0.2	0.2	37.5	0.8	255	1
3110MH0007230031101723C00	1723	13801	8.36	-0.2	0.2	36.3	0.8	223	2
3110MH0007230031101724C00	1724	13837	8.05	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	191	3
3110MH0007230031101725C00	1725	13873	7.76	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	159	4
3110MH0007230031101726C00	1726	13909	7.48	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	127	5
3110MH0007230031101727C00	1727	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	85	6
3110MH0007230031101728C00	1728	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	63	7
3110MH0007230031101729C00	1729	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	31	8

updated: 10_May_2021

Sol 3110 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Gourdon - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3110MH0007970011101731C00				
best focus image:	3110MH0001930001101741R00	1741	motor count:		14251	range (cm):		5.4	
range map product:	3110MH0001930001101742S00	1742	acquired sequence:		mhli00797	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-May-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3110	focus merged on sol:		3110	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3110MH0007970031101733C00	1733	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	255	1
3110MH0007970031101734C00	1734	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	223	2
3110MH0007970031101735C00	1735	14131	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	191	3
3110MH0007970031101736C00	1736	14191	5.74	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	159	4
3110MH0007970031101737C00	1737	14251	5.44	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	127	5
3110MH0007970031101738C00	1738	14311	5.17	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	85	6
3110MH0007970031101739C00	1739	14371	4.91	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	63	7
3110MH0007970031101740C00	1740	14431	4.68	-0.1	0.1	23.4	0.3	31	8

updated: 10_May_2021

Sol 3112 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pezuls - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3112MH0007400011101751C00				
best focus image:	3112MH0002270001101816R00	1816	motor count:		13953	range (cm):		7.2	
range map product:	3112MH0002270001101817S00	1817	acquired sequence:		mhli00740	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	8-May-21	merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3112	focus merged on sol:		3112	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3112MH0007400031101753C00	1753	13737	8.96	-0.3	0.2	38.4	0.9	255	1
3112MH0007400031101754C00	1754	13791	8.45	-0.2	0.2	36.6	0.8	223	2
3112MH0007400031101755C00	1755	13845	7.98	-0.2	0.2	35.0	0.7	191	3
3112MH0007400031101756C00	1756	13899	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	159	4
3112MH0007400031101757C00	1757	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	127	5
3112MH0007400031101758C00	1758	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	85	6
3112MH0007400031101759C00	1759	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3112MH0007400031101760C00	1760	14115	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	31	8

updated: 10_May_2021

Sol 3112 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pezuls - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3112MH0007400011101762C00				
best focus image:	3112MH0002270001101814R00	1814	motor count:		13958	range (cm):		7.1	
range map product:	3112MH0002270001101815S00	1815	acquired sequence:		mhli00740	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	8-May-21	merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3112	focus merged on sol:		3112	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3112MH0007400031101764C00	1764	13742	8.91	-0.3	0.2	38.3	0.8	255	1
3112MH0007400031101765C00	1765	13796	8.40	-0.2	0.2	36.5	0.8	223	2
3112MH0007400031101766C00	1766	13850	7.94	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	191	3
3112MH0007400031101767C00	1767	13904	7.52	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	159	4
3112MH0007400031101768C00	1768	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	127	5
3112MH0007400031101769C00	1769	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	85	6
3112MH0007400031101770C00	1770	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3112MH0007400031101771C00	1771	14120	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

updated: 10_May_2021

Sol 3112 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pezuls - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3112MH0008000011101773C00				
best focus image:	3112MH0002270001101812R00	1812	motor count:		14618	range (cm):		4.0	
range map product:	3112MH0002270001101813S00	1813	acquired sequence:		mhli00800	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	8-May-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3112	focus merged on sol:		3112	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3112MH0008000031101775C00	1775	14402	4.79	-0.1	0.1	23.8	0.4	255	1
3112MH0008000031101776C00	1776	14456	4.58	-0.1	0.1	23.0	0.3	223	2
3112MH0008000031101777C00	1777	14510	4.39	-0.1	0.1	22.3	0.3	191	3
3112MH0008000031101778C00	1778	14564	4.20	-0.1	0.1	21.7	0.3	159	4
3112MH0008000031101779C00	1779	14618	4.03	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	127	5
3112MH0008000031101780C00	1780	14672	3.87	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	85	6
3112MH0008000031101781C00	1781	14726	3.71	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	63	7
3112MH0008000031101782C00	1782	14780	3.56	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	31	8

updated: 10_May_2021

Sol 3112 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Le_Bugue - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3112MH0007400011101787C00				
best focus image:	3112MH0002270001101810R00	1810	motor count:		14118	range (cm):		6.1	
range map product:	3112MH0002270001101811S00	1811	acquired sequence:		mhli00740	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	8-May-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3112	focus merged on sol:		3112	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3112MH0007400031101789C00	1789	13902	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3112MH0007400031101790C00	1790	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
3112MH0007400031101791C00	1791	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
3112MH0007400031101792C00	1792	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	159	4
3112MH0007400031101793C00	1793	14118	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	127	5
3112MH0007400031101794C00	1794	14172	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	85	6
3112MH0007400031101795C00	1795	14226	5.56	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	63	7
3112MH0007400031101796C00	1796	14280	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	31	8

updated: 10_May_2021

Sol 3112 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Le_Bugue - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3112MH0007400011101798C00				
best focus image:	3112MH0002270001101808R00	1808	motor count:		14118	range (cm):		6.1	
range map product:	3112MH0002270001101809S00	1809	acquired sequence:		mhli00740	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	8-May-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3112	focus merged on sol:		3112	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3112MH0007400031101800C00	1800	13902	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3112MH0007400031101801C00	1801	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
3112MH0007400031101802C00	1802	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
3112MH0007400031101803C00	1803	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	159	4
3112MH0007400031101804C00	1804	14118	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	127	5
3112MH0007400031101805C00	1805	14172	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	85	6
3112MH0007400031101806C00	1806	14226	5.56	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	63	7
3112MH0007400031101807C00	1807	14280	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	31	8

updated: 12_May_2021

Sol 3115 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Biras - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3115MH0007210011101822C00				
best focus image:	3115MH0001530001101875R00	1875	motor count:		13978	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3115MH0001530001101876S00	1876	acquired sequence:		mhli00721	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	11-May-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3115	focus merged on sol:		3115	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3115MH0007210031101824C00	1824	13810	8.28	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	255	1
3115MH0007210031101825C00	1825	13852	7.93	-0.2	0.2	34.8	0.7	223	2
3115MH0007210031101826C00	1826	13894	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	191	3
3115MH0007210031101827C00	1827	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4
3115MH0007210031101828C00	1828	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
3115MH0007210031101829C00	1829	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	85	6
3115MH0007210031101830C00	1830	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3115MH0007210031101831C00	1831	14104	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

updated: 12_May_2021

Sol 3115 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Biras - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3115MH0007210011101833C00				
best focus image:	3115MH0001530001101873R00	1873	motor count:		13982	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3115MH0001530001101874S00	1874	acquired sequence:		mhli00721	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	11-May-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3115	focus merged on sol:		3115	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3115MH0007210031101835C00	1835	13814	8.25	-0.2	0.2	35.9	0.8	255	1
3115MH0007210031101836C00	1836	13856	7.89	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	223	2
3115MH0007210031101837C00	1837	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	191	3
3115MH0007210031101838C00	1838	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	159	4
3115MH0007210031101839C00	1839	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5
3115MH0007210031101840C00	1840	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3115MH0007210031101841C00	1841	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3115MH0007210031101842C00	1842	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 12_May_2021

Sol 3115 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Quinsac - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3115MH0007080011101847C00				
best focus image:	3115MH0001530001101871R00	1871	motor count:		13987	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3115MH0001530001101872S00	1872	acquired sequence:		mhli00708	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	11-May-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3115	focus merged on sol:		3115	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3115MH0007080031101849C00	1849	13747	8.86	-0.2	0.2	38.1	0.8	255	1
3115MH0007080031101850C00	1850	13807	8.31	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	223	2
3115MH0007080031101851C00	1851	13867	7.81	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	191	3
3115MH0007080031101852C00	1852	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	159	4
3115MH0007080031101853C00	1853	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3115MH0007080031101854C00	1854	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	85	6
3115MH0007080031101855C00	1855	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
3115MH0007080031101856C00	1856	14167	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	31	8

updated: 12_May_2021

Sol 3115 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Quinsac - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3115MH0007080011101858C00				
best focus image:	3115MH0001530001101869R00	1869	motor count:		13988	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3115MH0001530001101870S00	1870	acquired sequence:		mhli00708	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	11-May-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3115	focus merged on sol:		3115	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3115MH0007080031101860C00	1860	13748	8.85	-0.2	0.2	38.0	0.8	255	1
3115MH0007080031101861C00	1861	13808	8.30	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	223	2
3115MH0007080031101862C00	1862	13868	7.80	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	191	3
3115MH0007080031101863C00	1863	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	159	4
3115MH0007080031101864C00	1864	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3115MH0007080031101865C00	1865	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	85	6
3115MH0007080031101866C00	1866	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
3115MH0007080031101867C00	1867	14168	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	31	8

updated: 17_May_2021

Sol 3117 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Busserolles - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3117MH0007230011101881C00				
best focus image:	3117MH0001930001101917R00	1917	motor count:		14030	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3117MH0001930001101918S00	1918	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	13-May-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3117	focus merged on sol:		3117	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3117MH0007230031101883C00	1883	13886	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1
3117MH0007230031101884C00	1884	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3117MH0007230031101885C00	1885	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3117MH0007230031101886C00	1886	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3117MH0007230031101887C00	1887	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3117MH0007230031101888C00	1888	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	85	6
3117MH0007230031101889C00	1889	14102	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	63	7
3117MH0007230031101890C00	1890	14138	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 17_May_2021

Sol 3117 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Busserolles - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3117MH0007230011101892C00				
best focus image:	3117MH0001930001101915R00	1915	motor count:		14034	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3117MH0001930001101916S00	1916	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	13-May-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3117	focus merged on sol:		3117	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3117MH0007230031101894C00	1894	13890	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3117MH0007230031101895C00	1895	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3117MH0007230031101896C00	1896	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
3117MH0007230031101897C00	1897	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3117MH0007230031101898C00	1898	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
3117MH0007230031101899C00	1899	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	85	6
3117MH0007230031101900C00	1900	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
3117MH0007230031101901C00	1901	14142	6.00	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	31	8

updated: 17_May_2021

Sol 3117 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Busserolles - ~1 cm standoff												
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3117MH0007850011101903C00								
best focus image:		3117MH0001930001101913R00		1913		motor count:		15183		range (cm):		2.7		
range map product:		3117MH0001930001101914S00		1914		acquired sequence:		mhli00785		stack type:		Relative		
acquired on date:		13-May-21				merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:			42		acquired on sol:		3117		focus merged on sol:		3117			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8					
				near	far									
3117MH0007850031101905C00	1905	15015	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	255	1					
3117MH0007850031101906C00	1906	15057	2.92	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	223	2					
3117MH0007850031101907C00	1907	15099	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	191	3					
3117MH0007850031101908C00	1908	15141	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	159	4					
3117MH0007850031101909C00	1909	15183	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	127	5					
3117MH0007850031101910C00	1910	15225	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	85	6					
3117MH0007850031101911C00	1911	15267	2.53	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	63	7					
3117MH0007850031101912C00	1912	15309	2.46	0.0	0.1	15.6	0.2	31	8					

updated: 21_May_2021

Sol 3119 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Monsec - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3119MH0007230011101927C00				
best focus image:	3119MH0002270001101992R00	1992	motor count:		13980	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3119MH0002270001101993S00	1993	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	16-May-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3119	focus merged on sol:		3119	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3119MH0007230031101929C00	1929	13836	8.06	-0.2	0.2	35.3	0.7	255	1
3119MH0007230031101930C00	1930	13872	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	223	2
3119MH0007230031101931C00	1931	13908	7.49	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	191	3
3119MH0007230031101932C00	1932	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	159	4
3119MH0007230031101933C00	1933	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
3119MH0007230031101934C00	1934	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	85	6
3119MH0007230031101935C00	1935	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3119MH0007230031101936C00	1936	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 21_May_2021

Sol 3119 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Monsec - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3119MH0007230011101938C00				
best focus image:	3119MH0002270001101990R00	1990	motor count:		13984	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3119MH0002270001101991S00	1991	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	16-May-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3119	focus merged on sol:		3119	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3119MH0007230031101940C00	1940	13840	8.03	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	255	1
3119MH0007230031101941C00	1941	13876	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	223	2
3119MH0007230031101942C00	1942	13912	7.46	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	191	3
3119MH0007230031101943C00	1943	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	159	4
3119MH0007230031101944C00	1944	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5
3119MH0007230031101945C00	1945	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	85	6
3119MH0007230031101946C00	1946	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3119MH0007230031101947C00	1947	14092	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

updated: 21_May_2021

Sol 3119 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Monsec - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3119MH0008020011101949C00			
best focus image:	3119MH0002270001101988R00	1988	motor count:		14635	range (cm):		4.0	
range map product:	3119MH0002270001101989S00	1989	acquired sequence:		mhli00802	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	16-May-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3119	focus merged on sol:		3119	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3119MH0008020031101951C00	1951	14371	4.91	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	255	1
3119MH0008020031101952C00	1952	14437	4.65	-0.1	0.1	23.3	0.3	223	2
3119MH0008020031101953C00	1953	14503	4.41	-0.1	0.1	22.4	0.3	191	3
3119MH0008020031101954C00	1954	14569	4.19	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	159	4
3119MH0008020031101955C00	1955	14635	3.98	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	127	5
3119MH0008020031101956C00	1956	14701	3.78	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	85	6
3119MH0008020031101957C00	1957	14767	3.60	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	63	7
3119MH0008020031101958C00	1958	14833	3.43	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	31	8

updated: 21_May_2021

Sol 3119 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	first merge of: target Salagnac - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3119MH0007230011101963C00			
best focus image:	3119MH0002270001101986R00	1986	motor count:		14143	range (cm):		6.0	
range map product:	3119MH0002270001101987S00	1987	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	16-May-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3119	focus merged on sol:		3119	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3119MH0007230031101965C00	1965	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	255	1
3119MH0007230031101966C00	1966	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	223	2
3119MH0007230031101967C00	1967	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	191	3
3119MH0007230031101968C00	1968	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	159	4
3119MH0007230031101969C00	1969	14143	5.99	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	127	5
3119MH0007230031101970C00	1970	14179	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	85	6
3119MH0007230031101971C00	1971	14215	5.62	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	63	7
3119MH0007230031101972C00	1972	14251	5.44	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	31	8

updated: 21_May_2021

Sol 3119 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	second merge of: target Salagnac - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff - merge occurred following Sol 3122 MAHLI mechanism fault which prevented new focus stack acquisition on Sol 3122								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3119MH0007230011101963C00				
best focus image:	3122MH0002650001102001R00	2001	motor count:		14143	range (cm):		6.0	
range map product:	3122MH0002650001102002S00	2002	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	16-May-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3119	focus merged on sol:		3122	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3119MH0007230031101965C00	1965	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	255	1
3119MH0007230031101966C00	1966	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	223	2
3119MH0007230031101967C00	1967	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	191	3
3119MH0007230031101968C00	1968	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	159	4
3119MH0007230031101969C00	1969	14143	5.99	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	127	5
3119MH0007230031101970C00	1970	14179	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	85	6
3119MH0007230031101971C00	1971	14215	5.62	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	63	7
3119MH0007230031101972C00	1972	14251	5.44	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	31	8

updated: 21_May_2021

Sol 3119 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	first merge of: target Salagnac - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3119MH0007230011101974C00				
best focus image:	3119MH0002270001101984R00	1984	motor count:		14148	range (cm):		6.0	
range map product:	3119MH0002270001101985S00	1985	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	16-May-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3119	focus merged on sol:		3119	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3119MH0007230031101976C00	1976	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	255	1
3119MH0007230031101977C00	1977	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	223	2
3119MH0007230031101978C00	1978	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	191	3
3119MH0007230031101979C00	1979	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	159	4
3119MH0007230031101980C00	1980	14148	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	127	5
3119MH0007230031101981C00	1981	14184	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	85	6
3119MH0007230031101982C00	1982	14220	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	63	7
3119MH0007230031101983C00	1983	14256	5.42	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	31	8

updated: 21_May_2021

Sol 3119 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		second merge of: target Salagnac - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff - merge occurred following Sol 3122 MAHLI mechanism fault which prevented new focus stack acquisition on Sol 3122							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3119MH0007230011101974C00				
best focus image:	3122MH0002650001101999R00	1999	motor count:		14148	range (cm):		6.0	
range map product:	3122MH0002650001102000S00	2000	acquired sequence:		mhli00723		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	16-May-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3119	focus merged on sol:		3122	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3119MH0007230031101976C00	1976	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	255	1
3119MH0007230031101977C00	1977	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	223	2
3119MH0007230031101978C00	1978	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	191	3
3119MH0007230031101979C00	1979	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	159	4
3119MH0007230031101980C00	1980	14148	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	127	5
3119MH0007230031101981C00	1981	14184	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	85	6
3119MH0007230031101982C00	1982	14220	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	63	7
3119MH0007230031101983C00	1983	14256	5.42	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	31	8

updated: 08_June_2021

Sol 3139 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Beauronne - ~5 cm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3139MH0007630011102008C00		
best focus image:	3140MH0001930001102047R00	2047		motor count:		13987	range (cm):	6.9	
range map product:	3140MH0001930001102048S00	2048		acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	5-Jun-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3139	focus merged on sol:		3140	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3139MH0007630031102010C00	2010	13891	7.62	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3139MH0007630031102011C00	2011	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2
3139MH0007630031102012C00	2012	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3139MH0007630031102013C00	2013	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3139MH0007630031102014C00	2014	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3139MH0007630031102015C00	2015	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	85	6
3139MH0007630031102016C00	2016	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
3139MH0007630031102017C00	2017	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 08_June_2021

Sol 3139 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Cladech - APXS Spot 2 - ~4 cm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3139MH0007090011102022C00		
best focus image:	3140MH0001930001102045R00	2045		motor count:		14196	range (cm):	5.7	
range map product:	3140MH0001930001102046S00	2046		acquired sequence:		mhli00709	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	5-Jun-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3139	focus merged on sol:		3140	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3139MH0007090031102024C00	2024	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	255	1
3139MH0007090031102025C00	2025	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	223	2
3139MH0007090031102026C00	2026	14100	6.23	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	191	3
3139MH0007090031102027C00	2027	14148	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	159	4
3139MH0007090031102028C00	2028	14196	5.71	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	127	5
3139MH0007090031102029C00	2029	14244	5.48	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	85	6
3139MH0007090031102030C00	2030	14292	5.25	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	63	7
3139MH0007090031102031C00	2031	14340	5.04	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	31	8

updated: 08_June_2021

Sol 3139 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Cladech - APXS Spot 1 - ~4 cm standoff											
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3139MH0007090011102033C00							
best focus image:		3140MH0001930001102043R00		2043		motor count:		14188		range (cm):		5.8	
range map product:		3140MH0001930001102044S00		2044		acquired sequence:		mhli00709		stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:		5-Jun-21				merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type:		Basic	
motor count interval:		48		acquired on sol:		3139		focus merged on sol:		3140			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8				
				near	far								
3139MH0007090031102035C00	2035	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	255	1				
3139MH0007090031102036C00	2036	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	223	2				
3139MH0007090031102037C00	2037	14092	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	191	3				
3139MH0007090031102038C00	2038	14140	6.01	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	159	4				
3139MH0007090031102039C00	2039	14188	5.75	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	127	5				
3139MH0007090031102040C00	2040	14236	5.52	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	85	6				
3139MH0007090031102041C00	2041	14284	5.29	-0.1	0.1	25.5	0.4	63	7				
3139MH0007090031102042C00	2042	14332	5.08	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	31	8				

updated: 17_June_2021

Sol 3142 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Minzac - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3142MH0006990011102053C00			
best focus image:	3143MH0001530001102102R00		2102	motor count:		13989	range (cm):	6.9	
range map product:	3143MH0001530001102103S00		2103	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	8-Jun-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3142	focus merged on sol:		3143	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3142MH0006990031102055C00	2055	13869	7.79	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	255	1
3142MH0006990031102056C00	2056	13899	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2
3142MH0006990031102057C00	2057	13929	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
3142MH0006990031102058C00	2058	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
3142MH0006990031102059C00	2059	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3142MH0006990031102060C00	2060	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	85	6
3142MH0006990031102061C00	2061	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3142MH0006990031102062C00	2062	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 17_June_2021

Sol 3142 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Minzac - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3142MH0006990011102064C00			
best focus image:	3143MH0001530001102100R00		2100	motor count:		13992	range (cm):	6.9	
range map product:	3143MH0001530001102101S00		2101	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	8-Jun-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3142	focus merged on sol:		3143	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3142MH0006990031102066C00	2066	13872	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
3142MH0006990031102067C00	2067	13902	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2
3142MH0006990031102068C00	2068	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
3142MH0006990031102069C00	2069	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3142MH0006990031102070C00	2070	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3142MH0006990031102071C00	2071	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	85	6
3142MH0006990031102072C00	2072	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3142MH0006990031102073C00	2073	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

updated: 17_June_2021

Sol 3142 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3142MH0002970011102077C00				
best focus image:	3143MH0001530001102098R00	2098	motor count:		14043	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3143MH0001530001102099S00	2099	acquired sequence:		mhli00297	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	8-Jun-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3142	focus merged on sol:		3143	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3142MH0002970021102078C00	2078	13803	8.34	-0.2	0.2	36.3	0.8	255	1
3142MH0002970021102079C00	2079	13863	7.84	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	223	2
3142MH0002970021102080C00	2080	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	191	3
3142MH0002970021102081C00	2081	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3142MH0002970021102082C00	2082	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
3142MH0002970021102083C00	2083	14103	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	85	6
3142MH0002970021102084C00	2084	14163	5.88	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	63	7
3142MH0002970021102085C00	2085	14223	5.58	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	31	8

updated: 17_June_2021

Sol 3142 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3142MH0002970011102087C00				
best focus image:	3143MH0001530001102096R00	2096	motor count:		14048	range (cm):		6.5	
range map product:	3143MH0001530001102097S00	2097	acquired sequence:		mhli00297	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	8-Jun-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3142	focus merged on sol:		3143	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3142MH0002970021102088C00	2088	13808	8.30	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	255	1
3142MH0002970021102089C00	2089	13868	7.80	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	223	2
3142MH0002970021102090C00	2090	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
3142MH0002970021102091C00	2091	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3142MH0002970021102092C00	2092	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	127	5
3142MH0002970021102093C00	2093	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	85	6
3142MH0002970021102094C00	2094	14168	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	63	7
3142MH0002970021102095C00	2095	14228	5.55	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	31	8

updated: 22_June_2021

Sol 3144 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Plaisance - After DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff											
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3144MH0006990011102110C00							
best focus image:		3145MH0002270001102175R00		2175		motor count:		13999		range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:		3145MH0002270001102176S00		2176		acquired sequence:		mhli00699		stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:		10-Jun-21				merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type:		Basic	
motor count interval:		30		acquired on sol:		3144		focus merged on sol:		3145			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8				
				near	far								
3144MH0006990031102112C00	2112	13879	7.71	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1				
3144MH0006990031102113C00	2113	13909	7.48	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	223	2				
3144MH0006990031102114C00	2114	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3				
3144MH0006990031102115C00	2115	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4				
3144MH0006990031102116C00	2116	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5				
3144MH0006990031102117C00	2117	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	85	6				
3144MH0006990031102118C00	2118	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7				
3144MH0006990031102119C00	2119	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8				

updated: 22_June_2021

Sol 3144 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Plaisance - After DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff											
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3144MH0006990011102121C00							
best focus image:		3145MH0002270001102173R00		2173		motor count:		14000		range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:		3145MH0002270001102174S00		2174		acquired sequence:		mhli00699		stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:		10-Jun-21				merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type:		Basic	
motor count interval:		30		acquired on sol:		3144		focus merged on sol:		3145			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8				
				near	far								
3144MH0006990031102123C00	2123	13880	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1				
3144MH0006990031102124C00	2124	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	223	2				
3144MH0006990031102125C00	2125	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3				
3144MH0006990031102126C00	2126	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4				
3144MH0006990031102127C00	2127	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5				
3144MH0006990031102128C00	2128	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	85	6				
3144MH0006990031102129C00	2129	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7				
3144MH0006990031102130C00	2130	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8				

updated: 22_June_2021

Sol 3144 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Plaisance - After DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3144MH0008240011102132C00			
best focus image:	3145MH0002270001102171R00	2171	motor count:		14690	range (cm):		3.8	
range map product:	3145MH0002270001102172S00	2172	acquired sequence:		mhli00824	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	10-Jun-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3144	focus merged on sol:		3145	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3144MH0008240031102134C00	2134	14522	4.35	-0.1	0.1	22.2	0.3	255	1
3144MH0008240031102135C00	2135	14564	4.20	-0.1	0.1	21.7	0.3	223	2
3144MH0008240031102136C00	2136	14606	4.07	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	191	3
3144MH0008240031102137C00	2137	14648	3.94	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	159	4
3144MH0008240031102138C00	2138	14690	3.81	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	127	5
3144MH0008240031102139C00	2139	14732	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	85	6
3144MH0008240031102140C00	2140	14774	3.58	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	63	7
3144MH0008240031102141C00	2141	14816	3.47	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	31	8

updated: 22_June_2021

Sol 3144 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Sarlande - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3144MH0007080011102146C00			
best focus image:	3145MH0002270001102169R00	2169	motor count:		14221	range (cm):		5.6	
range map product:	3145MH0002270001102170S00	2170	acquired sequence:		mhli00708	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	10-Jun-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3144	focus merged on sol:		3145	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3144MH0007080031102148C00	2148	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
3144MH0007080031102149C00	2149	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	223	2
3144MH0007080031102150C00	2150	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	191	3
3144MH0007080031102151C00	2151	14161	5.89	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	159	4
3144MH0007080031102152C00	2152	14221	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	127	5
3144MH0007080031102153C00	2153	14281	5.30	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	85	6
3144MH0007080031102154C00	2154	14341	5.04	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	63	7
3144MH0007080031102155C00	2155	14401	4.79	-0.1	0.1	23.8	0.4	31	8

updated: 22_June_2021

Sol 3144 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Sarlande - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff										
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3144MH0007080011102157C00						
best focus image:		3145MH0002270001102167R00		2167		motor count:		14124		range (cm): 6.1		
range map product:		3145MH0002270001102168S00		2168		acquired sequence:		mhli00708		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:		10-Jun-21				merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:			60		acquired on sol:		3144		focus merged on sol:		3145	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8			
				near	far							
3144MH0007080031102159C00	2159	13884	7.67	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1			
3144MH0007080031102160C00	2160	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2			
3144MH0007080031102161C00	2161	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3			
3144MH0007080031102162C00	2162	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	159	4			
3144MH0007080031102163C00	2163	14124	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	127	5			
3144MH0007080031102164C00	2164	14184	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	85	6			
3144MH0007080031102165C00	2165	14244	5.48	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	63	7			
3144MH0007080031102166C00	2166	14304	5.20	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	31	8			

updated: 18_June_2021

Sol 3146 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Monpazier - stereo-1 - ~3 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3146MH0006990011102181C00				
best focus image:	3147MH0001530001102233R00	2233	motor count:		14357	range (cm):		5.0	
range map product:	3147MH0001530001102234S00	2234	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	12-Jun-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3146	focus merged on sol:		3147	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3146MH0006990031102183C00	2183	14237	5.51	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	255	1
3146MH0006990031102184C00	2184	14267	5.37	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	223	2
3146MH0006990031102185C00	2185	14297	5.23	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	191	3
3146MH0006990031102186C00	2186	14327	5.10	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	159	4
3146MH0006990031102187C00	2187	14357	4.97	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	127	5
3146MH0006990031102188C00	2188	14387	4.85	-0.1	0.1	24.0	0.4	85	6
3146MH0006990031102189C00	2189	14417	4.73	-0.1	0.1	23.6	0.3	63	7
3146MH0006990031102190C00	2190	14447	4.62	-0.1	0.1	23.1	0.3	31	8

updated: 18_June_2021

Sol 3146 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Monpazier - stereo-2 - ~3 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3146MH0006990011102192C00				
best focus image:	3147MH0001530001102231R00	2231	motor count:		14366	range (cm):		4.9	
range map product:	3147MH0001530001102232S00	2232	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	12-Jun-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3146	focus merged on sol:		3147	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3146MH0006990031102194C00	2194	14246	5.47	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	255	1
3146MH0006990031102195C00	2195	14276	5.33	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	223	2
3146MH0006990031102196C00	2196	14306	5.19	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	191	3
3146MH0006990031102197C00	2197	14336	5.06	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	159	4
3146MH0006990031102198C00	2198	14366	4.94	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	127	5
3146MH0006990031102199C00	2199	14396	4.81	-0.1	0.1	23.8	0.4	85	6
3146MH0006990031102200C00	2200	14426	4.70	-0.1	0.1	23.4	0.3	63	7
3146MH0006990031102201C00	2201	14456	4.58	-0.1	0.1	23.0	0.3	31	8

updated: 18_June_2021

Sol 3146 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nabirat - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3146MH0007400011102206C00				
best focus image:	3147MH0001530001102229R00	2229	motor count:		14014	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3147MH0001530001102230S00	2230	acquired sequence:		mhli00740		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	12-Jun-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3146	focus merged on sol:		3147	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3146MH0007400031102208C00	2208	13798	8.39	-0.2	0.2	36.4	0.8	255	1
3146MH0007400031102209C00	2209	13852	7.93	-0.2	0.2	34.8	0.7	223	2
3146MH0007400031102210C00	2210	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	191	3
3146MH0007400031102211C00	2211	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3146MH0007400031102212C00	2212	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3146MH0007400031102213C00	2213	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	85	6
3146MH0007400031102214C00	2214	14122	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	63	7
3146MH0007400031102215C00	2215	14176	5.82	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	31	8

updated: 18_June_2021

Sol 3146 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nabirat - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3146MH0007400011102217C00				
best focus image:	3147MH0001530001102227R00	2227	motor count:		14007	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3147MH0001530001102228S00	2228	acquired sequence:		mhli00740		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	12-Jun-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3146	focus merged on sol:		3147	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3146MH0007400031102219C00	2219	13791	8.45	-0.2	0.2	36.6	0.8	255	1
3146MH0007400031102220C00	2220	13845	7.98	-0.2	0.2	35.0	0.7	223	2
3146MH0007400031102221C00	2221	13899	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	191	3
3146MH0007400031102222C00	2222	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
3146MH0007400031102223C00	2223	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3146MH0007400031102224C00	2224	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6
3146MH0007400031102225C00	2225	14115	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	63	7
3146MH0007400031102226C00	2226	14169	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	31	8

updated: 07_July_2021

Sol 3160 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Simeyrols - stereo-1 - ~6 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3160MH0007230011102239C00				
best focus image:	3161MH0001530001102291R00	2291	motor count:		13881	range (cm):		7.7	
range map product:	3161MH0001530001102292S00	2292	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Jun-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3160	focus merged on sol:		3161	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3160MH0007230031102241C00	2241	13737	8.96	-0.3	0.2	38.4	0.9	255	1
3160MH0007230031102242C00	2242	13773	8.61	-0.2	0.2	37.2	0.8	223	2
3160MH0007230031102243C00	2243	13809	8.29	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	191	3
3160MH0007230031102244C00	2244	13845	7.98	-0.2	0.2	35.0	0.7	159	4
3160MH0007230031102245C00	2245	13881	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	127	5
3160MH0007230031102246C00	2246	13917	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	85	6
3160MH0007230031102247C00	2247	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	63	7
3160MH0007230031102248C00	2248	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	31	8

updated: 07_July_2021

Sol 3160 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Simeyrols - stereo-2 - ~6 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3160MH0007230011102250C00				
best focus image:	3161MH0001530001102289R00	2289	motor count:		13882	range (cm):		7.7	
range map product:	3161MH0001530001102290S00	2290	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Jun-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3160	focus merged on sol:		3161	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3160MH0007230031102252C00	2252	13738	8.95	-0.3	0.2	38.4	0.9	255	1
3160MH0007230031102253C00	2253	13774	8.60	-0.2	0.2	37.2	0.8	223	2
3160MH0007230031102254C00	2254	13810	8.28	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	191	3
3160MH0007230031102255C00	2255	13846	7.98	-0.2	0.2	35.0	0.7	159	4
3160MH0007230031102256C00	2256	13882	7.69	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	127	5
3160MH0007230031102257C00	2257	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	85	6
3160MH0007230031102258C00	2258	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	63	7
3160MH0007230031102259C00	2259	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	31	8

updated: 07_July_2021

Sol 3160 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Rouffignac - stereo-1 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3160MH0007090011102264C00				
best focus image:	3161MH0001530001102287R00	2287	motor count:		13932	range (cm):		7.3	
range map product:	3161MH0001530001102288S00	2288	acquired sequence:		mhli00709	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Jun-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3160	focus merged on sol:		3161	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3160MH0007090031102266C00	2266	13740	8.93	-0.3	0.2	38.3	0.9	255	1
3160MH0007090031102267C00	2267	13788	8.48	-0.2	0.2	36.7	0.8	223	2
3160MH0007090031102268C00	2268	13836	8.06	-0.2	0.2	35.3	0.7	191	3
3160MH0007090031102269C00	2269	13884	7.67	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	159	4
3160MH0007090031102270C00	2270	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	127	5
3160MH0007090031102271C00	2271	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	85	6
3160MH0007090031102272C00	2272	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
3160MH0007090031102273C00	2273	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 07_July_2021

Sol 3160 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Rouffignac - stereo-2 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3160MH0007090011102275C00				
best focus image:	3161MH0001530001102285R00	2285	motor count:		13922	range (cm):		7.4	
range map product:	3161MH0001530001102286S00	2286	acquired sequence:		mhli00709	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Jun-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3160	focus merged on sol:		3161	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3160MH0007090031102277C00	2277	13730	9.02	-0.3	0.2	38.7	0.9	255	1
3160MH0007090031102278C00	2278	13778	8.57	-0.2	0.2	37.1	0.8	223	2
3160MH0007090031102279C00	2279	13826	8.14	-0.2	0.2	35.6	0.7	191	3
3160MH0007090031102280C00	2280	13874	7.75	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	159	4
3160MH0007090031102281C00	2281	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	127	5
3160MH0007090031102282C00	2282	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	85	6
3160MH0007090031102283C00	2283	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
3160MH0007090031102284C00	2284	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

updated: 09_July_2021

Sol 3167 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pontours - After DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3167MH0006990011102301C00				
best focus image:	3167MH0001530001102352R00	2352	motor count:		13957	range (cm):		7.1	
range map product:	3167MH0001530001102353S00	2353	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	4-Jul-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3167	focus merged on sol:		3167	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3167MH0006990031102303C00	2303	13837	8.05	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	255	1
3167MH0006990031102304C00	2304	13867	7.81	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	223	2
3167MH0006990031102305C00	2305	13897	7.57	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	191	3
3167MH0006990031102306C00	2306	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	159	4
3167MH0006990031102307C00	2307	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	127	5
3167MH0006990031102308C00	2308	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	85	6
3167MH0006990031102309C00	2309	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
3167MH0006990031102310C00	2310	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 09_July_2021

Sol 3167 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pontours - After DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3167MH0006990011102312C00				
best focus image:	3167MH0001530001102350R00	2350	motor count:		13967	range (cm):		7.1	
range map product:	3167MH0001530001102351S00	2351	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	4-Jul-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3167	focus merged on sol:		3167	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3167MH0006990031102314C00	2314	13847	7.97	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	255	1
3167MH0006990031102315C00	2315	13877	7.73	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	223	2
3167MH0006990031102316C00	2316	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	191	3
3167MH0006990031102317C00	2317	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4
3167MH0006990031102318C00	2318	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	127	5
3167MH0006990031102319C00	2319	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	85	6
3167MH0006990031102320C00	2320	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
3167MH0006990031102321C00	2321	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 09_July_2021

Sol 3167 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pontours- After DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3167MH0007850011102323C00			
best focus image:	3167MH0001530001102348R00	2348	motor count:		14971	range (cm):	3.1		
range map product:	3167MH0001530001102349S00	2349	acquired sequence:		mhli00785	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	4-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3167	focus merged on sol:		3167	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3167MH0007850031102325C00	2325	14803	3.50	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	255	1
3167MH0007850031102326C00	2326	14845	3.40	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	223	2
3167MH0007850031102327C00	2327	14887	3.29	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	191	3
3167MH0007850031102328C00	2328	14929	3.20	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	159	4
3167MH0007850031102329C00	2329	14971	3.10	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	127	5
3167MH0007850031102330C00	2330	15013	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	85	6
3167MH0007850031102331C00	2331	15055	2.92	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	63	7
3167MH0007850031102332C00	2332	15097	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	31	8

updated: 09_July_2021

Sol 3167 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pontours- After DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3167MH0006990011102334C00			
best focus image:	3167MH0001530001102346R00	2346	motor count:		13969	range (cm):	7.1		
range map product:	3167MH0001530001102347S00	2347	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	4-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3167	focus merged on sol:		3167	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3167MH0006990031102336C00	2336	13849	7.95	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	255	1
3167MH0006990031102337C00	2337	13879	7.71	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	223	2
3167MH0006990031102338C00	2338	13909	7.48	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	191	3
3167MH0006990031102339C00	2339	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4
3167MH0006990031102340C00	2340	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	127	5
3167MH0006990031102341C00	2341	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	85	6
3167MH0006990031102342C00	2342	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
3167MH0006990031102343C00	2343	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 19_July_2021

Sol 3180 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Chanterac - APXS Spot 5 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3180MH0002970011102384C00				
best focus image:	3180MH0002270001102441R00	2441	motor count:		13999	range (cm):	6.9		
range map product:	3180MH0002270001102442S00	2442	acquired sequence:		mhli00297	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	17-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3180	focus merged on sol:		3180	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3180MH0002970021102385C00	2385	13759	8.74	-0.2	0.2	37.7	0.8	255	1
3180MH0002970021102386C00	2386	13819	8.20	-0.2	0.2	35.8	0.7	223	2
3180MH0002970021102387C00	2387	13879	7.71	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	191	3
3180MH0002970021102388C00	2388	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	159	4
3180MH0002970021102389C00	2389	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3180MH0002970021102390C00	2390	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	85	6
3180MH0002970021102391C00	2391	14119	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	63	7
3180MH0002970021102392C00	2392	14179	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	31	8

updated: 19_July_2021

Sol 3180 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Chanterac - APXS Spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3180MH0002970011102394C00				
best focus image:	3180MH0002270001102439R00	2439	motor count:		13979	range (cm):	7.0		
range map product:	3180MH0002270001102440S00	2440	acquired sequence:		mhli00297	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	17-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3180	focus merged on sol:		3180	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3180MH0002970021102395C00	2395	13739	8.94	-0.3	0.2	38.4	0.9	255	1
3180MH0002970021102396C00	2396	13799	8.38	-0.2	0.2	36.4	0.8	223	2
3180MH0002970021102397C00	2397	13859	7.87	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	191	3
3180MH0002970021102398C00	2398	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	159	4
3180MH0002970021102399C00	2399	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
3180MH0002970021102400C00	2400	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	85	6
3180MH0002970021102401C00	2401	14099	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	63	7
3180MH0002970021102402C00	2402	14159	5.91	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	31	8

updated: 19_July_2021

Sol 3180 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Chanterac - APXS Spot 2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3180MH0002970011102404C00			
best focus image:	3180MH0002270001102437R00		2437	motor count:		13955	range (cm):	7.1	
range map product:	3180MH0002270001102438S00		2438	acquired sequence:		mhli00297	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	17-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3180	focus merged on sol:		3180	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3180MH0002970021102405C00	2405	13715	9.18	-0.3	0.3	39.2	0.9	255	1
3180MH0002970021102406C00	2406	13775	8.59	-0.2	0.2	37.2	0.8	223	2
3180MH0002970021102407C00	2407	13835	8.07	-0.2	0.2	35.3	0.7	191	3
3180MH0002970021102408C00	2408	13895	7.59	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	159	4
3180MH0002970021102409C00	2409	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	127	5
3180MH0002970021102410C00	2410	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	85	6
3180MH0002970021102411C00	2411	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3180MH0002970021102412C00	2412	14135	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 19_July_2021

Sol 3180 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Chanterac - APXS Spot 3 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3180MH0002970011102414C00			
best focus image:	3180MH0002270001102435R00		2435	motor count:		13968	range (cm):	7.1	
range map product:	3180MH0002270001102436S00		2436	acquired sequence:		mhli00297	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	17-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3180	focus merged on sol:		3180	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3180MH0002970021102415C00	2415	13728	9.04	-0.3	0.2	38.7	0.9	255	1
3180MH0002970021102416C00	2416	13788	8.48	-0.2	0.2	36.7	0.8	223	2
3180MH0002970021102417C00	2417	13848	7.96	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	191	3
3180MH0002970021102418C00	2418	13908	7.49	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	159	4
3180MH0002970021102419C00	2419	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	127	5
3180MH0002970021102420C00	2420	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3180MH0002970021102421C00	2421	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3180MH0002970021102422C00	2422	14148	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 19_July_2021

Sol 3180 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Chanterac - APXS Spot 4 - ~5 cm standoff											
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3180MH0002970011102424C00							
best focus image:		3180MH0002270001102433R00		2433		motor count:		13945		range (cm):		7.2	
range map product:		3180MH0002270001102434S00		2434		acquired sequence:		mhli00297		stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:		17-Jul-21				merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type:		Basic	
motor count interval:		60		acquired on sol:		3180		focus merged on sol:		3180			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8				
				near	far								
3180MH0002970021102425C00	2425	13705	9.28	-0.3	0.3	39.6	0.9	255	1				
3180MH0002970021102426C00	2426	13765	8.69	-0.2	0.2	37.5	0.8	223	2				
3180MH0002970021102427C00	2427	13825	8.15	-0.2	0.2	35.6	0.7	191	3				
3180MH0002970021102428C00	2428	13885	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	159	4				
3180MH0002970021102429C00	2429	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	127	5				
3180MH0002970021102430C00	2430	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	85	6				
3180MH0002970021102431C00	2431	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7				
3180MH0002970021102432C00	2432	14125	6.09	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	31	8				

updated: 03_August_2021

Sol 3183 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Montagenet - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3183MH0002990011102448C00				
best focus image:	3183MH0001930001102481R00	2481	motor count:		13977	range (cm):	7.0		
range map product:	3183MH0001930001102482S00	2482	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	20-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3183	focus merged on sol:		3183	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3183MH0002990021102449C00	2449	13833	8.08	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	255	1
3183MH0002990021102450C00	2450	13869	7.79	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	223	2
3183MH0002990021102451C00	2451	13905	7.51	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	191	3
3183MH0002990021102452C00	2452	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	159	4
3183MH0002990021102453C00	2453	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
3183MH0002990021102454C00	2454	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	85	6
3183MH0002990021102455C00	2455	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3183MH0002990021102456C00	2456	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 03_August_2021

Sol 3183 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Montagenet - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3183MH0002990011102458C00				
best focus image:	3183MH0001930001102479R00	2479	motor count:		13994	range (cm):	6.9		
range map product:	3183MH0001930001102480S00	2480	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	20-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3183	focus merged on sol:		3183	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3183MH0002990021102459C00	2459	13850	7.94	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	255	1
3183MH0002990021102460C00	2460	13886	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
3183MH0002990021102461C00	2461	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	191	3
3183MH0002990021102462C00	2462	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
3183MH0002990021102463C00	2463	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3183MH0002990021102464C00	2464	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	85	6
3183MH0002990021102465C00	2465	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3183MH0002990021102466C00	2466	14102	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

updated: 03_August_2021

Sol 3183 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Montagenet- ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3183MH0006490011102468C00				
best focus image:	3183MH0001930001102477R00	2477	motor count:		15086	range (cm):		2.9	
range map product:	3183MH0001930001102478S00	2478	acquired sequence:		mhli00649		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	20-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		78	acquired on sol:		3183	focus merged on sol:		3183	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3183MH0006490021102469C00	2469	14774	3.58	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	255	1
3183MH0006490021102470C00	2470	14852	3.38	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	223	2
3183MH0006490021102471C00	2471	14930	3.19	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	191	3
3183MH0006490021102472C00	2472	15008	3.02	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	159	4
3183MH0006490021102473C00	2473	15086	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	127	5
3183MH0006490021102474C00	2474	15164	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	85	6
3183MH0006490021102475C00	2475	15242	2.57	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	63	7
3183MH0006490021102476C00	2476	15320	2.44	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	31	8

updated: 27_July_2021

Sol 3185 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Javerlhac - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3185MH0008030011102487C00			
best focus image:	3185MH0002650001102510R00	2510	motor count:		14260	range (cm):		5.4	
range map product:	3185MH0002650001102511S00	2511	acquired sequence:		mhli00803	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	22-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		84	acquired on sol:		3185	focus merged on sol:		3185	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3185MH0008030031102489C00	2489	13924	7.37	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
3185MH0008030031102490C00	2490	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	223	2
3185MH0008030031102491C00	2491	14092	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	191	3
3185MH0008030031102492C00	2492	14176	5.82	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	159	4
3185MH0008030031102493C00	2493	14260	5.40	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	127	5
3185MH0008030031102494C00	2494	14344	5.03	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	85	6
3185MH0008030031102495C00	2495	14428	4.69	-0.1	0.1	23.4	0.3	63	7
3185MH0008030031102496C00	2496	14512	4.38	-0.1	0.1	22.3	0.3	31	8

updated: 27_July_2021

Sol 3185 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Javerlhac - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3185MH0008030011102498C00			
best focus image:	3185MH0002650001102508R00	2508	motor count:		14310	range (cm):		5.2	
range map product:	3185MH0002650001102509S00	2509	acquired sequence:		mhli00803	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	22-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		84	acquired on sol:		3185	focus merged on sol:		3185	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3185MH0008030031102500C00	2500	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
3185MH0008030031102501C00	2501	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	223	2
3185MH0008030031102502C00	2502	14142	6.00	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	191	3
3185MH0008030031102503C00	2503	14226	5.56	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	159	4
3185MH0008030031102504C00	2504	14310	5.17	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	127	5
3185MH0008030031102505C00	2505	14394	4.82	-0.1	0.1	23.9	0.4	85	6
3185MH0008030031102506C00	2506	14478	4.50	-0.1	0.1	22.7	0.3	63	7
3185MH0008030031102507C00	2507	14562	4.21	-0.1	0.1	21.7	0.3	31	8

updated: 10_August_2021

Sol 3187 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Chauffour - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3187MH0001820011102515C00				
best focus image:	3188MH0001630001102586R00	2586	motor count:		13989	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3188MH0001630001102587S00	2587	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	24-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3187	focus merged on sol:		3188	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3187MH0001820021102516C00	2516	13893	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3187MH0001820021102517C00	2517	13917	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
3187MH0001820021102518C00	2518	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3187MH0001820021102519C00	2519	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3187MH0001820021102520C00	2520	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3187MH0001820021102521C00	2521	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	85	6
3187MH0001820021102522C00	2522	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
3187MH0001820021102523C00	2523	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 10_August_2021

Sol 3187 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Chauffour - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3187MH0001820011102525C00				
best focus image:	3188MH0001630001102584R00	2584	motor count:		13978	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3188MH0001630001102585S00	2585	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	24-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3187	focus merged on sol:		3188	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3187MH0001820021102526C00	2526	13882	7.69	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	255	1
3187MH0001820021102527C00	2527	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
3187MH0001820021102528C00	2528	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
3187MH0001820021102529C00	2529	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
3187MH0001820021102530C00	2530	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
3187MH0001820021102531C00	2531	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	85	6
3187MH0001820021102532C00	2532	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
3187MH0001820021102533C00	2533	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 10_August_2021

Sol 3187 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Chauffour - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3187MH0003020011102535C00			
best focus image:	3188MH0001630001102582R00		2582	motor count:		14622	range (cm):	4.0	
range map product:	3188MH0001630001102583S00		2583	acquired sequence:		mhli00302	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	24-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3187	focus merged on sol:		3188	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3187MH0003020021102536C00	2536	14502	4.42	-0.1	0.1	22.4	0.3	255	1
3187MH0003020021102537C00	2537	14532	4.31	-0.1	0.1	22.1	0.3	223	2
3187MH0003020021102538C00	2538	14562	4.21	-0.1	0.1	21.7	0.3	191	3
3187MH0003020021102539C00	2539	14592	4.11	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	159	4
3187MH0003020021102540C00	2540	14622	4.02	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	127	5
3187MH0003020021102541C00	2541	14652	3.93	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	85	6
3187MH0003020021102542C00	2542	14682	3.84	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	63	7
3187MH0003020021102543C00	2543	14712	3.75	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	31	8

updated: 10_August_2021

Sol 3187 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Le_Manet - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3187MH0002240011102547C00			
best focus image:	3188MH0001630001102580R00		2580	motor count:		13923	range (cm):	7.4	
range map product:	3188MH0001630001102581S00		2581	acquired sequence:		mhli00224	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	24-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3187	focus merged on sol:		3188	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3187MH0002240021102548C00	2548	13755	8.78	-0.2	0.2	37.8	0.8	255	1
3187MH0002240021102549C00	2549	13797	8.40	-0.2	0.2	36.5	0.8	223	2
3187MH0002240021102550C00	2550	13839	8.03	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	191	3
3187MH0002240021102551C00	2551	13881	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	159	4
3187MH0002240021102552C00	2552	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	127	5
3187MH0002240021102553C00	2553	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	85	6
3187MH0002240021102554C00	2554	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	63	7
3187MH0002240021102555C00	2555	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 10_August_2021

Sol 3187 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Le_Manet - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3187MH0002240011102557C00				
best focus image:	3188MH0001630001102578R00	2578	motor count:		13977	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3188MH0001630001102579S00	2579	acquired sequence:		mhli00224	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	24-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3187	focus merged on sol:		3188	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3187MH0002240021102558C00	2558	13809	8.29	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	255	1
3187MH0002240021102559C00	2559	13851	7.94	-0.2	0.2	34.8	0.7	223	2
3187MH0002240021102560C00	2560	13893	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	191	3
3187MH0002240021102561C00	2561	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	159	4
3187MH0002240021102562C00	2562	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
3187MH0002240021102563C00	2563	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	85	6
3187MH0002240021102564C00	2564	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3187MH0002240021102565C00	2565	14103	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

updated: 10_August_2021

Sol 3187 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Le_Manet - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3187MH0001760011102567C00				
best focus image:	3188MH0001630001102576R00	2576	motor count:		14642	range (cm):		4.0	
range map product:	3188MH0001630001102577S00	2577	acquired sequence:		mhli00176	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	24-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3187	focus merged on sol:		3188	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3187MH0001760021102568C00	2568	14450	4.61	-0.1	0.1	23.1	0.3	255	1
3187MH0001760021102569C00	2569	14498	4.43	-0.1	0.1	22.5	0.3	223	2
3187MH0001760021102570C00	2570	14546	4.26	-0.1	0.1	21.9	0.3	191	3
3187MH0001760021102571C00	2571	14594	4.11	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	159	4
3187MH0001760021102572C00	2572	14642	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	127	5
3187MH0001760021102573C00	2573	14690	3.81	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	85	6
3187MH0001760021102574C00	2574	14738	3.68	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	63	7
3187MH0001760021102575C00	2575	14786	3.55	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	31	8

updated: 11_August_2021

Sol 3190 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Fressignas - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3190MH0007210011102592C00		
best focus image:	3190MH0002650001102615R00	2615		motor count:		14006	range (cm):	6.8	
range map product:	3190MH0002650001102616S00	2616		acquired sequence:		mhli00721	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3190	focus merged on sol:		3190	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3190MH0007210031102594C00	2594	13838	8.04	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	255	1
3190MH0007210031102595C00	2595	13880	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	223	2
3190MH0007210031102596C00	2596	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	191	3
3190MH0007210031102597C00	2597	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3190MH0007210031102598C00	2598	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3190MH0007210031102599C00	2599	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	85	6
3190MH0007210031102600C00	2600	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
3190MH0007210031102601C00	2601	14132	6.05	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	31	8

updated: 11_August_2021

Sol 3190 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Fressignas - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3190MH0007210011102603C00		
best focus image:	3190MH0002650001102613R00	2613		motor count:		13999	range (cm):	6.9	
range map product:	3190MH0002650001102614S00	2614		acquired sequence:		mhli00721	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3190	focus merged on sol:		3190	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3190MH0007210031102605C00	2605	13831	8.10	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	255	1
3190MH0007210031102606C00	2606	13873	7.76	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	223	2
3190MH0007210031102607C00	2607	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	191	3
3190MH0007210031102608C00	2608	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
3190MH0007210031102609C00	2609	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3190MH0007210031102610C00	2610	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	85	6
3190MH0007210031102611C00	2611	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
3190MH0007210031102612C00	2612	14125	6.09	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 03_August_2021

Sol 3192 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Champeaux - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3192MH0001820011102620C00				
best focus image:	3192MH0001930001102653R00	2653	motor count:		13992	range (cm):	6.9		
range map product:	3192MH0001930001102654S00	2654	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	29-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3192	focus merged on sol:		3192	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3192MH0001820021102621C00	2621	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3192MH0001820021102622C00	2622	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3192MH0001820021102623C00	2623	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3192MH0001820021102624C00	2624	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3192MH0001820021102625C00	2625	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3192MH0001820021102626C00	2626	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	85	6
3192MH0001820021102627C00	2627	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3192MH0001820021102628C00	2628	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 03_August_2021

Sol 3192 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Champeaux - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3192MH0001820011102630C00				
best focus image:	3192MH0001930001102651R00	2651	motor count:		13997	range (cm):	6.9		
range map product:	3192MH0001930001102652S00	2652	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	29-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3192	focus merged on sol:		3192	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3192MH0001820021102631C00	2631	13901	7.54	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3192MH0001820021102632C00	2632	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3192MH0001820021102633C00	2633	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3192MH0001820021102634C00	2634	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3192MH0001820021102635C00	2635	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3192MH0001820021102636C00	2636	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	85	6
3192MH0001820021102637C00	2637	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3192MH0001820021102638C00	2638	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

updated: 03_August_2021

Sol 3192 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target EyzeraC - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3192MH0003590011102640C00				
best focus image:	3192MH0001930001102649R00	2649	motor count:		13017	range (cm):		26.5	
range map product:	3192MH0001930001102650S00	2650	acquired sequence:		mhli00359		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	29-Jul-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3192	focus merged on sol:		3192	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3192MH0003590021102641C00	2641	12945	31.68	-2.5	2.9	118.4	9.5	255	1
3192MH0003590021102642C00	2642	12963	30.22	-2.3	2.6	113.3	8.6	223	2
3192MH0003590021102643C00	2643	12981	28.89	-2.1	2.4	108.6	7.9	191	3
3192MH0003590021102644C00	2644	12999	27.66	-1.9	2.2	104.3	7.2	159	4
3192MH0003590021102645C00	2645	13017	26.52	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	127	5
3192MH0003590021102646C00	2646	13035	25.47	-1.6	1.8	96.5	6.1	85	6
3192MH0003590021102647C00	2647	13053	24.49	-1.5	1.7	93.1	5.7	63	7
3192MH0003590021102648C00	2648	13071	23.57	-1.4	1.6	89.9	5.2	31	8

6 Image comment, purpose, RATIONALE_DESC

A RATIONALE_DESC accompanies each MAHLI image and each focus merge product archived with the NASA PDS. It is found in in each archived image label file (.LBL).

The RATIONALE_DESC is a text description of the purpose (rationale) behind the acquisition of each MAHLI parent image.

For onboard focus merge products, the RATIONALE_DESC includes information regarding when the merge was performed and which parent images were merged. This information is not automatically tracked by the instrument or ground data system and thus requires human intervention; this is the only pathway by which this information is conveyed to the data user through the NASA PDS archival products.

The MAHLI PI and his assistants draft each RATIONALE_DESC as the data are acquired and returned to Earth. Final editing of each RATIONALE_DESC is performed a few months before the data are archived with the NASA PDS. In some cases, an error might be detected in a RATIONALE_DESC some time after the data are first archived; in such a case, the corrections are made in a later release of MAHLI data to the PDS (as long as the mission continues and funding is available to do so).

The pages that follow capture the RATIONALE_DESC for each MAHLI image acquired and lists the ID for the best available image or focus merge product returned to Earth. Note that the RATIONALE_DESC also applies to any other child images spawned by a given parent image and thus there might be additional images, not listed here, that correspond to a given RATIONALE_DESC. In some cases, it was only necessary to return a thumbnail image; the IDs for these are given in orange text. As noted earlier, purple text indicates Image IDs for which the last two characters might differ from those in the NASA PDS archives.

Note that the text on the pages that follow is tiny. We highly recommend that the reader view this document electronically (*i.e.*, PDF file on a computer screen) and magnify the view $\geq 400\%$.

The *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* that follow include data acquired Sol 3069–3192. During this period, the instrument obtained images and/or performed focus merges on **Sols 3069, 3070, 3071, 3072, 3074, 3076, 3078, 3079, 3081, 3083, 3085, 3086, 3088, 3092, 3094, 3102, 3110, 3112, 3115, 3117, 3119, 3122, 3124, 3139, 3140, 3142, 3143, 3144, 3145, 3146, 3147, 3160, 3161, 3167, 3168, 3178, 3180, 3181, 3183, 3185, 3187, 3188, 3190, 3192.**

updated: 29_March_2021

Sol 3069 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	25-Mar-21			
		camera position	6	Image ID:		
		total parent images	54	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received		
		focus merges performed	4	CDPID:		
		total focus merge products	8	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
		total parent images + focus merge products	62			
summary of MAHLI activities						
MAHLI imaged the Nontron Sample Discard Pile and the target Chassenon. The focus stack images were also merged.						
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00122	Nontron sample discard pile APXS spot 2 ~55 mm standoff	3069MH00122001101176C00	1176	autofocus sub-frame for Nontron sample discard pile - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm		
		3069MH00122001101177C00	1177	Nontron sample discard pile - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm		
mN00122	Nontron sample discard pile APXS spot 1 ~55 mm standoff	3069MH00122001101178C00	1178	autofocus sub-frame for Nontron sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm		
		3069MH00122001101179C00	1179	Nontron sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm		
mN00706	Chassenon APXS spot 3 ~25 cm standoff	3069MH00706001101180C00	1180	autofocus sub-frame for target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 25 cm		
		3069MH00706001101181C00	1181	target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 25 cm		
		3069MH00706001101182C00	1182	target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mN00763	Chassenon APXS spot 3 ~5 cm standoff	3069MH00763001101183C00	1183	autofocus sub-frame for target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3069MH00763001101184C00	1184	target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3069MH00763001101185C00	1185	target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3069MH00763001101186C00	1186	target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00763001101187C00	1187	target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00763001101188C00	1188	target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00763001101189C00	1189	target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00763001101190C00	1190	target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00763001101191C00	1191	target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00763001101192C00	1192	target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00763001101193C00	1193	target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00794	Chassenon APXS spot 3 ~1 cm standoff	3069MH00794001101194C00	1194	autofocus sub-frame for target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 1 cm
				3069MH00794001101195C00	1195	target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 1 cm
3069MH00794001101196C00	1196			target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
3069MH00794001101197C00	1197			target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3069MH00794001101198C00	1198			target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3069MH00794001101199C00	1199			target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3069MH00794001101200C00	1200			target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3069MH00794001101201C00	1201			target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3069MH00794001101202C00	1202			target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3069MH00794001101203C00	1203			target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3069MH00794001101204C00	1204			target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00763	Chassenon APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff			3069MH00763001101205C00	1205	autofocus sub-frame for target Chassenon - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3069MH00763001101206C00	1206	target Chassenon - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3069MH00763001101207C00	1207	target Chassenon - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3069MH00763001101208C00	1208	target Chassenon - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00763001101209C00	1209	target Chassenon - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00763001101210C00	1210	target Chassenon - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00763001101211C00	1211	target Chassenon - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00763001101212C00	1212	target Chassenon - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00763001101213C00	1213	target Chassenon - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00763001101214C00	1214	target Chassenon - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00763001101215C00	1215	target Chassenon - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00706	Chassenon APXS spot 1 ~25 cm standoff	3069MH00706001101216C00	1216	autofocus sub-frame for target Chassenon - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
				3069MH00706001101217C00	1217	target Chassenon - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
3069MH00706001101218C00	1218			target Chassenon - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mN00721	Chassenon APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3069MH00721001101219C00	1219	autofocus sub-frame for target Chassenon - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3069MH00721001101220C00	1220	target Chassenon - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3069MH00721001101221C00	1221	target Chassenon - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3069MH00721001101222C00	1222	target Chassenon - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00721001101223C00	1223	target Chassenon - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00721001101224C00	1224	target Chassenon - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00721001101225C00	1225	target Chassenon - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00721001101226C00	1226	target Chassenon - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00721001101227C00	1227	target Chassenon - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00721001101228C00	1228	target Chassenon - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3069MH00721001101229C00	1229	target Chassenon - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00153	Focus Merges	3069MH00153001101230R00	1230	target Chassenon - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3069 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID= 1222-1229 - best focus image product
				3069MH00153001101231S00	1231	target Chassenon - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3069 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID= 1222-1229 - range map product
3069MH00153001101232R00	1232			target Chassenon - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3069 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID= 1208-1215 - best focus image product		
3069MH00153001101233S00	1233			target Chassenon - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3069 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID= 1208-1215 - range map product		
3069MH00153001101234R00	1234			target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3069 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID= 1197-1204 - best focus image product		
3069MH00153001101235S00	1235			target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3069 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID= 1197-1204 - range map product		
3069MH00153001101236R00	1236			target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3069 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID= 1186-1193 - best focus image product		
3069MH00153001101237S00	1237			target Chassenon - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3069 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID= 1186-1193 - range map product		

updated: 30_March_2021

Sol 3071 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27-Mar-21
camera positions	2
total parent images	19
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	19

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
summary of MAHLI activities: During the day, MAHLI imaged the REMS UV sensor and the target Chassenon. At night, MAHLI acquired a dark current assessment image to help with the Sol 3071 triboluminescence study and MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.				
mnh00095	REMS UV sensor ~15 cm standoff	3071MH000950001101298C00	1298	autofocus sub-frame for REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
		3071MH000950001101299C00	1299	REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
mnh00763	Chassenon APXS spot 4 ~5 cm standoff	3071MH000763001101300C00	1300	autofocus sub-frame for target Chassenon - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm
		3071MH000763001101301C00	1301	target Chassenon - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm
		3071MH000763001101302C00	1302	target Chassenon - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3071MH000763001101303C00	1303	target Chassenon - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3071MH000763001101304C00	1304	target Chassenon - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3071MH000763001101305C00	1305	target Chassenon - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3071MH000763001101306C00	1306	target Chassenon - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3071MH000763001101307C00	1307	target Chassenon - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3071MH000763001101308C00	1308	target Chassenon - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3071MH000763001101309C00	1309	target Chassenon - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3071MH000763001101310C00	1310	target Chassenon - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mnh00826	dark current assessment image dust cover closed no blue analysis regions	3071MH0008260001101311C00	1311	dark current image to support sol 3071 triboluminescence investigation - no focus mechanism motion - dust cover closed - at night with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure
mnh00312	MAHLI 12.4 cm working distance above CheMin inlet mesh; inlet cover open; position 1 of 3; imaging at night	3071MH0003120001101312C00	1312	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
		3071MH0003120001101313C00	1313	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at mesh at 124 mm working distance
mnh00226	position 2 of 3, otherwise same as above	3071MH0003260001101314C00	1314	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mnh00326	position 3 of 3, otherwise same as two above	3071MH0003260001101315C00	1315	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mnh00228	~17 cm above open CheMin inlet	3071MH0002280001101316C00	1316	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at 17 cm working distance

updated: 29_March_2021

Sol 3072 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)		28-Mar-21		
camera positions:	3	Image ID:		
total parent images:	2	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
focus merges performed:	1	CCPFD:		
total focus merge products:	2	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
total parent images + focus merge products:	4			
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the Nontron drill cuttings and the Sol 3071 focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CCPFD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00122	Nontron drill cuttings ~5 cm standoff	3072MH001220001101317C00	1317	autofocus sub-frame for Nontron drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm
		3072MH001220011101318C00	1318	Nontron drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm
mN00258	Focus Merge	3072MH002580001101319R00	1319	target Chassenon - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3071 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1303-1310 - best focus image product
		3072MH002580001101320S00	1320	target Chassenon - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3071 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1303-1310 - range map product

updated: 26_April_2021

Sol 3074 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	30-Mar-21
camera positions	2
total parent images	23
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the target Bara_Bahau and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Bara_Bahau ~25 cm standoff	3074MH00190001101321C0D	1321	autofocus sub-frame for target Bara_Bahau - standoff near 25 cm
		3074MH00190001101322C0D	1322	target Bara_Bahau - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Bara_Bahau stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3074MH001680021101323C0D	1323	autofocus sub-frame for target Bara_Bahau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3074MH001680021101324C0D	1324	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3074MH001680021101325C0D	1325	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3074MH001680021101326C0D	1326	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3074MH001680021101327C0D	1327	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3074MH001680021101328C0D	1328	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3074MH001680021101329C0D	1329	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3074MH001680021101330C0D	1330	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3074MH001680021101331C0D	1331	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3074MH001680021101332C0D	1332	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Bara_Bahau stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3074MH001680021101333C0D	1333	autofocus sub-frame for target Bara_Bahau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3074MH001680021101334C0D	1334	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3074MH001680021101335C0D	1335	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3074MH001680021101336C0D	1336	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3074MH001680021101337C0D	1337	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3074MH001680021101338C0D	1338	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3074MH001680021101339C0D	1339	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3074MH001680021101340C0D	1340	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3074MH001680021101341C0D	1341	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3074MH001680021101342C0D	1342	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00205	Focus Merges	3074MH002050001101343R0D	1343	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3074 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1335-1342 - best focus image product
		3074MH002050001101344S0D	1344	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3074 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1335-1342 - range map product
		3074MH002050001101345R0D	1345	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3074 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1325-1332 - best focus image product
		3074MH002050001101346S0D	1346	target Bara_Bahau - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3074 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1325-1332 - range map product

updated: 29_April_2021

Sol 3076 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	0 Apr 21
camera position:	0
total parent images:	23
focus merges performed:	2
total focus merge products:	4
total parent images + focus merge products:	26

MAHLI imaged the target Tursac and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Tursac ~25 cm standoff	3076MH00190001101247C0D	1347	autofocus sub-frame for target Tursac - standoff near 25 cm
		3076MH00190001101348C0D	1348	target Tursac - standoff near 25 cm
		3076MH003060021101249C0D	1349	autofocus sub-frame for target Tursac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00306	Tursac stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3076MH003060021101350C0D	1350	target Tursac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3076MH003060021101351C0D	1351	target Tursac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3076MH003060021101352C0D	1352	target Tursac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3076MH003060021101353C0D	1353	target Tursac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3076MH003060021101354C0D	1354	target Tursac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3076MH003060021101355C0D	1355	target Tursac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3076MH003060021101356C0D	1356	target Tursac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3076MH003060021101357C0D	1357	target Tursac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3076MH003060021101358C0D	1358	target Tursac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00306	Tursac stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3076MH003060021101359C0D
3076MH003060021101360C0D	1360			target Tursac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
3076MH003060021101361C0D	1361			target Tursac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3076MH003060021101362C0D	1362			target Tursac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
3076MH003060021101363C0D	1363			target Tursac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3076MH003060021101364C0D	1364			target Tursac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
3076MH003060021101365C0D	1365			target Tursac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
3076MH003060021101366C0D	1366			target Tursac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
3076MH003060021101367C0D	1367			target Tursac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3076MH003060021101368C0D	1368			target Tursac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00265	Focus Merges	3076MH002650001101369R0D	1369	target Tursac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3076 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1361-1368 - best focus image product
		3076MH002650001101370S0D	1370	target Tursac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3076 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1361-1368 - range map product
		3076MH002650001101371R0D	1371	target Tursac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3076 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1351-1358 - best focus image product
		3076MH002650001101372S0D	1372	target Tursac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3076 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1351-1358 - range map product

Sol 3078 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	0_Apr_21			
		camera positions	54	Image ID:		
		total parent images	54	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:		
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
		total parent images + focus merge products	54			
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI acquired the first part of a 2-sol activity for full rover wheel inspection (to image a 360° surface of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel). MAHLI also imaged the targets Garve and Scoor.						
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3078MH0007690011013730I	1373	rover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm		
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3078MH0007700011013740I	1374	rover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm		
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3078MH0007710011013750I	1375	rover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm		
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3078MH0007720011013760I	1376	rover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm		
mN00706	Garve ~25 cm standoff	3078MH0007060011013770C	1377	autofocus sub-frame for target Garve - bedform trough - standoff near 25 cm		
		3078MH0007060011013780C	1378	target Garve - bedform trough - standoff near 25 cm		
		3078MH0007060011013790C	1379	target Garve - bedform trough - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mN00763	Garve stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3078MH0007630011013800C	1380	autofocus sub-frame for target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3078MH0007630011013810C	1381	target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3078MH0007630011013820C	1382	target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3078MH0007630011013830C	1383	target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3078MH0007630011013840C	1384	target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3078MH0007630011013850C	1385	target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3078MH0007630011013860C	1386	target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3078MH0007630011013870C	1387	target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3078MH0007630011013880C	1388	target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3078MH0007630011013890C	1389	target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3078MH0007630011013900C	1390	target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00763	Garve stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3078MH0007630011013910C	1391	autofocus sub-frame for target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				3078MH0007630011013920C	1392	target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
3078MH0007630011013930C	1393			target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
3078MH0007630011013940C	1394			target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3078MH0007630011013950C	1395			target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3078MH0007630011013960C	1396			target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3078MH0007630011013970C	1397			target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3078MH0007630011013980C	1398			target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3078MH0007630011013990C	1399			target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3078MH0007630011014000C	1400			target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3078MH0007630011014010C	1401			target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00706	Scoor ~25 cm standoff			3078MH0007060011014020C	1402	autofocus sub-frame for target Scoor - bedform crest - standoff near 25 cm
				3078MH0007060011014030C	1403	target Scoor - bedform crest - standoff near 25 cm
		3078MH0007060011014040C	1404	target Scoor - bedform crest - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mN00709	Scoor stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3078MH0007090011014050C	1405	autofocus sub-frame for target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3078MH0007090011014060C	1406	target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3078MH0007090011014070C	1407	target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3078MH0007090011014080C	1408	target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3078MH0007090011014090C	1409	target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3078MH0007090011014100C	1410	target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3078MH0007090011014110C	1411	target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3078MH0007090011014120C	1412	target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3078MH0007090011014130C	1413	target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3078MH0007090011014140C	1414	target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3078MH0007090011014150C	1415	target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00709	Scoor stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3078MH0007090011014160C	1416	autofocus sub-frame for target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				3078MH0007090011014170C	1417	target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
3078MH0007090011014180C	1418			target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
3078MH0007090011014190C	1419			target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3078MH0007090011014200C	1420			target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3078MH0007090011014210C	1421			target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3078MH0007090011014220C	1422			target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3078MH0007090011014230C	1423			target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3078MH0007090011014240C	1424			target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3078MH0007090011014250C	1425			target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3078MH0007090011014260C	1426			target Scoor - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 26_April_2021

Sol 3079 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	4 Apr 21
camera position	12
total parent images	15
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	23

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CPDID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

MAHLI imaged the target Garve and acquired the second part of a 2-sol activity for full over wheel inspection (to image ≥ 360° surface of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel). The focus stack images from Sol 3078 were merged as well.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00022	-4 cm standoff	3079MH0001220011014770D	1427	autofocus sub-frame for target Garve - bedform trough - standoff near 4 cm
		3079MH0001220011014280D	1428	target Garve - bedform trough - standoff near 4 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3079MH0007690011014290E1	1429	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3079MH000770001101430E1	1430	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3079MH000771001101431E1	1431	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3079MH000772001101432E1	1432	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3079MH000769001101433E1	1433	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3079MH000770001101434E1	1434	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3079MH000771001101435E1	1435	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3079MH000772001101436E1	1436	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3079MH000769001101437E1	1437	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3079MH000770001101438E1	1438	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3079MH000771001101439E1	1439	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3079MH000772001101440E1	1440	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3079MH000769001101441E1	1441	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3079MH000770001101442E1	1442	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3079MH000771001101443E1	1443	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3079MH000772001101444E1	1444	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sols 3078 and 3079 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mN00707	Focus Merges	3079MH0007070001101445R0	1445	target Scour - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3078 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1419-1426 - best focus image product
		3079MH0007070001101446S0	1446	target Scour - bedform crest - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3078 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1419-1426 - range map product
		3079MH0007070001101447R0	1447	target Scour - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3078 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1408-1415 - best focus image product
		3079MH0007070001101448S0	1448	target Scour - bedform crest - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3078 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1408-1415 - range map product
		3079MH0007070001101449R0	1449	target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3078 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1394-1401 - best focus image product
		3079MH0007070001101450S0	1450	target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3078 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1394-1401 - range map product
		3079MH0007070001101451R0	1451	target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3078 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1383-1390 - best focus image product
		3079MH0007070001101452S0	1452	target Garve - bedform trough - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3078 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1383-1390 - range map product

updated: 29_April_2021

Sol 3081 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	6 Apr 21
camera positions	2
total parent images	23
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	27

MAHLI imaged the target Orlicac and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00706	Orlicac ~25 cm standoff	3081MH0007060001101453C00	1453	autofocus sub-frame for target Orlicac - standoff near 25 cm
		3081MH000706001101454C00	1454	target Orlicac - standoff near 25 cm
		3081MH0007060021101455C00	1455	target Orlicac - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00299	Orlicac stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3081MH000299001101456C00	1456	autofocus sub-frame for target Orlicac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3081MH000299001101457C00	1457	target Orlicac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3081MH0002990021101458C00	1458	target Orlicac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3081MH0002990031101459C00	1459	target Orlicac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3081MH0002990041101460C00	1460	target Orlicac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3081MH0002990051101461C00	1461	target Orlicac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3081MH0002990061101462C00	1462	target Orlicac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3081MH0002990071101463C00	1463	target Orlicac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3081MH0002990081101464C00	1464	target Orlicac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3081MH0002990091101465C00	1465	target Orlicac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00299	Orlicac stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3081MH000299001101466C00	1466	autofocus sub-frame for target Orlicac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3081MH000299001101467C00	1467	target Orlicac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3081MH0002990021101468C00	1468	target Orlicac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3081MH0002990031101469C00	1469	target Orlicac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3081MH0002990041101470C00	1470	target Orlicac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3081MH0002990051101471C00	1471	target Orlicac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3081MH0002990061101472C00	1472	target Orlicac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3081MH0002990071101473C00	1473	target Orlicac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3081MH0002990081101474C00	1474	target Orlicac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3081MH0002990091101475C00	1475	target Orlicac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00265	Focus Merges	3081MH0002650001101476R00	1476	target Orlicac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3081 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1468-1475 - best focus image product
		3081MH0002650001101477S00	1477	target Orlicac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3081 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1468-1475 - range map product
		3081MH0002650001101478R00	1478	target Orlicac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3081 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1458-1465 - best focus image product
		3081MH0002650001101479S00	1479	target Orlicac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3081 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1458-1465 - range map product

updated: 26_April_2021

Sol 3083 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	8 Apr 21
camera positions	2
total parent images	23
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	27

MAHLI imaged the target Puyangou and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00706	Puyangou ~25 cm standoff	30E3MH0007060001101400C00	1480	autofocus sub-frame for target Puyangou - standoff near 25 cm
		30E3MH000706001101481C00	1481	target Puyangou - standoff near 25 cm
		30E3MH0007060021101402C00	1482	target Puyangou - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00152	Puyangou stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	30E3MH0001520001101483C00	1483	autofocus sub-frame for target Puyangou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		30E3MH0001520011101404C00	1484	target Puyangou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		30E3MH0001520021101485C00	1485	target Puyangou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		30E3MH0001520031101486C00	1486	target Puyangou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		30E3MH0001520041101487C00	1487	target Puyangou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		30E3MH0001520051101488C00	1488	target Puyangou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		30E3MH0001520061101489C00	1489	target Puyangou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		30E3MH0001520071101490C00	1490	target Puyangou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		30E3MH0001520081101491C00	1491	target Puyangou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		30E3MH0001520091101492C00	1492	target Puyangou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00152	Puyangou stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	30E3MH0001520001101493C00	1493	autofocus sub-frame for target Puyangou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		30E3MH0001520011101494C00	1494	target Puyangou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		30E3MH0001520021101495C00	1495	target Puyangou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		30E3MH0001520031101496C00	1496	target Puyangou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		30E3MH0001520041101497C00	1497	target Puyangou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		30E3MH0001520051101498C00	1498	target Puyangou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		30E3MH0001520061101499C00	1499	target Puyangou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		30E3MH0001520071101500C00	1500	target Puyangou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		30E3MH0001520081101501C00	1501	target Puyangou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		30E3MH0001520091101502C00	1502	target Puyangou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00265	Focus Merges	30E3MH0002650001101503R00	1503	target Puyangou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3083 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1495-1502 - best focus image product
		30E3MH0002650001101504S00	1504	target Puyangou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3083 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1495-1502 - range map product
		30E3MH0002650001101505R00	1505	target Puyangou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3083 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1485-1492 - best focus image product
		30E3MH0002650001101506S00	1506	target Puyangou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3083 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1485-1492 - range map product

Sol 3085 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	11-Apr-21
camera position	13
total parent images	75
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	75

MAHLI imaged the sky, with the dust cover open and closed for flat fielding, and the DRT-brushed target Peyrignac.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mNI00712	sky flats - dust cover closed - MAHLI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +115° azimuth, +35° elevation, away from the rover deck	3085MH0007120001101507000	1507	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 0 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm		
		3085MH000712001101508000	1508	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 2412 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm		
		3085MH000712002101509000	1509	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 3078 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm		
		3085MH000712003101510000	1510	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4062 - focus as if for working distance of 248 mm		
		3085MH000712004101511000	1511	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4488 - near infinity focus		
mNI00453	sky flats - MAHLI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +115° azimuth, +35° elevation, away from the rover deck	3085MH0004530001101512000	1512	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 15996 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm		
		3085MH000453002101513000	1513	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 14664 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm		
		3085MH000453003101514000	1514	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13998 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm		
		3085MH000453004101515000	1515	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12014 - focus as if for working distance of 267 mm		
		3085MH000453005101516000	1516	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12750 - focus as if for working distance of 613 mm		
mNI00453	sky flats - MAHLI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +115° azimuth, +35° elevation, away from the rover deck camera rotated 180° relative to the preceding set of sky flats	3085MH000453006101517000	1517	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12552 - near infinity focus		
		3085MH000453007101518000	1518	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 15996 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		3085MH000453008101519000	1519	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 14664 - focus as if for working distance of 39 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		3085MH000453009101520000	1520	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13998 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		3085MH000453010101521000	1521	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 13014 - focus as if for working distance of 267 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
mNI00712	sky flats - dust cover closed - MAHLI looking at the sky opposite the sun at +115° azimuth, +25° elevation, away from the rover deck camera rotated 180° relative to the preceding set of sky flats	3085MH000712001101522000	1522	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12750 - focus as if for working distance of 613 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		3085MH000712002101523000	1523	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover open - manual focus at motor count 12552 - near infinity focus - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		3085MH000712003101524000	1524	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 15996 - close focus position - focus as if for working distance 21 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		3085MH000712004101525000	1525	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 13014 - focus as if for working distance of 267 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		3085MH000712005101526000	1526	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 3078 - focus as if for working distance of 69 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
mNI00706	Peyrignac after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3085MH000706000101527000	1527	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4062 - focus as if for working distance of 248 mm - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		3085MH000712006101528000	1528	MAHLI sky flat field image - dust cover closed - manual focus at motor count 4488 - near infinity focus - camera head rotated 180-degrees relative to previous acquired this same sol		
		3085MH000706001101529000	1529	autofocus sub-frame for target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm		
		3085MH000706002101530000	1530	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm		
		3085MH000706003101531000	1531	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00721	Peyrignac after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 relief model position 1 ~5 cm standoff	3085MH000712007101532000	1532	autofocus sub-frame for target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3085MH000712008101533000	1533	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3085MH000712009101534000	1534	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3085MH000712010101535000	1535	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3085MH000712011101536000	1536	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3085MH000712012101537000	1537	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3085MH000712013101538000	1538	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3085MH000712014101539000	1539	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3085MH000712015101540000	1540	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3085MH0007120161015410000	1541	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3085MH0007120171015420000	1542	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3085MH0007120181015430000	1543	autofocus sub-frame for target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3085MH0007120191015440000	1544	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3085MH0007120201015450000	1545	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3085MH0007120211015460000	1546	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00705	Peyrignac after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 relief model position 2 ~5 cm standoff	3085MH0007120221015470000	1547	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3085MH0007120231015480000	1548	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3085MH0007120241015490000	1549	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3085MH0007120251015500000	1550	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3085MH00071202610155100000	1551	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3085MH00071202710155200000	1552	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3085MH00071202810155300000	1553	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3085MH0007050011015540000	1554	autofocus sub-frame for target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3085MH0007050021015550000	1555	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm		
		mNI00705	Peyrignac after DRT APXS spot 2 relief model position 4 ~5 cm standoff	3085MH0007050031015560000	1556	autofocus sub-frame for target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
				3085MH0007050041015570000	1557	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
				3085MH0007050051015580000	1558	autofocus sub-frame for target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
				3085MH0007050061015590000	1559	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
				3085MH0007050071015600000	1560	autofocus sub-frame for target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm
		mNI00795	Peyrignac after DRT APXS spot 2 ~2 cm standoff	3085MH0007950011015610000	1561	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm
3085MH0007950021015620000	1562			target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
3085MH0007950031015630000	1563			target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3085MH0007950041015640000	1564			target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3085MH0007950051015650000	1565			target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3085MH0007950061015660000	1566			target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3085MH0007950071015670000	1567			target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3085MH0007950081015680000	1568			target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3085MH0007950091015690000	1569			target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3085MH0007950101015700000	1570			target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

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mH00721	Peyrignac after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3085MH0072100011015174C00	1571	autofocus sub-frame for target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3085MH0072100111015172C00	1572	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3085MH0072100211015173C00	1573	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3085MH0072100311015174C00	1574	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3085MH0072100311015175C00	1575	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3085MH0072100311015176C00	1576	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3085MH0072100311015177C00	1577	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3085MH0072100311015178C00	1578	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3085MH0072100311015179C00	1579	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3085MH0072100311015180C00	1580	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3085MH0072100311015181C00	1581	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 12_April_2021

Sol 3086 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	11_Apr_21
camera positions	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	8

summary of MAHLI activities: The focus stack images from Sol 3085 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00133	Focus Merges	3086MH001530001101582N00	1582	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3085 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1574-1581 - best focus image product
		3086MH001530001101583S00	1583	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3085 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1574-1581 - range map product
		3086MH001530001101584N00	1584	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3085 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1563-1570 - best focus image product
		3086MH001530001101585S00	1585	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3085 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1563-1570 - range map product
		3086MH001530001101586N00	1586	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3085 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1546-1553 - best focus image product
		3086MH001530001101587S00	1587	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3085 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1546-1553 - range map product
		3086MH001530001101588N00	1588	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3085 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1535-1542 - best focus image product
		3086MH001530001101589S00	1589	target Peyrignac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3085 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1535-1542 - range map product

updated: 29_April_2021

Sol 3092 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18-Apr-21
camera position	2
total parent images	59
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	54

MAHLI imaged the target Cussac and the Intendod drill target Bardou after the Sol 3090 DRT and a drill bit preload test; then the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00290	Cussac ~25 cm standoff	302MH0001900011016280C0	1628	autofocus sub-frame for target Cussac - standoff near 25 cm
		302MH0001900011016290C0	1629	target Cussac - standoff near 25 cm
mN00268	Cussac ~5 cm standoff	302MH0001680021016300C0	1630	autofocus sub-frame for target Cussac - standoff near 5 cm
		302MH0001680011016310C0	1631	target Cussac - standoff near 5 cm
		302MH0001680021016320C0	1632	target Cussac - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0001680021016330C0	1633	target Cussac - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0001680021016340C0	1634	target Cussac - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0001680021016350C0	1635	target Cussac - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0001680021016360C0	1636	target Cussac - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0001680021016370C0	1637	target Cussac - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0001680021016380C0	1638	target Cussac - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0001680021016390C0	1639	target Cussac - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00706	Bardou after sol 3090 DRT ~25 cm standoff	302MH0007600011016400C0	1640	autofocus sub-frame for intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		302MH0007600011016410C0	1641	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00763	Bardou after sol 3090 DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	302MH0007600021016420C0	1642	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		302MH0007600011016430C0	1643	autofocus sub-frame for intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		302MH0007600011016440C0	1644	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		302MH0007600011016450C0	1645	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		302MH0007600011016460C0	1646	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0007600011016470C0	1647	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0007600011016480C0	1648	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0007600011016490C0	1649	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0007600011016500C0	1650	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0007600011016510C0	1651	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00763	Bardou after sol 3090 DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	302MH0007600011016520C0	1652	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0007600011016530C0	1653	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0007600011016540C0	1654	autofocus sub-frame for intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		302MH0007600011016550C0	1655	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		302MH0007600011016560C0	1656	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		302MH0007600011016570C0	1657	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0007600011016580C0	1658	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0007600011016590C0	1659	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0007600011016600C0	1660	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0007600011016610C0	1661	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00813	Bardou after sol 3090 DRT ~2 cm standoff	302MH0008100011016620C0	1662	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0008100011016630C0	1663	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0008100011016640C0	1664	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0008100011016650C0	1665	autofocus sub-frame for intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		302MH0008100011016660C0	1666	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		302MH0008100011016670C0	1667	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		302MH0008100011016680C0	1668	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0008100011016690C0	1669	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0008100011016700C0	1670	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0008100011016710C0	1671	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00465	Bardou after sol 3090 DRT after drill bit preload test ~35 cm standoff	302MH0004650011016720C0	1672	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0004650011016730C0	1673	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00153	Focus Merges	302MH0008100011016740C0	1674	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0008100011016750C0	1675	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		302MH0004650011016760C0	1676	autofocus sub-frame for intended Bardou drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
		302MH0004650011016770C0	1677	intended Bardou drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
		302MH0001530011016780C0	1678	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3092 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1668-1675 - best focus image product
		302MH0001530011016790C0	1679	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3092 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1668-1675 - range map product
		302MH0001530011016800C0	1680	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3092 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1657-1664 - best focus image product
		302MH0001530011016810C0	1681	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3092 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1657-1664 - range map product
302MH0001530011016820C0	1682	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3092 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1646-1653 - best focus image product		
302MH0001530011016830C0	1683	intended Bardou drill site - after sol 3090 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3092 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1646-1653 - range map product		
302MH0001530011016840C0	1684	target Cussac - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3092 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1632-1639 - best focus image product		
302MH0001530011016850C0	1685	target Cussac - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3092 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1632-1639 - range map product		

updated: 29_April_2021

Sol 3102 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	28-Apr-21
camera positions	6
total parent images	13
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	13

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the Bardou sample discard pile, the Bardou drill hole and the surfaces surrounding SAM Inlet #2, with the inlet cover open, a follow-up to Bardou sample drop-offs.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00187	Bardou sample discard pile ~25 cm standoff	3102MH001970001101692C00	1692	autofocus sub-frame for Bardou sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
		3102MH001970001101693C00	1693	Bardou sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00187	Bardou drill hole drilled on Sol 3094 ~25 cm standoff	3102MH001970001101694C00	1694	autofocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Bardou - drilled sol 3094 - standoff near 25 cm
		3102MH001970001101695C00	1695	drill hole in rock named Bardou - drilled sol 3094 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00774	Bardou drill hole drilled on Sol 3094 ~10 cm standoff	3102MH007740001101696C00	1696	autofocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Bardou - drilled sol 3094 - sub-frame positioned to focus on surface outside hole - standoff near 10 cm
		3102MH007740001101697C00	1697	drill hole in rock named Bardou - drilled sol 3094 - focus based on preceding autofocus sub-frame - standoff near 10 cm
mN00779	SAM Inlet 2 ~20 cm standoff	3102MH007790001101698C00	1698	SAM inlet 2 cover open after sample drop-off - inspect surface surrounding inlet perimeter - manual focus assuming 231 mm working distance
		3102MH007790001101699C00	1699	autofocus sub-frame for SAM inlet 2 cover open after sample drop-off - inspect surface surrounding inlet perimeter - standoff near 20 cm
		3102MH007790001101700C00	1700	SAM inlet 2 cover open after sample drop-off - inspect surface surrounding inlet perimeter - standoff near 20 cm
mN00122	Bardou sample discard pile APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3102MH001220001101701C00	1701	autofocus sub-frame for Bardou sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3102MH001220001101702C00	1702	Bardou sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00122	Bardou sample discard pile APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	3102MH001220001101703C00	1703	autofocus sub-frame for Bardou sample discard pile - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3102MH001220001101704C00	1704	Bardou sample discard pile - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm

updated: 10_May_2021

Sol 3110 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	8-May-21
camera positions	4
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	8
total parent images - focus merge products	42
Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	

MAHLI sol 3110 activities were the first to occur following a mechanism fault that occurred on sol 3103 which left the dust cover in a partially open state. An attempt to complete dust cover opening and closure on sol 3105 resulted in an additional fault. That fault was studied, found to be understood, and the dust cover was driven closed and into its launch restraint position on sol 3108. On sol 3110, MAHLI imaged the target Gourdron and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mhl00706	Gourdron ~25 cm standoff	3110MH0007060001101705C00	1705	autofocus sub-frame for target Gourdron - standoff near 25 cm
		3110MH000706001101706C00	1706	target Gourdron - standoff near 25 cm
		3110MH0007060021101707C00	1707	target Gourdron - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mhl00723	Gourdron stereo-1 ~55 mm standoff	3110MH0007230001101708C00	1708	autofocus sub-frame for target Gourdron - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		3110MH0007230011101709C00	1709	target Gourdron - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		3110MH0007230021101710C00	1710	target Gourdron - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3110MH0007230031101711C00	1711	target Gourdron - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007230041101712C00	1712	target Gourdron - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007230051101713C00	1713	target Gourdron - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007230061101714C00	1714	target Gourdron - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007230071101715C00	1715	target Gourdron - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007230081101716C00	1716	target Gourdron - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007230091101717C00	1717	target Gourdron - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007230101101718C00	1718	target Gourdron - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00723	Gourdron stereo-2 ~55 mm standoff	3110MH0007230011101719C00	1719	autofocus sub-frame for target Gourdron - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		3110MH0007230021101720C00	1720	target Gourdron - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		3110MH0007230031101721C00	1721	target Gourdron - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3110MH0007230041101722C00	1722	target Gourdron - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007230051101723C00	1723	target Gourdron - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007230061101724C00	1724	target Gourdron - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007230071101725C00	1725	target Gourdron - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007230081101726C00	1726	target Gourdron - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007230091101727C00	1727	target Gourdron - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007230101101728C00	1728	target Gourdron - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH000723011101729C00	1729	target Gourdron - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00797	Gourdron ~35 mm standoff	3110MH0007970001101730C00	1730	autofocus sub-frame for target Gourdron - standoff near 35 mm
		3110MH0007970011101731C00	1731	target Gourdron - standoff near 35 mm
		3110MH0007970021101732C00	1732	target Gourdron - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3110MH0007970031101733C00	1733	target Gourdron - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007970041101734C00	1734	target Gourdron - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007970051101735C00	1735	target Gourdron - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007970061101736C00	1736	target Gourdron - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007970071101737C00	1737	target Gourdron - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007970081101738C00	1738	target Gourdron - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007970091101739C00	1739	target Gourdron - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3110MH0007970101101740C00	1740	target Gourdron - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00189	Focus Merges	3110MH0001930001101741K00	1741	target Gourdron - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3110 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1733-1740 - best focus image product
		3110MH0001930001101742K00	1742	target Gourdron - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3110 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1733-1740 - range map product
		3110MH000193001101743K00	1743	target Gourdron - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3110 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1722-1729 - best focus image product
		3110MH0001930001101744K00	1744	target Gourdron - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3110 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1722-1729 - range map product
		3110MH0001930001101745K00	1745	target Gourdron - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3110 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1711-1718 - best focus image product
3110MH0001930001101746K00	1746	target Gourdron - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3110 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1711-1718 - range map product		

Sol 3112 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	8-May-2021
camera position	7
total parent images	61
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	71

MAHLI imaged the targets Pezuls and Le_Bugue and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mhl00706	Pezuls ~25 cm standoff	3112MH0070600011017470CD	1747	autofocus sub-frame for target Pezuls - standoff near 25 cm
		3112MH007060011017480CD	1748	target Pezuls - standoff near 25 cm
		3112MH0070600211017490CD	1749	target Pezuls - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mhl00707	Pezuls stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3112MH0074000011017500CD	1750	autofocus sub-frame for target Pezuls - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3112MH0074000111017510CD	1751	target Pezuls - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3112MH0074000211017520CD	1752	target Pezuls - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3112MH0074000311017530CD	1753	target Pezuls - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000411017540CD	1754	target Pezuls - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000511017550CD	1755	target Pezuls - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000611017560CD	1756	target Pezuls - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000711017570CD	1757	target Pezuls - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000811017580CD	1758	target Pezuls - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000911017590CD	1759	target Pezuls - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074001011017600CD	1760	target Pezuls - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00708	Pezuls stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3112MH0074000111017610CD	1761	autofocus sub-frame for target Pezuls - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3112MH0074000211017620CD	1762	target Pezuls - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3112MH0074000311017630CD	1763	target Pezuls - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3112MH0074000411017640CD	1764	target Pezuls - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000511017650CD	1765	target Pezuls - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000611017660CD	1766	target Pezuls - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000711017670CD	1767	target Pezuls - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000811017680CD	1768	target Pezuls - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000911017690CD	1769	target Pezuls - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074001011017700CD	1770	target Pezuls - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH007400111017710CD	1771	target Pezuls - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00800	Pezuls ~2 cm standoff	3112MH0080000011017720CD	1772	autofocus sub-frame for target Pezuls - standoff near 2 cm
		3112MH0080000111017730CD	1773	target Pezuls - standoff near 2 cm
		3112MH0080000211017740CD	1774	target Pezuls - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3112MH0080000311017750CD	1775	target Pezuls - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0080000411017760CD	1776	target Pezuls - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0080000511017770CD	1777	target Pezuls - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0080000611017780CD	1778	target Pezuls - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0080000711017790CD	1779	target Pezuls - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0080000811017800CD	1780	target Pezuls - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0080000911017810CD	1781	target Pezuls - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0080001011017820CD	1782	target Pezuls - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00709	Le_Bugue ~25 cm standoff	3112MH0070600011017830CD	1783	autofocus sub-frame for target Le_Bugue - standoff near 25 cm
		3112MH007060011017840CD	1784	target Le_Bugue - standoff near 25 cm
		3112MH0070600211017850CD	1785	target Le_Bugue - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mhl00710	Le_Bugue stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3112MH0074000011017860CD	1786	autofocus sub-frame for target Le_Bugue - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3112MH0074000111017870CD	1787	target Le_Bugue - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3112MH0074000211017880CD	1788	target Le_Bugue - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3112MH0074000311017890CD	1789	target Le_Bugue - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000411017900CD	1790	target Le_Bugue - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000511017910CD	1791	target Le_Bugue - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000611017920CD	1792	target Le_Bugue - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000711017930CD	1793	target Le_Bugue - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000811017940CD	1794	target Le_Bugue - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000911017950CD	1795	target Le_Bugue - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074001011017960CD	1796	target Le_Bugue - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00711	Le_Bugue stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3112MH0074000111017970CD	1797	autofocus sub-frame for target Le_Bugue - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3112MH0074000211017980CD	1798	target Le_Bugue - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3112MH0074000311017990CD	1799	target Le_Bugue - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3112MH0074000411018000CD	1800	target Le_Bugue - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000511018010CD	1801	target Le_Bugue - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000611018020CD	1802	target Le_Bugue - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000711018030CD	1803	target Le_Bugue - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000811018040CD	1804	target Le_Bugue - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074000911018050CD	1805	target Le_Bugue - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH0074001011018060CD	1806	target Le_Bugue - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3112MH007400111018070CD	1807	target Le_Bugue - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mH00227	Focus Merges	3112MH000227000110180800	1808	target Le_Bugue - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3112 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1800-1807 - best focus image product
		3112MH000227000110180950	1809	target Le_Bugue - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3112 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1800-1807 - range map product
		3112MH000227000110181000	1810	target Le_Bugue - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3112 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1789-1796 - best focus image product
		3112MH000227000110181150	1811	target Le_Bugue - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3112 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1789-1796 - range map product
		3112MH000227000110181200	1812	target Pezulis - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3112 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1775-1782 - best focus image product
		3112MH000227000110181350	1813	target Pezulis - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3112 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1775-1782 - range map product
		3112MH000227000110181400	1814	target Pezulis - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3112 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1764-1771 - best focus image product
		3112MH000227000110181550	1815	target Pezulis - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3112 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1764-1771 - range map product
		3112MH000227000110181600	1816	target Pezulis - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3112 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1753-1760 - best focus image product
		3112MH000227000110181750	1817	target Pezulis - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3112 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1753-1760 - range map product

updated: 17_March_2021

Sol 3117 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	13-May-21
camera positions	4
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	41

MAHLI imaged the target Buserolles and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00706	Buserolles ~25 cm standoff	3117MH000706001101877C0D	1877	autofocus sub-frame for target Buserolles - standoff near 25 cm
		3117MH000706001101878C0D	1878	target Buserolles - standoff near 25 cm
		3117MH000706001101879C0D	1879	target Buserolles - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00723	Buserolles stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3117MH000723001101880C0D	1880	autofocus sub-frame for target Buserolles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3117MH000723001101881C0D	1881	target Buserolles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3117MH000723001101882C0D	1882	target Buserolles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3117MH000723001101883C0D	1883	target Buserolles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000723001101884C0D	1884	target Buserolles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000723001101885C0D	1885	target Buserolles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000723001101886C0D	1886	target Buserolles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000723001101887C0D	1887	target Buserolles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000723001101888C0D	1888	target Buserolles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000723001101889C0D	1889	target Buserolles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000723001101890C0D	1890	target Buserolles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00723	Buserolles stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3117MH000723001101891C0D	1891	autofocus sub-frame for target Buserolles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3117MH000723001101892C0D	1892	target Buserolles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3117MH000723001101893C0D	1893	target Buserolles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3117MH000723001101894C0D	1894	target Buserolles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000723001101895C0D	1895	target Buserolles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000723001101896C0D	1896	target Buserolles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000723001101897C0D	1897	target Buserolles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000723001101898C0D	1898	target Buserolles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000723001101899C0D	1899	target Buserolles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000723001101900C0D	1900	target Buserolles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000723001101901C0D	1901	target Buserolles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00785	Buserolles ~1 cm standoff	3117MH000785001101902C0D	1902	autofocus sub-frame for target Buserolles - standoff near 1 cm
		3117MH000785001101903C0D	1903	target Buserolles - standoff near 1 cm
		3117MH000785001101904C0D	1904	target Buserolles - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3117MH000785001101905C0D	1905	target Buserolles - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000785001101906C0D	1906	target Buserolles - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000785001101907C0D	1907	target Buserolles - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000785001101908C0D	1908	target Buserolles - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000785001101909C0D	1909	target Buserolles - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000785001101910C0D	1910	target Buserolles - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000785001101911C0D	1911	target Buserolles - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3117MH000785001101912C0D	1912	target Buserolles - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00189	Focus Merges	3117MH000193000110191300D	1913	target Buserolles - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3117 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1905-1912 - best focus image product
		3117MH000193000110191450D	1914	target Buserolles - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3117 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1905-1912 - range map product
		3117MH000193000110191590D	1915	target Buserolles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3117 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1894-1901 - best focus image product
		3117MH000193000110191650D	1916	target Buserolles - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3117 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1894-1901 - range map product
		3117MH000193000110191700D	1917	target Buserolles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3117 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1883-1890 - best focus image product
		3117MH000193000110191850D	1918	target Buserolles - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3117 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1883-1890 - range map product

Sol 3119 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	10-May-21	
		camera position	75	Image ID:
		total parent images	5	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	5	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	10	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	10	
summary of MAHLI activities				
MAHLI images of the targets Monsec and Salagnac and the focus stack images were merged. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness. However, a stepper motor "slipping" issue occurred during the night-time imaging, which caused all reported motor counts (which are used to determine range and scale) to be incorrect for the CheMin inlet. In addition, because of this anomaly, the CheMin inlet images are not in sharp focus.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00190	Monsec before DRT ~25 cm standoff	3119MH0001900001101919ZC00	1919	autofocus sub-frame for target Monsec - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3119MH000190001101920ZC00	1920	target Monsec - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mNI00212	Monsec before DRT ~5 cm standoff	3119MH000123001101921ZC00	1921	autofocus sub-frame for target Monsec - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm
		3119MH000123001101922ZC00	1922	target Monsec - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm
mNI00706	Monsec after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3119MH0007060001101923ZC00	1923	autofocus sub-frame for target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3119MH000706001101924ZC00	1924	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3119MH0007060021101925ZC00	1925	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00723	Monsec after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3119MH000723001101926ZC00	1926	autofocus sub-frame for target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3119MH000723001101927ZC00	1927	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3119MH000723001101928ZC00	1928	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3119MH000723001101929ZC00	1929	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101930ZC00	1930	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101931ZC00	1931	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101932ZC00	1932	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101933ZC00	1933	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101934ZC00	1934	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101935ZC00	1935	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101936ZC00	1936	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101937ZC00	1937	autofocus sub-frame for target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3119MH000723001101938ZC00	1938	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3119MH000723001101939ZC00	1939	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00723	Monsec after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3119MH000723001101940ZC00	1940	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101941ZC00	1941	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101942ZC00	1942	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101943ZC00	1943	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101944ZC00	1944	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101945ZC00	1945	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101946ZC00	1946	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101947ZC00	1947	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH0008020001101948ZC00	1948	autofocus sub-frame for target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3119MH000802001101949ZC00	1949	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3119MH0008020021101950ZC00	1950	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3119MH0008020031101951ZC00	1951	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH0008020041101952ZC00	1952	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH0008020051101953ZC00	1953	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3119MH0008020061101954ZC00	1954	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3119MH0008020071101955ZC00	1955	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3119MH0008020081101956ZC00	1956	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3119MH0008020091101957ZC00	1957	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3119MH0008020101101958ZC00	1958	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00706	Salagnac ~25 cm standoff	3119MH0007060001101959ZC00	1959	autofocus sub-frame for target Salagnac - standoff near 25 cm
		3119MH000706001101960ZC00	1960	target Salagnac - standoff near 25 cm
		3119MH0007060021101961ZC00	1961	target Salagnac - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00723	Salagnac stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3119MH000723001101962ZC00	1962	autofocus sub-frame for target Salagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3119MH000723001101963ZC00	1963	target Salagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3119MH000723001101964ZC00	1964	target Salagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3119MH000723001101965ZC00	1965	target Salagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101966ZC00	1966	target Salagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101967ZC00	1967	target Salagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101968ZC00	1968	target Salagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101969ZC00	1969	target Salagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101970ZC00	1970	target Salagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101971ZC00	1971	target Salagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101972ZC00	1972	target Salagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3119MH000723001101973ZC00	1973	autofocus sub-frame for target Salagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3119MH000723001101974ZC00	1974	target Salagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3119MH000723001101975ZC00	1975	target Salagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
3119MH000723001101976ZC00	1976	target Salagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3119MH000723001101977ZC00	1977	target Salagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3119MH000723001101978ZC00	1978	target Salagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3119MH000723001101979ZC00	1979	target Salagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3119MH000723001101980ZC00	1980	target Salagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3119MH000723001101981ZC00	1981	target Salagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3119MH000723001101982ZC00	1982	target Salagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3119MH000723001101983ZC00	1983	target Salagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

mNH00227	Focus Merges	3119MH000227000110196800	1984	target Salagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3119 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1976-1983 - best focus image product
		3119MH000227000110198550	1985	target Salagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3119 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1976-1983 - range map product
		3119MH000227000110198680	1986	target Salagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3119 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1965-1972 - best focus image product
		3119MH000227000110198750	1987	target Salagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3119 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1965-1972 - range map product
		3119MH000227000110198880	1988	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3119 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1951-1958 - best focus image product
		3119MH000227000110198950	1989	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3119 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1951-1958 - range map product
		3119MH000227000110199080	1990	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3119 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1940-1947 - best focus image product
		3119MH000227000110199150	1991	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3119 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1940-1947 - range map product
		3119MH000227000110199280	1992	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3119 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1929-1936 - best focus image product
		3119MH000227000110199350	1993	target Monsec - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3119 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1929-1936 - range map product
mNH00312	MAHL 12.4 cm working distance above Chemin inlet mesh; inlet cover open; position 1 of 3; imaging at right	3119MH000312000110199400	1994	Chemin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance - image not in sharp focus because of a focus mechanism problem
		3119MH000312001110199500	1995	Chemin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at mesh at 124 mm working distance - image not in sharp focus because of a focus mechanism problem
mNH00316	position 2 of 3, otherwise same as above	3119MH000316000110199600	1996	Chemin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance - image not in sharp focus because of a focus mechanism problem
mNH00316	position 3 of 3, otherwise same as two above	3119MH000316000110199700	1997	Chemin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance - image not in sharp focus because of a focus mechanism problem
mNH00328	~17 cm above open Chemin inlet	3119MH00028800110199800	1998	Chemin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at 17 cm working distance - image not in sharp focus because of a focus mechanism problem

MAHLI Sol 3119 ERRATA

Sol	M5L-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (M5L-COM)	Errata
3119	1994	Owing to a stepper motor skipping event, the motor count for this image does not indicate actual lens focus position and cannot be used to estimate image range and scale - in addition, the image is not in sharp focus
3119	1995	Owing to a stepper motor skipping event, the motor count for this image does not indicate actual lens focus position and cannot be used to estimate image range and scale - in addition, the image is not in sharp focus
3119	1996	Owing to a stepper motor skipping event, the motor count for this image does not indicate actual lens focus position and cannot be used to estimate image range and scale - in addition, the image is not in sharp focus
3119	1997	Owing to a stepper motor skipping event, the motor count for this image does not indicate actual lens focus position and cannot be used to estimate image range and scale - in addition, the image is not in sharp focus
3119	1998	Owing to a stepper motor skipping event, the motor count for this image does not indicate actual lens focus position and cannot be used to estimate image range and scale - in addition, the image is not in sharp focus

updated: 20_May_2021

Sol 3122 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)		18-May-21		
camera position:		0	Image ID:	
total parent images:		0	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received	
focus merges performed:		2	CDPID:	
total focus merge products:		4	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	
total parent images + focus merge products:		4		
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI mechanism fault: With the MAHLI camera head at ~25 cm above the surface, a mechanism fault occurred on Sol 3122 while the MAHLI dust cover was opening. None of the planned imaging occurred on Sol 3122. Since no new data were collected, the Salagnac focus stack images from Sol 3119 were merged a second time.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	
			Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)	
mN002ES	Focus Merges	3122MH0002650001101999R00	1999	target Salagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3119 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1976-1983 - best focus image product
		3122MH0002650001102000S00	2000	target Salagnac - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3119 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1976-1983 - range map product
		3122MH0002650001102001R00	2001	target Salagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3119 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1965-1972 - best focus image product
		3122MH0002650001102002S00	2002	target Salagnac - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3119 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1965-1972 - range map product

updated: 21_May_2021

Sol 3124 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)		21_May_21	
camera position:	1	image ID:	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
total parent images:	1	CDPID:	
focus merges performed:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	
total focus merge products:	0		
total parent images + focus merge products:	1		
summary of MAHLI activities	<p>MAHLI Fault Response Process: MAHLI diagnostic test imaging as part of the process to recover from MAHLI mechanism fault that occurred on Sol 3122 leaving MAHLI ~25 cm above the Martian surface with the cover open. The MAHLI dust cover did not completely open on Sol 3122, causing a fault that impacted plans for arm motion, driving, and other science observing. The 2-sol plan for Sol 3122-3123 included: (1) leaving the MAHLI dust cover open through the two sols, as it was in an uncertain mechanical state, and, on Sol 3124; (2) move the robotic arm so as to present the MAHLI dust cover and hinge areas to the Mastcams for inspection; (3) robotic arm movement of MAHLI to the shoulder-out cover staging pose ~ 1.25 m above the Martian surface, with MAHLI pointed down, to help protect the front lens element (sapphire window) from dust settling from suspension and from the impact of potential saltating sand grains from below; and (4) with no MAHLI mechanism movement, acquire a MAHLI image at shoulder-out cover staging pose ~ 1.25 m above the Martian surface. The MAHLI image was intended to provide more data about lens focus position relative to the position of the mostly open dust cover. The reported motor count for the Sol 3124 image may not indicate actual focus position.</p>		
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID
mNID0858	Diagnostic Imaging No Cover Focus Mechanism Movement ~1.25 m standoff	3124M00088800110203E01	2003
<p>Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)</p> <p>MAHLI diagnostic imaging following sol 3122 mechanism fault in which dust cover did not completely open - no focus mechanism motion since sol 3122 fault - camera pointed down - standoff distance to surface is near 125 cm - intent to understand camera focus at time of fault occurrence</p>			

updated: 08_June_2021

Sol 3139 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	5-Jun-21
camera positions:	0
total parent images:	39
focus merges performed:	0
total focus merge products:	0
total parent images + focus merge products:	39
Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels:	

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

Following a series of efforts to recover MAHLI from the fault that occurred on Sol 3122 and a stand-down period to consider the path forward, the team concluded that the symptoms observed in recent months, dating back to a motor count "slipping" event on Sol 3088, appear to result from camera head thermal conditions (i.e., lubricant temperature likely too cool) after (and during) cold rights. The team decided to resume science/engineering operation of the instrument but with a temporary restriction to operate in the warmest part of the afternoon between local times of 14:00 to 17:00. For Sol 3139, MAHLI was thus employed to image geological targets named Beauvernie and Cladech. These imaging operations were successful and concluded without incident.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mhl00706	Beauvernie ~25 cm standoff	3139MH00706001102004C00	2004	autofocus sub-frame for target Beauvernie - standoff near 25 cm
		3139MH00706001102005C00	2005	target Beauvernie - standoff near 25 cm
		3139MH00706001102006C00	2006	target Beauvernie - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mhl007063	Beauvernie ~5 cm standoff	3139MH007063001102007C00	2007	autofocus sub-frame for target Beauvernie - standoff near 5 cm
		3139MH007063001102008C00	2008	target Beauvernie - standoff near 5 cm
		3139MH007063001102009C00	2009	target Beauvernie - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3139MH007063001102010C00	2010	target Beauvernie - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH007063001102011C00	2011	target Beauvernie - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH007063001102012C00	2012	target Beauvernie - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH007063001102013C00	2013	target Beauvernie - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH007063001102014C00	2014	target Beauvernie - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH007063001102015C00	2015	target Beauvernie - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH007063001102016C00	2016	target Beauvernie - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH007063001102017C00	2017	target Beauvernie - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00706	Cladech ~25 cm standoff	3139MH00706001102018C00	2018	autofocus sub-frame for target Cladech - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3139MH00706001102019C00	2019	target Cladech - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3139MH00706001102020C00	2020	target Cladech - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mhl00709	Cladech APXS spot 2 ~4 cm standoff	3139MH00709001102021C00	2021	autofocus sub-frame for target Cladech - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3139MH00709001102022C00	2022	target Cladech - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3139MH00709001102023C00	2023	target Cladech - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3139MH00709001102024C00	2024	target Cladech - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH00709001102025C00	2025	target Cladech - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH00709001102026C00	2026	target Cladech - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH00709001102027C00	2027	target Cladech - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH00709001102028C00	2028	target Cladech - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH00709001102029C00	2029	target Cladech - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH00709001102030C00	2030	target Cladech - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH00709001102031C00	2031	target Cladech - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00709	Cladech APXS spot 1 ~4 cm standoff	3139MH00709001102032C00	2032	autofocus sub-frame for target Cladech - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3139MH00709001102033C00	2033	target Cladech - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3139MH00709001102034C00	2034	target Cladech - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3139MH00709001102035C00	2035	target Cladech - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH00709001102036C00	2036	target Cladech - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH00709001102037C00	2037	target Cladech - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH00709001102038C00	2038	target Cladech - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH00709001102039C00	2039	target Cladech - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH00709001102040C00	2040	target Cladech - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH00709001102041C00	2041	target Cladech - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139MH00709001102042C00	2042	target Cladech - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 07_june_2021

Sol 3140 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	6 Jun 21
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	3
total focus merge products:	3
total parent images + focus merge products:	3

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3139 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00289	Focus Merges	3140MH001930001102043R00	2043	target Cladech - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3139 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2035-2042 - best focus image product
		3140MH001930001102044S00	2044	target Cladech - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3139 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2035-2042 - range map product
		3140MH001930001102045R00	2045	target Cladech - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3139 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2024-2031 - best focus image product
		3140MH001930001102046S00	2046	target Cladech - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3139 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2024-2031 - range map product
		3140MH001930001102047R00	2047	target Beauronne - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3139 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2010-2017 - best focus image product
		3140MH001930001102048S00	2048	target Beauronne - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3139 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2010-2017 - range map product

updated: 17_June_2021

Sol 3142- MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	8-Jun-21
camera position:	6
total parent images:	47
focus merges performed:	0
total focus merge products:	0
total parent images + focus merge products:	47

MAHLI imaged the targets Minzac and Terrasson_Lavilledieu.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mNI00706	Minzac ~25 cm standoff	3142MH000706001102049C00	2049	autofocus sub-frame for target Minzac - standoff near 25 cm		
		3142MH000706001102050C00	2050	target Minzac - standoff near 25 cm		
		3142MH000706001102051C00	2051	target Minzac - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00699	Minzac stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3142MH000699001102052C00	2052	autofocus sub-frame for target Minzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3142MH000699001102053C00	2053	target Minzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3142MH000699001102054C00	2054	target Minzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3142MH000699001102055C00	2055	target Minzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3142MH000699001102056C00	2056	target Minzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3142MH000699001102057C00	2057	target Minzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3142MH000699001102058C00	2058	target Minzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3142MH000699001102059C00	2059	target Minzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3142MH000699001102060C00	2060	target Minzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3142MH000699001102061C00	2061	target Minzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3142MH000699001102062C00	2062	target Minzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00699	Minzac stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3142MH000699001102063C00	2063	autofocus sub-frame for target Minzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3142MH000699001102064C00	2064	target Minzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3142MH000699001102065C00	2065	target Minzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
3142MH000699001102066C00	2066			target Minzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3142MH000699001102067C00	2067			target Minzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3142MH000699001102068C00	2068			target Minzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3142MH000699001102069C00	2069			target Minzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3142MH000699001102070C00	2070			target Minzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3142MH000699001102071C00	2071			target Minzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3142MH000699001102072C00	2072			target Minzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3142MH000699001102073C00	2073			target Minzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00190	Terrasson_Lavilledieu ~25 cm standoff			3142MH000190001102074C00	2074	autofocus sub-frame for target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - standoff near 25 cm
mNI00297	Terrasson_Lavilledieu stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff			3142MH000190001102075C00	2075	target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - standoff near 25 cm
				3142MH000297001102076C00	2076	autofocus sub-frame for target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3142MH000297001102077C00	2077	target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm		
		3142MH000297001102078C00	2078	target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3142MH000297001102079C00	2079	target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3142MH000297001102080C00	2080	target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3142MH000297001102081C00	2081	target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3142MH000297001102082C00	2082	target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3142MH000297001102083C00	2083	target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3142MH000297001102084C00	2084	target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3142MH000297001102085C00	2085	target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00297	Terrasson_Lavilledieu stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3142MH000297001102086C00	2086	autofocus sub-frame for target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
				3142MH000297001102087C00	2087	target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
				3142MH000297001102088C00	2088	target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3142MH000297001102089C00	2089			target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3142MH000297001102090C00	2090			target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3142MH000297001102091C00	2091			target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3142MH000297001102092C00	2092			target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3142MH000297001102093C00	2093			target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3142MH000297001102094C00	2094			target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3142MH000297001102095C00	2095			target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 11_june_2021

Sol 3143 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	9 Jun 21
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	4
total focus merge products:	8
total parent images + focus merge products:	8

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received

CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3142 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N0013	Focus Merges	3143MH001530001102096R00	2096	target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3142 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2088-2095 - best focus image product
		3143MH001530001102097S00	2097	target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3142 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2088-2095 - range map product
		3143MH001530001102098R00	2098	target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3142 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2078-2085 - best focus image product
		3143MH001530001102099S00	2099	target Terrasson_Lavilledieu - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3142 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2078-2085 - range map product
		3143MH001530001102100R00	2100	target Minzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3142 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2066-2073 - best focus image product
		3143MH001530001102101S00	2101	target Minzac - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3142 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2066-2073 - range map product
		3143MH001530001102102R00	2102	target Minzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3142 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2055-2062 - best focus image product
		3143MH001530001102103S00	2103	target Minzac - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3142 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2055-2062 - range map product

updated: 22_June_2021

Sol 3144 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	10-Jun-21
camera position	6
total parent images	63
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	63

MAHLI imaged the REMS UV Sensor and the targets Plaisance and Sarlande.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mNI0095	REMS UV sensor ~25 cm standoff	3144MH000950011021040CD	2104	autofocus sub-frame for REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation		
		3144MH000950011021050CD	2105	REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation		
mNI00706	Plaisance after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3144MH0007060011021060CD	2106	autofocus sub-frame for target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm		
		3144MH0007060011021070CD	2107	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm		
		3144MH0007060011021080CD	2108	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00699	Plaisance after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3144MH0006990011021090CD	2109	autofocus sub-frame for target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3144MH0006990011021100CD	2110	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3144MH0006990011021110CD	2111	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3144MH0006990011021120CD	2112	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0006990011021130CD	2113	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0006990011021140CD	2114	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0006990011021150CD	2115	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0006990011021160CD	2116	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0006990011021170CD	2117	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0006990011021180CD	2118	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0006990011021190CD	2119	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00699	Plaisance after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3144MH0006990011021200CD	2120	autofocus sub-frame for target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3144MH0006990011021210CD	2121	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3144MH0006990011021220CD	2122	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
3144MH0006990011021230CD	2123			target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3144MH0006990011021240CD	2124			target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3144MH0006990011021250CD	2125			target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3144MH0006990011021260CD	2126			target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3144MH0006990011021270CD	2127			target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3144MH0006990011021280CD	2128			target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3144MH0006990011021290CD	2129			target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3144MH0006990011021300CD	2130			target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00824	Plaisance after DRT ~2 cm standoff			3144MH0008240011021310CD	2131	autofocus sub-frame for target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
				3144MH0008240011021320CD	2132	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
				3144MH0008240011021330CD	2133	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3144MH0008240011021340CD	2134	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0008240011021350CD	2135	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0008240011021360CD	2136	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0008240011021370CD	2137	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0008240011021380CD	2138	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0008240011021390CD	2139	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0008240011021400CD	2140	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0008240011021410CD	2141	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00706	Sarlande ~25 cm standoff	3144MH0007060011021420CD	2142	autofocus sub-frame for target Sarlande - standoff near 25 cm
				3144MH0007060011021430CD	2143	target Sarlande - standoff near 25 cm
				3144MH0007060011021440CD	2144	target Sarlande - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00708	Sarlande stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3144MH0007080011021450CD	2145	autofocus sub-frame for target Sarlande - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3144MH0007080011021460CD	2146	target Sarlande - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3144MH0007080011021470CD	2147	target Sarlande - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3144MH0007080011021480CD	2148	target Sarlande - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0007080011021490CD	2149	target Sarlande - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0007080011021500CD	2150	target Sarlande - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0007080011021510CD	2151	target Sarlande - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0007080011021520CD	2152	target Sarlande - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0007080011021530CD	2153	target Sarlande - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0007080011021540CD	2154	target Sarlande - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3144MH0007080011021550CD	2155	target Sarlande - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00708	Sarlande stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3144MH0007080011021560CD	2156	autofocus sub-frame for target Sarlande - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				3144MH0007080011021570CD	2157	target Sarlande - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				3144MH0007080011021580CD	2158	target Sarlande - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
3144MH0007080011021590CD	2159			target Sarlande - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3144MH0007080011021600CD	2160			target Sarlande - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3144MH0007080011021610CD	2161			target Sarlande - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3144MH0007080011021620CD	2162			target Sarlande - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3144MH0007080011021630CD	2163			target Sarlande - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3144MH0007080011021640CD	2164			target Sarlande - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3144MH0007080011021650CD	2165			target Sarlande - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3144MH0007080011021660CD	2166	target Sarlande - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack				

updated: 11_june_2021

Sol 3145 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	15_jun_21
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3144 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3145MH0002270001102167900	2167	target Sarlande - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3144 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2159-2166 - best focus image product
		3145MH0002270001102168500	2168	target Sarlande - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3144 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2159-2166 - range map product
		3145MH0002270001102169900	2169	target Sarlande - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3144 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2148-2155 - best focus image product
		3145MH0002270001102170500	2170	target Sarlande - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3144 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2148-2155 - range map product
		3145MH0002270001102171900	2171	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3144 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2134-2141 - best focus image product
		3145MH0002270001102172500	2172	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3144 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2134-2141 - range map product
		3145MH0002270001102173900	2173	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3144 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2123-2130 - best focus image product
		3145MH0002270001102174500	2174	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3144 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2123-2130 - range map product
		3145MH0002270001102175900	2175	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3144 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2112-2119 - best focus image product
		3145MH0002270001102176500	2176	target Plaisance - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3144 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2112-2119 - range map product

updated: 30_June_2021

Sol 3146 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	23_Jan_21
camera position:	6
total parent images:	50
focus merges performed:	0
total focus merge products:	0
total parent images + focus merge products:	50

MAHLI imaged the targets Monpaszier and Habirat.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN100706	Monpaszier ~23 cm standoff	3146MH000706000110217700D	2177	autofocus sub-frame for target Monpaszier - standoff near 23 cm
		3146MH00070600110217800D	2178	target Monpaszier - standoff near 23 cm
		3146MH000706002110217900D	2179	target Monpaszier - standoff near 23 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN100699	Monpaszier stereo-1 ~3 cm standoff	3146MH000699000110218000D	2180	autofocus sub-frame for target Monpaszier - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm
		3146MH000699001102181000D	2181	target Monpaszier - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm
		3146MH000699002110218200D	2182	target Monpaszier - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3146MH000699003110218300D	2183	target Monpaszier - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000699004110218400D	2184	target Monpaszier - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000699005110218500D	2185	target Monpaszier - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000699006110218600D	2186	target Monpaszier - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000699007110218700D	2187	target Monpaszier - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000699008110218800D	2188	target Monpaszier - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000699009110218900D	2189	target Monpaszier - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000699010110219000D	2190	target Monpaszier - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100699	Monpaszier stereo-2 ~3 cm standoff	3146MH000699000110219100D	2191	autofocus sub-frame for target Monpaszier - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		3146MH00069900110219200D	2192	target Monpaszier - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		3146MH000699002110219300D	2193	target Monpaszier - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3146MH000699003110219400D	2194	target Monpaszier - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000699004110219500D	2195	target Monpaszier - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000699005110219600D	2196	target Monpaszier - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000699006110219700D	2197	target Monpaszier - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000699007110219800D	2198	target Monpaszier - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000699008110219900D	2199	target Monpaszier - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000699009110220000D	2200	target Monpaszier - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000699010110220100D	2201	target Monpaszier - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100706	Habirat ~25 cm standoff	3146MH000706000110220200D	2202	autofocus sub-frame for target Habirat - standoff near 25 cm
		3146MH00070600110220300D	2203	target Habirat - standoff near 25 cm
		3146MH000706002110220400D	2204	target Habirat - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN100740	Habirat stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3146MH000740000110220500D	2205	autofocus sub-frame for target Habirat - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3146MH00074000110220600D	2206	target Habirat - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3146MH000740002110220700D	2207	target Habirat - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3146MH000740003110220800D	2208	target Habirat - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000740004110220900D	2209	target Habirat - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000740005110221000D	2210	target Habirat - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000740006110221100D	2211	target Habirat - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000740007110221200D	2212	target Habirat - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000740008110221300D	2213	target Habirat - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000740009110221400D	2214	target Habirat - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000740010110221500D	2215	target Habirat - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100740	Habirat stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3146MH000740000110221600D	2216	autofocus sub-frame for target Habirat - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3146MH00074000110221700D	2217	target Habirat - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3146MH000740002110221800D	2218	target Habirat - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3146MH000740003110221900D	2219	target Habirat - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000740004110222000D	2220	target Habirat - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000740005110222100D	2221	target Habirat - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000740006110222200D	2222	target Habirat - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000740007110222300D	2223	target Habirat - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000740008110222400D	2224	target Habirat - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000740009110222500D	2225	target Habirat - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146MH000740010110222600D	2226	target Habirat - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 17_june_2021

Sol 3147 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	19_jun_21
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	4
total focus merge products:	8
total parent images + focus merge products:	8

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	
Focus stack images from Sol 3146 were merged.				
Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)				
m1N0013	Focus Merges	3147MH00153000110227900	2227	target Nabirat - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3146 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2219-2226 - best focus image product
		3147MH00153000110228500	2228	target Nabirat - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3146 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2219-2226 - range map product
		3147MH00153000110229900	2229	target Nabirat - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3146 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2208-2215 - best focus image product
		3147MH001530001102230500	2230	target Nabirat - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3146 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2208-2215 - range map product
		3147MH00153000110223100	2231	target Monpezier - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3146 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2194-2201 - best focus image product
		3147MH001530001102232500	2232	target Monpezier - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3146 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2194-2201 - range map product
		3147MH00153000110223900	2233	target Monpezier - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3146 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2183-2190 - best focus image product
		3147MH001530001102234500	2234	target Monpezier - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3146 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2183-2190 - range map product

updated: 07_July_2021

Sol 3160 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27-Jun-21
camera position	6
total parent images	50
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	50

Image ID: black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities		MAHLI imaged the targets Simeyrols and Rouffignac.		Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	
mN00706	Simeyrols ~25 cm standoff	3160MH007060001102235000	2235	autofocus sub-frame for target Simeyrols - standoff near 25 cm
		3160MH00706001102236000	2236	target Simeyrols - standoff near 25 cm
		3160MH007060021102237000	2237	target Simeyrols - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00723	Simeyrols stereo-1 ~6 cm standoff	3160MH007230001102238000	2238	autofocus sub-frame for target Simeyrols - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm
		3160MH007230011102239000	2239	target Simeyrols - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm
		3160MH007230021102240000	2240	target Simeyrols - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3160MH007230031102241000	2241	target Simeyrols - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3160MH007230041102242000	2242	target Simeyrols - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3160MH007230051102243000	2243	target Simeyrols - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3160MH007230061102244000	2244	target Simeyrols - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3160MH007230071102245000	2245	target Simeyrols - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3160MH007230081102246000	2246	target Simeyrols - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3160MH007230091102247000	2247	target Simeyrols - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3160MH007230101102248000	2248	target Simeyrols - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00723	Simeyrols stereo-2 ~6 cm standoff	3160MH00723001102249000
3160MH007230021102250000	2250			target Simeyrols - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm
3160MH007230031102251000	2251			target Simeyrols - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - alternative auto-exposure
3160MH007230041102252000	2252			target Simeyrols - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3160MH007230051102253000	2253			target Simeyrols - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
3160MH007230061102254000	2254			target Simeyrols - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3160MH007230071102255000	2255			target Simeyrols - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
3160MH007230081102256000	2256			target Simeyrols - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
3160MH007230091102257000	2257			target Simeyrols - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
3160MH007230101102258000	2258			target Simeyrols - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3160MH00723011102259000	2259			target Simeyrols - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00706	Rouffignac ~25 cm standoff			3160MH00706001102260000
		3160MH007060021102261000	2261	target Rouffignac - standoff near 25 cm
		3160MH007060031102262000	2262	target Rouffignac - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00709	Rouffignac stereo-1 ~55 mm standoff	3160MH007090001102263000	2263	autofocus sub-frame for target Rouffignac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		3160MH007090011102264000	2264	target Rouffignac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		3160MH007090021102265000	2265	target Rouffignac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3160MH007090031102266000	2266	target Rouffignac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3160MH007090041102267000	2267	target Rouffignac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3160MH007090051102268000	2268	target Rouffignac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3160MH007090061102269000	2269	target Rouffignac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3160MH007090071102270000	2270	target Rouffignac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3160MH007090081102271000	2271	target Rouffignac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3160MH007090091102272000	2272	target Rouffignac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3160MH007090101102273000	2273	target Rouffignac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00709	Rouffignac stereo-2 ~55 mm standoff	3160MH00709001102274000
3160MH007090021102275000	2275			target Rouffignac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
3160MH007090031102276000	2276			target Rouffignac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - alternative auto-exposure
3160MH007090041102277000	2277			target Rouffignac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3160MH007090051102278000	2278			target Rouffignac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
3160MH007090061102279000	2279			target Rouffignac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3160MH007090071102280000	2280			target Rouffignac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
3160MH007090081102281000	2281			target Rouffignac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
3160MH007090091102282000	2282			target Rouffignac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
3160MH007090101102283000	2283			target Rouffignac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3160MH00709011102284000	2284			target Rouffignac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 30_June_2021

Sol 3161 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	28 Jun 21
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	8

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3160 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N0013	Focus Merges	3161MH00153000110228900	2285	target Rouffignac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3160 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2277-2284 - best focus image product
		3161MH00153000110228650	2286	target Rouffignac - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3160 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2277-2284 - range map product
		3161MH00153000110228700	2287	target Rouffignac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3160 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2266-2273 - best focus image product
		3161MH00153000110228850	2288	target Rouffignac - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3160 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2266-2273 - range map product
		3161MH00153000110228900	2289	target Simeyois - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3160 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2252-2259 - best focus image product
		3161MH00153000110229050	2290	target Simeyois - stereo-2 - standoff near 6 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3160 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2252-2259 - range map product
		3161MH00153000110229100	2291	target Simeyois - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3160 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2241-2248 - best focus image product
		3161MH00153000110229250	2292	target Simeyois - stereo-1 - standoff near 6 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3160 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2241-2248 - range map product

Sol 3167 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	6 Jul 21	
		camera positions	8	
		total parent images	53	
		focus merges performed	4	
		total focus merge products	8	
		total parent images + focus merge products	61	
summary of MAHLI activities				
MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Pontours before and after DRT and a drill bit preload test; then the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00190	Pontours before DRT ~25 cm standoff	3167MH000190000110229300	2293	autofocus sub-frame for intended Pontours drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3167MH000190000110229400	2294	intended Pontours drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mNI00122	Pontours before DRT APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	3167MH000122000110229500	2295	autofocus sub-frame for intended Pontours drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3167MH000122000110229600	2296	intended Pontours drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
mNI00706	Pontours after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3167MH000706000110229700	2297	autofocus sub-frame for intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3167MH000706000110229800	2298	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3167MH000706000110229900	2299	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00699	Pontours after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3167MH000699000110230000	2300	autofocus sub-frame for intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3167MH000699000110230100	2301	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3167MH000699000110230200	2302	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3167MH000699000110230300	2303	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000699000110230400	2304	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000699000110230500	2305	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000699000110230600	2306	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000699000110230700	2307	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000699000110230800	2308	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000699000110230900	2309	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000699000110231000	2310	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000699000110231100	2311	autofocus sub-frame for intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3167MH000699000110231200	2312	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3167MH000699000110231300	2313	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00699	Pontours after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3167MH000699000110231400	2314	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000699000110231500	2315	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000699000110231600	2316	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000699000110231700	2317	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000699000110231800	2318	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000699000110231900	2319	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000699000110232000	2320	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000699000110232100	2321	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00785	Pontours after DRT APXS spot 2 ~1 cm standoff	3167MH000785000110232200	2322	autofocus sub-frame for intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3167MH000785000110232300	2323	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3167MH000785000110232400	2324	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3167MH000785000110232500	2325	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000785000110232600	2326	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000785000110232700	2327	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000785000110232800	2328	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000785000110232900	2329	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000785000110233000	2330	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000785000110233100	2331	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000785000110233200	2332	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mNI00699	Pontours after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3167MH000699000110233300
3167MH000699000110233400	2334			intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
3167MH000699000110233500	2335			intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
3167MH000699000110233600	2336			intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3167MH000699000110233700	2337			intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
3167MH000699000110233800	2338			intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3167MH000699000110233900	2339			intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
3167MH000699000110234000	2340			intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
3167MH000699000110234100	2341			intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
3167MH000699000110234200	2342			intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00465	Pontours after DRT after drill bit preload test ~35 cm standoff	3167MH000465000110234300	2343	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3167MH000465000110234400	2344	autofocus sub-frame for intended Pontours drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 3167 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
mNI00153	Focus Merges	3167MH000153000110234500	2345	intended Pontours drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 3167 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
		3167MH000153000110234600	2346	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3167 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2336-2343 - best focus image product
		3167MH000153000110234700	2347	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3167 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2336-2343 - range map product
		3167MH000153000110234800	2348	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3167 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2325-2332 - best focus image product
		3167MH000153000110234900	2349	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3167 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2325-2332 - range map product
		3167MH000153000110235000	2350	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3167 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2314-2321 - best focus image product
		3167MH000153000110235100	2351	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3167 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2314-2321 - range map product
		3167MH000153000110235200	2352	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3167 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2303-2310 - best focus image product
3167MH000153000110235300	2353	intended Pontours drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3167 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2303-2310 - range map product		

updated: 16_july_2021

Sol 3178 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	ES 00 21
camera positions:	0
total parent images:	19
focus merges performed:	0
total focus merge products:	0
total parent images + focus merge products:	19

MAHLI imaged the Pontours sample discard pile, the Pontours SAM inlet and the surfaces surrounding SAM inlet #2, with the inlet cover open, a follow-up to Pontours sample drop-offs. Then, MAHLI imaged the target Chanterac.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00187	Pontours sample discard pile ~25 cm standoff	3178MH00197001102360C00	2360	autofocus sub-frame for Pontours sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
		3178MH00197001102361C00	2361	Pontours sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00122	Pontours sample discard pile APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3178MH00122001102362C00	2362	autofocus sub-frame for Pontours sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3178MH00122001102363C00	2363	Pontours sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00122	Pontours sample discard pile APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	3178MH00122001102364C00	2364	autofocus sub-frame for Pontours sample discard pile - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3178MH00122001102365C00	2365	Pontours sample discard pile - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00779	SAM inlet 2 ~20 cm standoff	3178MH00779001102366C00	2366	SAM inlet 2 cover open after sample drop-off - inspect surface surrounding inlet perimeter - manual focus assuming 231 mm working distance
		3178MH00779001102367C00	2367	autofocus sub-frame for SAM inlet 2 cover open after sample drop-off - inspect surface surrounding inlet perimeter - standoff near 20 cm
		3178MH00779001102368C00	2368	SAM inlet 2 cover open after sample drop-off - inspect surface surrounding inlet perimeter - standoff near 20 cm
mN00197	Pontours drill hole drilled on Sol 3170 ~25 cm standoff	3178MH00197001102369C00	2369	autofocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Pontours - drilled sol 3170 - standoff near 25 cm
		3178MH00197001102370C00	2370	drill hole in rock named Pontours - drilled sol 3170 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00774	Pontours drill hole drilled on Sol 3170 ~10 cm standoff	3178MH00774001102371C00	2371	autofocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Pontours - drilled sol 3170 - sub-frame positioned to focus on surface outside hole - standoff near 10 cm
		3178MH00774001102372C00	2372	drill hole in rock named Pontours - drilled sol 3170 - focus based on preceding autofocus sub-frame - standoff near 10 cm
mN00172	Chanterac stereo-1 ~20 cm standoff	3178MH00172001102373C00	2373	autofocus sub-frame for target Chanterac - stereo-1 - standoff near 20 cm
		3178MH00172001102374C00	2374	target Chanterac - stereo-1 - standoff near 20 cm
mN00172	Chanterac stereo-2 ~20 cm standoff	3178MH00172001102375C00	2375	autofocus sub-frame for target Chanterac - stereo-2 - standoff near 20 cm
		3178MH00172001102376C00	2376	target Chanterac - stereo-2 - standoff near 20 cm
mN00122	Chanterac ~5 cm standoff	3178MH00122001102377C00	2377	autofocus sub-frame for target Chanterac - standoff near 5 cm
		3178MH00122001102378C00	2378	target Chanterac - standoff near 5 cm

updated: 19_July_2021

Sol 3180 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27 Jul 21
camera positions	7
total parent images	54
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	64

MAHLI imaged the Pontours Sample Discard Pile and the target Chanterac. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00212	Pontours sample discard pile APXS spot 1 ~5 mm standoff	3180MH000122001102379000	2379	autofocus sub-frame for Pontours sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm
		3180MH000122001102380000	2380	Pontours sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm
mN00212	Pontours sample discard pile APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	3180MH000122001102381000	2381	autofocus sub-frame for Pontours sample discard pile - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3180MH000122001102382000	2382	Pontours sample discard pile - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00259	Chanterac APXS spot 5 ~5 cm standoff	3180MH000297001102383000	2383	autofocus sub-frame for target Chanterac - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm
		3180MH000297001102384000	2384	target Chanterac - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm
		3180MH000297001102385000	2385	target Chanterac - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102386000	2386	target Chanterac - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102387000	2387	target Chanterac - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102388000	2388	target Chanterac - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102389000	2389	target Chanterac - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102390000	2390	target Chanterac - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102391000	2391	target Chanterac - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102392000	2392	target Chanterac - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00259	Chanterac APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3180MH000297001102393000	2393	autofocus sub-frame for target Chanterac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3180MH000297001102394000	2394	target Chanterac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3180MH000297001102395000	2395	target Chanterac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102396000	2396	target Chanterac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102397000	2397	target Chanterac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102398000	2398	target Chanterac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102399000	2399	target Chanterac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102400000	2400	target Chanterac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102401000	2401	target Chanterac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102402000	2402	target Chanterac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00259	Chanterac APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	3180MH000297001102403000	2403	autofocus sub-frame for target Chanterac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3180MH000297001102404000	2404	target Chanterac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3180MH000297001102405000	2405	target Chanterac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102406000	2406	target Chanterac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102407000	2407	target Chanterac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102408000	2408	target Chanterac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102409000	2409	target Chanterac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102410000	2410	target Chanterac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102411000	2411	target Chanterac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102412000	2412	target Chanterac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00259	Chanterac APXS spot 3 ~5 cm standoff	3180MH000297001102413000	2413	autofocus sub-frame for target Chanterac - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm
		3180MH000297001102414000	2414	target Chanterac - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm
		3180MH000297001102415000	2415	target Chanterac - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102416000	2416	target Chanterac - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102417000	2417	target Chanterac - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102418000	2418	target Chanterac - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102419000	2419	target Chanterac - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102420000	2420	target Chanterac - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102421000	2421	target Chanterac - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102422000	2422	target Chanterac - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00259	Chanterac APXS spot 4 ~5 cm standoff	3180MH000297001102423000	2423	autofocus sub-frame for target Chanterac - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm
		3180MH000297001102424000	2424	target Chanterac - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm
		3180MH000297001102425000	2425	target Chanterac - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102426000	2426	target Chanterac - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102427000	2427	target Chanterac - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102428000	2428	target Chanterac - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102429000	2429	target Chanterac - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102430000	2430	target Chanterac - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102431000	2431	target Chanterac - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3180MH000297001102432000	2432	target Chanterac - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00227	Focus Merges	3180MH000227000102433000	2433	target Chanterac - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3180 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2425-2432 - best focus image product
		3180MH000227000102434000	2434	target Chanterac - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3180 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2425-2432 - range map product
		3180MH000227000102435000	2435	target Chanterac - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3180 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2415-2422 - best focus image product
		3180MH000227000102436000	2436	target Chanterac - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3180 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2415-2422 - range map product
		3180MH000227000102437000	2437	target Chanterac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3180 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2405-2412 - best focus image product
		3180MH000227000102438000	2438	target Chanterac - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3180 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2405-2412 - range map product
		3180MH000227000102439000	2439	target Chanterac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3180 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2395-2402 - best focus image product
		3180MH000227000102440000	2440	target Chanterac - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3180 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2395-2402 - range map product
		3180MH000227000102441000	2441	target Chanterac - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3180 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2385-2392 - best focus image product
		3180MH000227000102442000	2442	target Chanterac - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3180 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2385-2392 - range map product

updated: 19_july_2021

Sol 3181 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	28 Jul 21	Image ID:		
camera positions:	0	Image ID:		
total parent images:	2	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
focus merges performed:	0	CDPID:		
total focus merge products:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
total parent images + focus merge products:	2			
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the Pontours Drill Cuttings.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00122	Pontours drill cuttings ~45 mm standoff	3181MH00122001102443C00	2443	autofocus sub-frame for Pontours drill cuttings - standoff near 45 mm
		3181MH00122001102444C00	2444	Pontours drill cuttings - standoff near 45 mm

updated: 03_August_2021

Sol 3183 - MAHLI Images

summary of MAHLI activities		The new heating strategy went into effect for the Sol 3183 plan which allowed MAHLI imaging to be acquired at any time of day. On Sol 3183, MAHLI imaged the target Montagenet and the focus stack images were merged.		
acquired/performed date(s)		20 Jul 21		
camera positions		4		
total parent images		33		
focus merges performed		3		
total focus merge products		6		
total parent images + focus merge products		39		
Image ID		Image ID		
CPDPD		CPDPD		
Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Montagenet ~25 cm standoff	3183MH00190001102445C0D	2445	autofocus sub-frame for target Montagenet - standoff near 25 cm
		3183MH00190001102446C0D	2446	target Montagenet - standoff near 25 cm
mN00299	Montagenet stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3183MH00299001102447C0D	2447	autofocus sub-frame for target Montagenet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3183MH00299001102448C0D	2448	target Montagenet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3183MH00299001102449C0D	2449	target Montagenet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00299001102450C0D	2450	target Montagenet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00299001102451C0D	2451	target Montagenet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00299001102452C0D	2452	target Montagenet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00299001102453C0D	2453	target Montagenet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00299001102454C0D	2454	target Montagenet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00299001102455C0D	2455	target Montagenet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00299001102456C0D	2456	target Montagenet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00299	Montagenet stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3183MH00299001102457C0D	2457	autofocus sub-frame for target Montagenet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3183MH00299001102458C0D	2458	target Montagenet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3183MH00299001102459C0D	2459	target Montagenet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00299001102460C0D	2460	target Montagenet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00299001102461C0D	2461	target Montagenet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00299001102462C0D	2462	target Montagenet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00299001102463C0D	2463	target Montagenet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00299001102464C0D	2464	target Montagenet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00299001102465C0D	2465	target Montagenet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00299001102466C0D	2466	target Montagenet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00649	Montagenet ~1 cm standoff	3183MH00649001102467C0D	2467	autofocus sub-frame for target Montagenet - standoff near 1 cm
		3183MH00649001102468C0D	2468	target Montagenet - standoff near 1 cm
		3183MH00649001102469C0D	2469	target Montagenet - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00649001102470C0D	2470	target Montagenet - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00649001102471C0D	2471	target Montagenet - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00649001102472C0D	2472	target Montagenet - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00649001102473C0D	2473	target Montagenet - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00649001102474C0D	2474	target Montagenet - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00649001102475C0D	2475	target Montagenet - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3183MH00649001102476C0D	2476	target Montagenet - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00299	Focus Merges	3183MH00193001102477R0D	2477	target Montagenet - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3183 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2469-2476 - best focus image product
		3183MH00193001102478S0D	2478	target Montagenet - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3183 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2469-2476 - range map product
		3183MH00193001102479W0D	2479	target Montagenet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3183 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2459-2466 - best focus image product
		3183MH00193001102480S0D	2480	target Montagenet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3183 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2459-2466 - range map product
		3183MH00193001102481R0D	2481	target Montagenet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3183 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2449-2456 - best focus image product
		3183MH00193001102482S0D	2482	target Montagenet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3183 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2449-2456 - range map product

updated: 27_July_2021

Sol 3185 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	23 Jul 21
camera positions:	2
total parent images:	25
focus merges performed:	2
total focus merge products:	4
total parent images + focus merge products:	29

MAHLI imaged the target Javerlhac and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00705	Javerlhac ~25 cm standoff	3185MH000706001102483CDD	2483	autofocus sub-frame for target Javerlhac - standoff near 25 cm
		3185MH000706001102484CDD	2484	target Javerlhac - standoff near 25 cm
		3185MH000706001102485CDD	2485	target Javerlhac - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00803	Javerlhac stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff	3185MH000803001102486CDD	2486	autofocus sub-frame for target Javerlhac - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3185MH000803001102487CDD	2487	target Javerlhac - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3185MH000803001102488CDD	2488	target Javerlhac - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3185MH000803001102489CDD	2489	target Javerlhac - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3185MH000803001102490CDD	2490	target Javerlhac - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3185MH000803001102491CDD	2491	target Javerlhac - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3185MH000803001102492CDD	2492	target Javerlhac - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3185MH000803001102493CDD	2493	target Javerlhac - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3185MH000803001102494CDD	2494	target Javerlhac - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3185MH000803001102495CDD	2495	target Javerlhac - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3185MH000803001102496CDD	2496	target Javerlhac - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00803	Javerlhac stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	3185MH000803001102497CDD
3185MH000803001102498CDD	2498			target Javerlhac - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
3185MH000803001102499CDD	2499			target Javerlhac - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure
3185MH000803001102500CDD	2500			target Javerlhac - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3185MH000803001102501CDD	2501			target Javerlhac - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
3185MH000803001102502CDD	2502			target Javerlhac - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3185MH000803001102503CDD	2503			target Javerlhac - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
3185MH000803001102504CDD	2504			target Javerlhac - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
3185MH000803001102505CDD	2505			target Javerlhac - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
3185MH000803001102506CDD	2506			target Javerlhac - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3185MH000803001102507CDD	2507			target Javerlhac - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00265	Focus Merges			3185MH0002650001102508R0D
		3185MH0002650001102509S0D	2509	target Javerlhac - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3185 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2500-2507 - range map product
		3185MH0002650001102510R0D	2510	target Javerlhac - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3185 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2489-2496 - best focus image product
		3185MH0002650001102511S0D	2511	target Javerlhac - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3185 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2489-2496 - range map product

updated: 10_August_2021

Sol 3187 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	28 Jul 21
camera position	6
total parent images	64
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	64

MAHLI imaged the target Chaffour after DRT and the target Le_Manet.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Chaffour after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3187MH000190000110251200	2512	autofocus sub-frame for target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3187MH000190000110251300	2513	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Chaffour after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3187MH000182000110251400	2514	autofocus sub-frame for target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3187MH000182000110251500	2515	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3187MH000182000110251600	2516	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000182000110251700	2517	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000182000110251800	2518	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000182000110251900	2519	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000182000110252000	2520	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000182000110252100	2521	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000182000110252200	2522	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000182000110252300	2523	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Chaffour after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3187MH000182000110252400	2524	autofocus sub-frame for target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3187MH000182000110252500	2525	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3187MH000182000110252600	2526	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000182000110252700	2527	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000182000110252800	2528	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000182000110252900	2529	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000182000110253000	2530	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000182000110253100	2531	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000182000110253200	2532	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000182000110253300	2533	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Chaffour after DRT ~2 cm standoff	3187MH000302000110253400	2534	autofocus sub-frame for target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3187MH000302000110253500	2535	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3187MH000302000110253600	2536	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000302000110253700	2537	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000302000110253800	2538	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000302000110253900	2539	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000302000110254000	2540	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000302000110254100	2541	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000302000110254200	2542	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000302000110254300	2543	target Chaffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Le_Manet ~25 cm standoff	3187MH000190000110254400	2544	autofocus sub-frame for target Le_Manet - standoff near 25 cm
		3187MH000190000110254500	2545	target Le_Manet - standoff near 25 cm
mN00224	Le_Manet stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3187MH000224000110254600	2546	autofocus sub-frame for target Le_Manet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3187MH000224000110254700	2547	target Le_Manet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3187MH000224000110254800	2548	target Le_Manet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000224000110254900	2549	target Le_Manet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000224000110255000	2550	target Le_Manet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000224000110255100	2551	target Le_Manet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000224000110255200	2552	target Le_Manet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000224000110255300	2553	target Le_Manet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000224000110255400	2554	target Le_Manet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000224000110255500	2555	target Le_Manet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Le_Manet stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3187MH000224000110255600	2556	autofocus sub-frame for target Le_Manet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3187MH000224000110255700	2557	target Le_Manet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3187MH000224000110255800	2558	target Le_Manet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000224000110255900	2559	target Le_Manet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000224000110256000	2560	target Le_Manet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000224000110256100	2561	target Le_Manet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000224000110256200	2562	target Le_Manet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000224000110256300	2563	target Le_Manet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000224000110256400	2564	target Le_Manet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000224000110256500	2565	target Le_Manet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00176	Le_Manet ~2 cm standoff	3187MH000176000110256600	2566	autofocus sub-frame for target Le_Manet - standoff near 2 cm
		3187MH000176000110256700	2567	target Le_Manet - standoff near 2 cm
		3187MH000176000110256800	2568	target Le_Manet - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000176000110256900	2569	target Le_Manet - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000176000110257000	2570	target Le_Manet - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000176000110257100	2571	target Le_Manet - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000176000110257200	2572	target Le_Manet - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3187MH000176000110257300	2573	target Le_Manet - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
3187MH000176000110257400	2574	target Le_Manet - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3187MH000176000110257500	2575	target Le_Manet - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 27_July_2021

Sol 3188 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	25 Jul 21
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	6
total focus merge products:	12
total parent images + focus merge products:	12

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 3187 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	3188MH001630001102576000	2576	target Ie_Manet - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3187 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2568-2575 - best focus image product
		3188MH001630001102577500	2577	target Ie_Manet - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3187 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2568-2575 - range map product
		3188MH001630001102578000	2578	target Ie_Manet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3187 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2558-2565 - best focus image product
		3188MH001630001102579500	2579	target Ie_Manet - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3187 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2558-2565 - range map product
		3188MH001630001102580000	2580	target Ie_Manet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3187 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2548-2555 - best focus image product
		3188MH001630001102581500	2581	target Ie_Manet - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3187 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2548-2555 - range map product
		3188MH001630001102582000	2582	target Chauffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3187 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2536-2543 - best focus image product
		3188MH001630001102583500	2583	target Chauffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3187 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2536-2543 - range map product
		3188MH001630001102584000	2584	target Chauffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3187 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2526-2533 - best focus image product
		3188MH001630001102585500	2585	target Chauffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3187 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2526-2533 - range map product
		3188MH001630001102586000	2586	target Chauffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3187 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2516-2523 - best focus image product
		3188MH001630001102587500	2587	target Chauffour - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3187 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2516-2523 - range map product

updated: 11_August_2021

Sol 3190 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27 Jul 21
camera positions	8
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the target Fressignas and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00706	Fressignas ~25 cm standoff	3190MH0007060001102588C0D	2588	autofocus sub-frame for target Fressignas - standoff near 25 cm		
		3190MH000706001102589C0D	2589	target Fressignas - standoff near 25 cm		
		3190MH0007060021102590C0D	2590	target Fressignas - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mN00721	Fressignas ~5 cm standoff	3190MH0007210001102591C0D	2591	autofocus sub-frame for target Fressignas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3190MH0007210011102592C0D	2592	target Fressignas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3190MH0007210021102593C0D	2593	target Fressignas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3190MH0007210031102594C0D	2594	target Fressignas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3190MH0007210041102595C0D	2595	target Fressignas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3190MH0007210051102596C0D	2596	target Fressignas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3190MH0007210061102597C0D	2597	target Fressignas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3190MH0007210071102598C0D	2598	target Fressignas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3190MH0007210081102599C0D	2599	target Fressignas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3190MH0007210091102600C0D	2600	target Fressignas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3190MH0007210101102601C0D	2601	target Fressignas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00722	Fressignas stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3190MH0007210001102602C0D	2602	autofocus sub-frame for target Fressignas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3190MH0007210011102603C0D	2603	target Fressignas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
3190MH0007210021102604C0D	2604			target Fressignas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
3190MH0007210031102605C0D	2605			target Fressignas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3190MH0007210041102606C0D	2606			target Fressignas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3190MH0007210051102607C0D	2607			target Fressignas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3190MH0007210061102608C0D	2608			target Fressignas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3190MH0007210071102609C0D	2609			target Fressignas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3190MH0007210081102610C0D	2610			target Fressignas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3190MH0007210091102611C0D	2611			target Fressignas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3190MH0007210101102612C0D	2612			target Fressignas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00265	Focus Merges			3190MH0002650001102613R0D	2613	target Fressignas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3190 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2605-2612 - best focus image product
				3190MH0002650001102614S0D	2614	target Fressignas - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3190 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2605-2612 - range map product
		3190MH0002650001102615R0D	2615	target Fressignas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3190 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2594-2601 - best focus image product		
		3190MH0002650001102616S0D	2616	target Fressignas - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3190 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2594-2601 - range map product		

updated: 03_August_2021

Sol 3192 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	29 Jul 21
camera positions	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the targets Champeaux and Eyszerac and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Champeaux ~25 cm standoff	3192MH0019000110261700D	2617	autofocus sub-frame for target Champeaux - standoff near 25 cm
		3192MH0019000110261800D	2618	target Champeaux - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Champeaux stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3192MH0018200110261900D	2619	autofocus sub-frame for target Champeaux - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3192MH0018200110262000D	2620	target Champeaux - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3192MH0018200110262100D	2621	target Champeaux - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0018200110262200D	2622	target Champeaux - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0018200110262300D	2623	target Champeaux - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0018200110262400D	2624	target Champeaux - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0018200110262500D	2625	target Champeaux - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0018200110262600D	2626	target Champeaux - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0018200110262700D	2627	target Champeaux - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0018200110262800D	2628	target Champeaux - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Champeaux stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3192MH0018200110262900D	2629	autofocus sub-frame for target Champeaux - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3192MH0018200110263000D	2630	target Champeaux - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3192MH0018200110263100D	2631	target Champeaux - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0018200110263200D	2632	target Champeaux - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0018200110263300D	2633	target Champeaux - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0018200110263400D	2634	target Champeaux - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0018200110263500D	2635	target Champeaux - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0018200110263600D	2636	target Champeaux - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0018200110263700D	2637	target Champeaux - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0018200110263800D	2638	target Champeaux - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00359	Eyszerac ~25 cm standoff	3192MH0035900110263900D	2639	autofocus sub-frame for target Eyszerac - standoff near 25 cm
		3192MH0035900110264000D	2640	target Eyszerac - standoff near 25 cm
		3192MH0035900110264100D	2641	target Eyszerac - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0035900110264200D	2642	target Eyszerac - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0035900110264300D	2643	target Eyszerac - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0035900110264400D	2644	target Eyszerac - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0035900110264500D	2645	target Eyszerac - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0035900110264600D	2646	target Eyszerac - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0035900110264700D	2647	target Eyszerac - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3192MH0035900110264800D	2648	target Eyszerac - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00189	Focus Merges	3192MH00193000110264900D	2649	target Eyszerac - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3192 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2641-2648 - best focus image product
		3192MH00193000110265000D	2650	target Eyszerac - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3192 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2641-2648 - range map product
		3192MH00193000110265100D	2651	target Champeaux - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3192 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2631-2638 - best focus image product
		3192MH00193000110265200D	2652	target Champeaux - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3192 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2631-2638 - range map product
		3192MH00193000110265300D	2653	target Champeaux - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3192 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2621-2628 - best focus image product
3192MH00193000110265400D	2654	target Champeaux - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3192 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2621-2628 - range map product		

7 Definitions, conventions, and acronyms

7.1 Definitions and conventions

absolute focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a commanded (manual) focus setting. The starting focus position (a stepper motor count), and the incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack, are specified by instrument commanding.

best focus image product

A *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *best focus image product* is a color JPEG that combines the in-focus (or closest to in-focus) elements of the up to 8 *parent images* into a single image. The onboard focus merge software also creates a *range map product*.

focus merge product

Using the methods described by Edgett *et al.* (2012), *focus merge products* are created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. Two products are created, a *best focus image product* and a *range map product*.

MAHLI toolframe +X distance

Same as *standoff distance*. See *standoff distance*.

parent and child images

Every MAHLI image has a *parent image*, the picture originally commanded to be acquired. Upon command, the parent image can spawn children (each a *child image*) onboard the instrument. Examples of children include *thumbnail images*, focus merge products, and any version of the image that is compressed differently than the parent (Edgett *et al.* 2012). While a parent can be an image that was compressed during image acquisition, our best practice since landing on Mars has been to acquire and store (onboard the instrument) most MAHLI images in uncompressed 8-bit form. An uncompressed 8-bit parent image can be commanded for compression some time after acquisition and storage, whereas a parent that was compressed at the time of acquisition cannot be further compressed onboard the instrument. When a parent is stored onboard in uncompressed form, it can be used to create multiple versions of the image, each time with a different compression scheme, for downlink to Earth. Thus, if the image received is over-compressed, we have the option to retrieve it again (as many times as necessary) in a less compressed form. Indeed, the majority of MAHLI images received from Mars have been losslessly compressed children of an uncompressed, 8-bit parent.

range

Used here in the context of describing a focus merge range map product, this term refers to the distance between the front lens element and in-focus elements of the imaged subject in a given MAHLI focus merge product. As each MAHLI focus stack is acquired at a fixed *working distance*, the range denotes the distance between the camera and the relief elements of the target (*i.e.*, subject), as indicated by grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) values in the range map product.

range map product

A grayscale JPEG image *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *range map product* accompanies a *best focus image product*. The grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) can be correlated with knowledge of instrument focus, *working distance*, *range*, and pixel scale.

RATIONALE_DESC

The term, RATIONALE_DESC, comes from the NASA PDS archivists. The RATIONALE_DESC for a given MAHLI image is a text description of the rationale or purpose behind the acquisition of a given MAHLI parent image or onboard focus merge product. Each parent image RATIONALE_DESC provides information that the MAHLI team desired to communicate to data users, such as the intended image target, intended working or standoff distance, intended purpose of the image (e.g., stereo, mosaic, autofocus sub-frame, range-finding), image position in a focus stack, as well as information regarding how the image supports observations made by other MSL science instruments, especially APXS and ChemCam. The RATIONALE_DESC for a focus merge product tells the user which images were merged (on what sol they were acquired and images of which CDPIDs were merged), as well as the focus merge product type (best focus or range map product).

relative focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a starting focus position determined by a preceding instrument command. Usually, this is a focus setting based upon a focus position determined by a preceding autofocus command. The incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack is specified by instrument commanding.

RP distance

RP refers to Rover Planners, the personnel who drive the Curiosity rover and operate its robotic arm. RP distance is equivalent to *standoff distance*. See definition of *standoff distance*.

sol

A Martian day; duration of ~1.027 Earth days.

Sol

A specific Martian sol during the MSL Curiosity mission. Because it landed during local afternoon, the sol that Curiosity arrived on Mars was designated Sol 0 and the first full sol after landing was Sol 1.

standoff distance

Also known as the MAHLI *toolframe distance* and *RP distance*, this is range between the subject photographed and the Y, Z plane defined by the two MAHLI contact sensor probe tips when they are not in contact with a surface. In the MAHLI toolframe, the X axis is equivalent to the instrument's optic (z) axis; the distance between the Y, Z plane and the subject is +X; the -X-axis goes from the Y, Z plane into the camera. *Standoff distance* and *RP distance* are equivalent to the +X MAHLI toolframe distance. MAHLI *standoff distance* is 1.9 cm less than *working distance*.

thumbnail images

Reduced-size versions of MAHLI *parent images* and *focus merge products*, approximately 1/8th size in terms of pixel dimensions. Under most circumstances, a *thumbnail image* is returned to Earth for every *parent image* acquired or *focus merge product* created, whether a full-size version of the *parent image* (or a *child image*) or *focus merge product* is returned or not.

working distance

A photography term that refers to the range between the front lens element of a camera and the subject imaged. MAHLI working distance is 1.9 cm greater than the toolframe (also known as standoff or RP) distance.

7.2 Acronyms

APXS

Alpha Particle X-ray Spectrometer (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CDPID or MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID

Each MAHLI parent image acquired or onboard focus merge product created and stored in the instrument's DEA flash memory is assigned a Camera Data Product ID (CDPID). This identifier, plus the time at which (or sol on which) the data were acquired, uniquely identify each image. The CDPID and sol are incorporated into the image ID. Data acquired by the camera but not stored in the DEA have less unique CDPIDs; these acquisitions have generally been rare and easy for the operations team to track (*i.e.*, 12 such images were obtained during Interplanetary Cruise, only one such image was obtained during the first 1000 sols of operations on Mars).

ChemCam

Chemistry Camera; Laser Induced Breakdown Spectrometer (LIBS) and Remote Microscopic Imager (RMI) (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CheMin

Chemistry and Mineralogy x-ray diffraction (XRD) and x-ray fluorescence (XRF) sample analysis investigation (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CHIMRA

Collection and Handling for Interior Martian Rock Analysis (sample handling and processing subsystem on Curiosity's robotic arm)

DEA

Digital Electronics Assembly, the MAHLI electronics housed inside Curiosity's rover body.

DN

data number (image pixel value)

DOF

image depth of field

DRT

Dust Removal Tool (wire brush tool on Curiosity's robotic arm)

EDR

Experiment Data Record

Hazcam(s)

Hazard cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

ID or image ID

Image identifier (NASA PDS image identifier for MAHLI images and focus merge products).

JPL-Caltech

Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, California, USA

MAHLI

Mars Hand Lens Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MARDI

Mars Descent Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-34 (also M-34 and M34)

34 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-100 (also M-100 and M100)

100 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MSL

Mars Science Laboratory

MSSS

Malin Space Science Systems, San Diego, California, USA

NASA

National Aeronautics and Space Administration (USA space agency)

Navcam(s)

Navigation cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

PDS

Planetary Data System (NASA planetary science data archives)

QMS

Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

RDR

Reduced Data Record

REMS

Rover Environment and Monitoring Station (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

SAM

Sample Analysis at Mars (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

TLS

Tunable Laser Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

USA

United States of America

UTC

Coordinated Universal Time

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